

REPORTE DE CITAS

Jefatura de Servicios Especializados de Información

INVESTIGADOR:
INSTITUCIÓN:
UNIDAD ACADÉMICA:
ID TRABAJADOR BUAP:
ORCID:
AUTHOR H-INDEX:
AUTHOR H-INDEX:

Hernández Gracidas Carlos Arturo
Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla
Facultad de Ciencias Físico Matemáticas
COL305600
0000-0003-0267-6306
5 (SCOPUS)
(Web of Science)

TOTAL DE CITAS SCOPUS - WoS:
TOTAL CITAS TIPO A:
TOTAL DE CITAS B Y C:
TOTAL DE CITAS GOOGLE SCHOLAR:
TOTAL DE CITAS TIPO A GS:
TOTAL DE CITAS B Y C GS:
TOTAL FINAL:
PERIODO DE BÚSQUEDA:
FUENTE:

531
472
59
726
637
89
1257
2007 - 2026
Scopus, Web of Science

bibliotecas.buap.mx

Elaboró: Silvana Georgina Guzmán Ramírez
e-mail: silvana.guzman@correo.buap.mx
Revisó: Laura Fraguela Birka
e-mail: laura.fraguela@correo.buap.mx

||1.0|13022026145254-3358|Hernández Gracidas Carlos Arturo|COL305600|Facultad de Ciencias Físico Matemáticas|26|0000-0003-0267-6306|531|472|59|2007 - 2026|2026-02-13 14:52:54|3358|DK16-JR47-MFHO-65YG-39RQ||

qC5EnvMHIWLTNw3hWWCArHjWV0APBrAXOCJQL/Wc9pj+6wpQCFhEe+zLAu3AuyfIAQeluxHYSd/NQzKuhU VLf17Lr71NmktRuhw15XU7ytMwloGJ1EYHmgDendX6u+zikKamgIM3Duc4XV0pCnGzseOmskoa07HPYGY GWMwEbsiu22I5bs4lq7LryRwOXv0ZZSe2ZSN05Kj4V8+QLvGgTmxnWmyoLler2MyRNSQDU8ZvgUYgAbPh 9Zy+rfQqk4m7EuY5lPgoApXdE3kpNblA18Auc4Mdyd2UP6DYQ6ngBgw8shl6b00C6Xr9SlnbA5arLxKrc5MHI aG3RfnrJY2b45hTX/Juwp8l8d7/BcpQbok2p99SGYn1ZaPCK77k61vwwhOG5gFerguNLgaOMh+MFQwmSq h/4dzRg31HhgkW4JnEaCoRcNNIDujyG2pvn7K0H3NpFnyO/KJtBiKB9ae6VrCrMQjPUgax8X9Gjclx1SOX1n2F 68OU9Hdf12

DOCUMENTOS CON CITAS ORIGINALES

1.- Investigating HLB control strategies using Genetic Algorithms: A two-orchard model approach with ACP dispersal

Anzo-Hernandez A., Gimenez-Mujica U.J., Gracidas C.A.H., Oliveros-Oliveros J.J.
2025, Computers and Electronics in Agriculture

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Research on a complex start-up control strategy for power-shift tractors based on rule mapping and multi-mode model predictive control	Lu L.-Q., Zhang Z.-P., Zhang G.-L., Yang H.-R., Zhu Z.-X., Song Z.-H., Zhai Z.-Q., Wang J.-H., Zhang C.-C.	2026	Computers and Electronics in Agriculture

2.- Optimizing control parameters for Huanglongbing disease in citrus orchards using SAIR-SI compartmental model, epidemic final size, and genetic algorithms

Anzo Hernandez A., Gimenez Mujica U.J., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Oliveros Oliveros J.J.
2025, Journal of Mathematical Biology

Citas: 3

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	A Nonlinear Delay Mathematical Model for Predicting Chlamydia Dynamics and Intervention Effects	Zeb S., Mohd Yatim S.A., Kamran A., Zulfiqar S., Rafiq M., Noor N.M.	2025	Communication in Biomathematical Sciences
2	Natural population dynamics of Asian citrus psyllid, <i>Diaphorina citri</i> , and its control based on pheromone trapping	Cardona-Salgado D., Dumont Y., Vasilieva O.	2025	Mathematical Biosciences
3	Detection of Citrus Huanglongbing in Natural Field Conditions Using an Enhanced YOLO11 Framework	Cao L., Xiao W., Hu Z., Li X., Wu Z.	2025	Mathematics

3.- Diagnosis and Study of Mechanical Vibrations in Cargo Vehicles Using ISO 2631-1:1997

Medina Santiago A., Orozco Torres J.A., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Garduza S.H., Franco J.D.
2023, Sensors

Citas: 7

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Guide to the Effects of Vibration on Health-Quantitative or Qualitative Occupational Health and Safety Prevention Guidance? A Scoping Review	Johanning, Eckardt; Turcot, Alice	2025	VIBRATION
2	The Effects of Whole-Body Vibration on Humans from a Physics and Reaction Speed Perspective	Lady, Lovely; Herodian, Sam	2025	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ACOUSTICS AND VIBRATION
3	Hybrid Supervised and Reinforcement Learning for Motion-Sickness-Aware Path Tracking in Autonomous Vehicles	Lv, Yukang; Chen, Yi; Chen, Zigu; Fan, Yuze; Tao, Yongchao; Zhao, Rui; Gao, Fei	2025	SENSORS

4	Design of Parameter Adaptive Suspension Controllers with Kalman Filter for Ride Comfort Enhancement and Motion Sickness Reduction	Kim, Jinwoo; Yim, Seongjin	2025	APPLIED SCIENCES-BASEL
5	Train-Induced Vibration Analysis and Isolation Trench Measures in Metro Depot Structures	Zhao, Shusong; Lu, Chenglin; Shen, Jiayu; Zhao, Mi	2025	APPLIED SCIENCES-BASEL
6	Dynamics of Vibration in Crane Operation: An Elementary Modal and Harmonic Analysis	Silva, Ricardo Luis Alves; Alves, Kleber Goncalves Bezerra; da Costa, Jose angelo Peixoto; Ochoa, Alvaro Antonio Villa; Michima, Paula Suemy Arruda; Leite, Gustavo de Novaes Pires; Caldas, Allysson Macario Araujo	2025	PROCESSES
7	Analytical Investigation of Vertical Force Control in In-Wheel Motors for Enhanced Ride Comfort	Bunlapyanan, Chanoknan; Chantranuwathana, Sunhapos; Phanomchoeng, Gridsada	2024	APPLIED SCIENCES-BASEL

4.- Efficient deep learning architectures for fast identification of bacterial strains in resource-constrained devices

Gallardo Garcia R., Jarquin Rodriguez S., Beltran Martinez B., Hernandez Gracidas C., Martinez Torres R.
2022, Multimedia Tools and Applications

Citas: 9

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	A Deep Learning-Based Approach to Microscopic Bacterial Species Classification	Kotwal S., Manhas J., Arif T., Sharma V.	2026	Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems
2	MACNeXt-Based Bacteria Species Detection	Aytac O., Senol F.F., Kivrak T., Toraman Z.A., Gun M.V., Goktas O.F., Dogan S., Tuncer T.	2025	Microorganisms
3	Use of artificial intelligence in the prediction of microbial species	Rahiya M., Kumari R., Vivekanand V., Pareek N.	2025	Artificial Intelligence in Microbiology Environmental Food Plant and Clinical Microbiology
4	Dilated multilevel fused network for virus classification using transmission electron microscopy images	Usman M., Sultan H., Hong J.S., Kim S.G., Akram R., Gondal H.A.H., Tariq M.H., Park K.R.	2024	Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence
5	A Deep Learning Model for Bacterial Classification Using Big Transfer (BIT)	Visitsattapong S., Bunkum M., Pintavirooj C., Paing M.P.	2024	IEEE Access
6	Deep Learning-Based Automated Approach for Classifying Bacterial Images	Abougarair A.J., Oun A.A., Sawan S.I., Ma'arif A.	2024	International Journal of Robotics and Control Systems
7	Comparison of Efficient Deep Learning Architecture for Lactobacillus Species Identification	Rusmawati D.A., Ariawan I., Firmanda A.	2024	Karbala International Journal of Modern Science
8	Knowing the Unknown: Open-set Bacteria Classification in Gram Stain Microscopic Images	Alhammad S., Lovell B.C.	2023	Proceedings of the International Joint Conference on Neural Networks

9	Machine learning algorithms in microbial classification: a comparative analysis	Wu, Yuandi; Gadsden, S. Andrew	2023	FRONTIERS IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
---	---	--------------------------------	------	--------------------------------------

5.- Stable Numerical Identification of Sources in Non-Homogeneous Media

Conde Mones J.J., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Morin Castillo M.M., Oliveros Oliveros J.J., Juarez Valencia L.H.
2022, Mathematics

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	An Underwater Passive Electric Field Positioning Method Based on Scalar Potential	Zhang, Yi; Chen, Cong; Sun, Jiaqing; Qiu, Mingjie; Wu, Xu	2024	MATHEMATICS

6.- A SHA-256 Hybrid-Redundancy Hardware Architecture for Detecting and Correcting Errors

Alfredo-Badillo I., Morales-Sandoval M., Medina-Santiago A., Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Lobato-Baez M., Morales-Rosales L.A.
2022, Sensors

Citas: 8

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Efficient FPGA-Based Implementation of SHA-256 Hash Function for Higher Throughput	Lawhale P.R., Kale S.N.	2025	Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering
2	FPGA Implementation of Compact Architecture for Lightweight Hash Algorithm for Resource Constrained Devices	Lawhale P.R., Kale S.N., Kasturiwale H., Thakare Y.N.	2025	Communications on Applied Nonlinear Analysis
3	A Comprehensive Analysis of Cryptographic Algorithms: Evaluating Security, Efficiency, and Future Challenges	Ramakrishna D., Ali Shaik M.	2025	IEEE Access
4	A Survey of Blockchain Applicability, Challenges, and Key Threats	Morar C.D., Popescu D.E.	2024	Computers
5	SignChain: Enhanced Digital Signature System Security with HashIDs in Blockchain	Darmawan I., Maulana F., Rahmatulloh A., Gunawan R., Rizal R.	2024	2024 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Blockchain Cloud Computing and Data Analytics Icoabcd 2024
6	HW/SW Co-Design of the Secure Hash Function SHA-256	Issad M., Anane N., Guenfoud N., Debyeche M.	2024	Icaee 2024 International Conference on Advanced Electrical Engineering 2024
7	Securing the Cyber Resilience of a Blockchain-Based Railroad Non-Stop Customs Clearance System	Kim S., Kim D.	2023	Sensors
8	Intelligent Crypto Currency Mining Farm for E-Vehicle	Rajasekar T., Ahila A., Dhanya G., Dharsana K.	2023	Proceedings of the 2023 2nd International Conference on Augmented Intelligence and Sustainable Systems, ICAISS 2023

7.- Searching for memory-lighter architectures for OCR-augmented image captioning

Gallardo-García R., Beltran-Martinez B., Hernandez-Gracidas C., Vilarino-Ayala D.

2022, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	EAES: Effective Augmented Embedding Spaces for Text-Based Image Captioning	Khang Nguyen; Bui, Doanh C.; Truc Trinh; Vo, Nguyen D.	2022	IEEE ACCESS

8.- Cmos implementation of anns based on analog optimization of n-dimensional objective functions

Medina-Santiago A., Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Morales-Rosales L.A., Algreto-Badillo I., Garcia M.A., Torres J.A.O.

2021, Sensors

Citas: 5

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Breast cancer detection and classification: A study on the specification and implementation of multilayer perceptron analog artificial neural networks	Silas K.L.T., Djimeli-Tsajio Alain B., Thierry N., Jean-Pierre L.T., Ejuh G.W.	2025	Computers in Biology and Medicine
2	Breast Cancer Diagnosis with Machine Learning Using Feed-Forward Multilayer Perceptron Analog Artificial Neural Network	Alain B.D.-T., Silas K.L.T., Jean-Pierre L.T., Thierry N., Ejuh G.W.	2024	International Journal of Electrical and Electronic Engineering and Telecommunications
3	Study of the Complexity of CMOS Neural Network Implementations Featuring Heart Rate Detection	Baryczkowski P., Szczepaniak S., Matykiewicz N., Perz K., Szczesny S.	2023	Electronics (Switzerland)
4	Analog Implementation of Neural Network	Desai, Vraj; Darji, Pallavi G.	2023	SOFT COMPUTING AND ITS ENGINEERING APPLICATIONS, ICISOFTCOMP 2022
5	Neuron Network with a Synapse of CMOS transistor and Anti-Parallel Memristors for Low power Implementations	Keerthy Rai V., Sakthivel R.	2022	Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers

9.- Reactive obstacle-avoidance systems for wheeled mobile robots based on artificial intelligence

Medina-Santiago A., Morales-Rosales L.A., Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Algreto-Badillo I., Pano-Azucena A.D., Torres J.A.O.

2021, Applied Sciences (Switzerland)

Citas: 8

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Neural network control insights and strategies in low-cost educational platforms: A pneumatic levitation case study	Tello-Monroy J.M., Acosta-Amaya G.A., Ceballos-Ramirez R.A., Jimenez-Builes J.A.	2026	Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence
2	ROS-Based Navigation and Obstacle Avoidance: A Study of Architectures, Methods, and Trends	Wei Z., Wang S., Chen K., Wang F.	2025	Sensors
3	Natural Language Understanding for Navigation of Service Robots in Low-Resource Domains and Languages: Scenarios in Spanish and Nahuatl	Hernandez A., Ortega-Mendoza R.M., Villatoro-Tello E., Camacho-Bello C.J., Perez-Cortes O.	2024	Mathematics

4	Implementation of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) Algorithm for Autonomous Robot	Dewi T.K., Saptaji K., Simarmata A., Fikri M.R.	2024	Journal of Mechanical Engineering
5	Path Planning for Robotic Fish Based on Improved PRM Algorithm Fused with DWA Algorithm	Zhou G., Wang C., Gan J., Li X.	2024	Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering
6	LiDAR-Based Obstacle Avoidance With Autonomous Vehicles: A Comprehensive Review	Leong P.Y., Ahmad N.S.	2024	IEEE Access
7	Intelligent Motion Control System for the Mobile Robotic Platform	Tsmots I., Teslyuk V., Opotyak Y., Rabyk V.	2023	CEUR Workshop Proceedings
8	The Impact of the Distance Sensors Orientation on the Obstacle Avoidance Ability of the Robot	Zhang G., Zhu Z.	2022	Proceedings - 2022 International Conference on Machine Learning and Intelligent Systems Engineering, MLISE 2022

10.- Towards Multilingual Image Captioning Models that Can Read

Gallardo Garcia R., Beltran Martinez B., Hernandez Gracidas C., Vilarino Ayala D.

2021, Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Review of Recent Datasets Used in Image Captioning Models	Srivastava S.	2024	5th International Conference on Sustainable Communication Networks and Application Icsna 2024 Proceedings
2	EAES: Effective Augmented Embedding Spaces for Text-Based Image Captioning	Nguyen K., Bui D.C., Trinh T., Vo N.D.	2022	IEEE Access

11.- An FPGA-based analysis of trade-offs in the presence of ill-conditioning and different precision levels in computations

Alfredo-Badillo I., Conde-Mones J.J., Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Morin-Castillo M.M., Oliveros-Oliveros J.J., Feregrino-Urbe C.

2020, PLoS ONE

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	A Hierarchical Optimization Method for Deformation Force Monitoring Layout of Annular Parts	Dai K., Liu C., Wang E., Zhao Z., Salonitis K., Li Y.	2025	Transactions of Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics
2	Acceleration of Nuclear Reactor Simulation and Uncertainty Quantification Using Low-Precision Arithmetic	Cherezov A., Vasiliev A., Ferroukhi H.	2023	Applied Sciences (Switzerland)

12.- A fuzzy petri net model for assessing analogical reasoning in children ranging from 5 to 8 years old

Alberto Morales-Rosales L., Algreto-Badillo I., Lobato-Baez M., Hernandez-Gracidas C., Rodriguez-Rangel H.

2020, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Modeling and Optimization of Multi-Section Management Decision-making Information Process Based on Petri Net	Zhang Q.Z., Zhao B., Li X.	2021	Proceedings - 2021 2nd International Seminar on Artificial Intelligence, Networking and Information Technology, AINIT 2021

13.- Real time FPGA-Ann architecture for outdoor obstacle detection focused in road safety

Algreto-Badillo I., Morales-Rosales L.A., Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Cruz-Victoria J.C., Pacheco-Bautista D., Morales-Sandoval M.

2019, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems

Citas: 8

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Assessing YOLO models for real-time object detection in urban environments for advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS)	Ayachi R., Said Y., Afif M., Alshammari A., Hleili M., Ben Abdelali A.	2025	Alexandria Engineering Journal
2	An Intelligent FPGA-Based Vehicle Accident Reporting System for Real-Time Emergency Response	Choudhary S., Jha A.K., Kumar S., Bangra R., Gupta A., Gupta A., Sen S., Raman A., Hamid S.	2025	International Conference on Electronics AI and Computing Innovating for A Sustainable and Connected Future Eaic 2025
3	A Method for Obstacle Detection in Radiotherapy Room Based on Improved YOLOv5	Zhang Y., Liu Z., Wei Z., Wu X., Qian J.	2024	2024 International Conference on Image Processing Computer Vision and Machine Learning Iciml 2024
4	A CMOS Image Readout Circuit with On-Chip Defective Pixel Detection and Correction	Lopez-Portilla B.M., Valenzuela W., Zarkesh-Ha P., Figueroa M.	2023	Sensors
5	System-independent irradiance sensorless ANN-based MPPT for photovoltaic systems in electric vehicles	Cortes B., Tapia R., Flores J.J.	2021	Energies
6	An automatic assessment of road condition from aerial imagery using modified VGG architecture in faster-RCNN framework	Malini A., Priyadharshini P., Sabeena S.	2021	Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems
7	Fixed point multi-bit approximate adder based convolutional neural network accelerator for digit classification inference	Nagarajan M., Sasikumar A., Muralidharan D., Rajappa M.	2020	Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems
8	Intelligent, smart and scalable cyber-physical systems	Vijayakumar V., Subramaniaswamy V., Abawajy J., Yang L.	2019	Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems

14.- On-road obstacle detection video system for traffic accident prevention

Rosales L.A.M., Algreto Badillo I., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Rangel H.R., Lobato Baez M.

2018, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems

Citas: 8

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Improved DAB-DETR model for irregular traffic obstacles detection in vision based driving environment perception scenario	Yang J., Zhang H., Zhou Y., Guo Z., Lin F.	2025	Applied Intelligence
2	Proactive Obstacle Monitoring and Prevention System	Ramakrishnan P., Muthumani P., Karthi A.S., Kavinesh C., Kavinraj S.	2025	Proceedings of 5th International Conference on Trends in Material Science and Inventive Materials Ictmim 2025
3	In-vehicle edge system for real-time dashcam video analysis	Lee S., King J., Lee Y.C., Han H., Kang S.	2025	Internet of Things the Netherlands
4	Nighttime trajectory extraction framework for traffic investigations at intersections based on improved SSD and DeepSort	Hu X., Zhang Q.	2023	Signal, Image and Video Processing
5	Small obstacles detection on roads scenes using semantic segmentation for the safe navigation of autonomous vehicles	Yasmin S., Durrani M.Y., Gillani S., Bukhari M., Maqsood M., Zghaibeh M.	2022	Journal of Electronic Imaging
6	Vision Transformer for Detecting Critical Situations and Extracting Functional Scenario for Automated Vehicle Safety Assessment	Kang M., Lee W., Hwang K., Yoon Y.	2022	Sustainability (Switzerland)
7	An automatic assessment of road condition from aerial imagery using modified VGG architecture in faster-RCNN framework	Malini A., Priyadharshini P., Sabeena S.	2021	Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems
8	Improvement of disability rights via geographic information science	Kocaman S., Ozdemir N.	2020	Sustainability (Switzerland)

15.- The Windows-Users and -Intruder simulations Logs dataset (WUIL): An experimental framework for masquerade detection mechanisms

Camina J.B., Hernandez-Gracidas C., Monroy R., Trejo L.

2014, Expert Systems with Applications

Citas: 26

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Insights into user behavioral-based insider threat detection: systematic review	Kamatchi K., Uma E.	2025	International Journal of Information Security
2	A Survey of Insider Threat Analysis and Defense Solutions	Sun D., Liu M., Li M., Wang X., Shi Z., Liu P., Li N.	2025	Journal of Cyber Security

3	Insider Threat Defense Strategies: Survey and Knowledge Integration	Song C., Zhang J., Ma L., Hu X., Zheng J., Yang L.	2024	Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics
4	Addressing insider attacks via forensic-ready risk management	Daubner L., Macak M., Matulevicius R., Buhnova B., Maksovic S., Pitner T.	2023	Journal of Information Security and Applications
5	Host-Based Intrusion Detection: A Behavioral Approach Using Graph Model	Cao Z., Stephen Huang S.-H.	2023	Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems
6	Detecting Masquerading Traitors from Process Visualization of Computer Usage	MacAk M., Oslejsek R., Buhnova B.	2023	Proceedings - 2023 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications, TrustCom/BigDataSE/CSE/EUC/ISCI 2023
7	A Behavioral Graph Model for Host-Based Intrusion Detection	Cao, Zechun; Huang, Shou-Hsuan Stephen	2023	JOURNAL OF INFORMATION ASSURANCE AND SECURITY
8	A benchmark for visual analysis of insider threat detection	Zhao Y., Yang K., Chen S., Zhang Z., Huang X., Li Q., Ma Q., Luan X., Fan X.	2022	Science China Information Sciences
9	Survey on Insider Threat Detection Method	Guo S., Zhang L., Pan Y., Tao W., Bai W., Zheng Q., Liu Y., Pan Z.	2022	Shuju Caiji Yu Chuli/Journal of Data Acquisition and Processing
10	Using binary classifiers for one-class classification	Kang S.	2022	Expert Systems with Applications
11	Detection of Insider Threats Using Deep Learning: A Review	Lavanya P., Shankar Sriram V.S.	2022	Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies
12	Analysis and Evaluation for Detection Techniques on Host Anomalous Behavior Using Machine Learning	Li B., Zhuang H., Liu R., Liao J.	2022	2022 2nd International Conference on Computer Science, Electronic Information Engineering and Intelligent Control Technology, CEI 2022
13	Qualitative data clustering to detect outliers	Nowak-Brzezinska A., Lazarz W.	2021	Entropy
14	GSketch: A Comprehensive Graph Analytic Approach for Masquerader Detection Based on File Access Graph	Jiang J., Wang X., Wang Y., Lv Q., Liu M., Wang T., Wang L.	2021	Proceedings - IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications
15	An analysis of the rising concerns of an insider threat for sustainable it development	Sashi Kumar M.S.V., Reddy C.R.K., Kanchukatla D.	2020	Journal of Green Engineering
16	Obfuscation of malicious behaviors for thwarting masquerade detection systems based on locality features	Vidal J.M., Monge M.A.S.	2020	Sensors

17	Empirical detection techniques of insider threat incidents	Alsowail R.A., Al-Shehari T.	2020	IEEE Access
18	Comparative evaluation of different classification techniques for masquerade attack detection	Elmasry W., Akbulut A., Zaim A.H.	2020	International Journal of Information and Computer Security
19	Employee profiling via aspect-based sentiment and network for insider threats detection	Soh C., Yu S., Narayanan A., Duraisamy S., Chen L.	2019	Expert Systems with Applications
20	Insight into insiders and IT: A survey of insider threat taxonomies, analysis, modeling, and countermeasures	Homoliak I., Toffalini F., Guarnizo J., Elovici Y., Ochoa M.	2019	ACM Computing Surveys
21	Full-featured information equalization modeling for insider threat detection	Liu Y., Luo S.-L., Qu L.-W., Pan L.-M., Zhang J.	2019	Zhejiang Daxue Xuebao (Gongxue Ban)/Journal of Zhejiang University (Engineering Science)
22	Detecting Intruders by User File Access Patterns	Huang S.-H.S., Cao Z., Raines C.E., Yang M.N., Simon C.	2019	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
23	Detection of masqueraders based on graph partitioning of file system access events	Toffalini F., Homoliak I., Harilal A., Binder A., Ochoa M.	2018	Proceedings - 2018 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy Workshops, SPW 2018
24	An insider threat detection method based on user behavior analysis	Jiang W., Tian Y., Liu W., Liu W.	2018	IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology
25	Insider threat detection and its future directions	Ko L.L., Divakaran D.M., Liao Y.S., Thing V.L.L.	2017	International Journal of Security and Networks
26	Online masquerade detection resistant to mimicry	Maestre Vidal J., Lucila Sandoval Orozco A., Javier Garcia Villalba L.	2016	Expert Systems with Applications

16.- Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations

Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Sucar L.E., Montes-Y-Gomez M.

2013, Multimedia Tools and Applications

Citas: 11

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Markov random fields		2021	Advances in Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
2	Pattern graph-based image retrieval system combining semantic and visual features	Allani O., Zghal H.B., Mellouli N., Akdag H.	2017	Multimedia Tools and Applications
3	A combinatorial reasoning mechanism with topological and metric relations for change detection in river planforms: An application to GlobeLand30's water bodies	Leng L., Yang G., Chen S.	2017	ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information

4	Incorporating spatial distribution feature with local patterns for content-based image retrieval	Shouhong W., Peiquan J., Yu X., Lihua Y.	2016	Chinese Journal of Electronics
5	A multi-channel based illumination compensation mechanism for brightness invariant image retrieval	Dubey S.R., Singh S.K., Singh R.K.	2015	Multimedia Tools and Applications
6	Comparative assessment of efficiency for content based image retrieval systems using different wavelet features and pre-classifier	Chowdhury M., Kundu M.K.	2015	Multimedia Tools and Applications
7	ALC(F): A new description logic for spatial reasoning in images	Hudelot C., Atif J., Bloch I.	2015	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
8	Markov random fields		2015	Advances in Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
9	Recent improvements in image retrieval	Zeng Y.S., Ying X.L.	2014	Advanced Materials Research
10	Characteristics Classification of Durian Varieties Images for Knowledge Representation by Using Conceptual Graph	Ibrahim N.S., Bakar Z.A., Rahman N.A.	2014	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
11	Trends in semantic and digital media technologies	Grzegorzec M., Granitzer M., Ruger S., Sintek M., Declerck T., Romanelli M.	2013	Multimedia Tools and Applications

17.- The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark

Escalante H.J., Hernandez C.A., Gonzalez J.A., Lopez-Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E.F., Enrique Sucar L., Villasenor L., Grubinger M.
2010, Computer Vision and Image Understanding

Citas: 351

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Joint asymmetric discrete hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Li J., Jiang L., Yang Z., Fang X., Xie S., Xu Y.	2026	Pattern Recognition
2	RISE: Semantics-guided discriminative and robust learning for unsupervised cross-modal hashing	Wang R., Huang H., Feng Y., Peng D., Hu P., Li Y.	2026	Knowledge Based Systems
3	SABA: Scene-aware bidirectional backdoor attack against multimodal learning	Xu S., Li G., Cao M., Zhang Y., Cao Y.	2026	Neurocomputing
4	RSPH: Robust self-paced hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Zhang D., Hu Z., Wu X.-J., Kittler J.	2026	Pattern Recognition
5	Progressive semantic refinement hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Cui Z., Ma H.	2026	Information Sciences
6	GREx: Generalized Referring Expression Segmentation, Comprehension, and Generation	Ding H., Liu C., He S., Jiang X., Jiang Y.-G.	2026	International Journal of Computer Vision

7	Asymmetric complementary manifold hashing with category correlation for cross-modal retrieval	Zheng L., Chen H., Xiang B., Yuan Z., Horng S.-J., Li T.	2025	Knowledge Based Systems
8	SALA: Semantic alignment and localization alignment for visual grounding	Li H., Wang X., Yang L., Li Q., Xiao B.	2025	Neurocomputing
9	Multi-view multi-label canonical correlation analysis for cross-modal multimedia retrieval	Rani A., Sanghavi R., Verma Y.	2025	Multimedia Tools and Applications
10	Dual-stage hash-aware distillation for unsupervised cross-modal hashing retrieval	Shu X., Li R., Li M.	2025	International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics
11	Latent structure-oriented asymmetric hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Ma J.	2025	Neurocomputing
12	Tensor-based Opposing yet Complementary Learning for Multi-view Multi-label Feature Selection	Hao P., Zhang H., Zhang Y.	2025	Mm 2025 Proceedings of the 33rd ACM International Conference on Multimedia Co Located with mm 2025
13	MAP: Parameter-Efficient Tuning for Referring Expression Comprehension via Multi-Modal Adaptive Positional Encoding	Yao R., Rong Y., Zou T., Zhang B., Li J., Xiong S., Xiong S.	2025	Mm 2025 Proceedings of the 33rd ACM International Conference on Multimedia Co Located with mm 2025
14	Dynamic Optimization Noisy Cross-Modal Hashing	Yao Z., Fu H., Yang Y., Gu G.	2025	Mm 2025 Proceedings of the 33rd ACM International Conference on Multimedia Co Located with mm 2025
15	Unsupervised Similarity-Fusion Transformer Hashing for Multimodal Retrieval	Yang Z., Chen B., Tang J., Li Y.	2025	Mm 2025 Proceedings of the 33rd ACM International Conference on Multimedia Co Located with mm 2025
16	Visual Grounding with Attention-Driven Constraint Balancing	Kang W., Zhou L., Wu J., Sun C., Yan Y.	2025	Mm 2025 Proceedings of the 33rd ACM International Conference on Multimedia Co Located with mm 2025
17	Weighted semantic feature based self-supervised deep cross-modal hashing	Gao L., Wang Z., Wang X., Zheng Z., Chen H., Lu S.	2025	International Journal of Multimedia Information Retrieval
18	OH-CMH: Towards cross-modal hashing for streaming data with hierarchical labels and label increment scenario	Peng J., Zhang C.-Y., Wang N., Zhan Y.-W., Chen Z.-D., Wang Y., Luo X., Xu X.-S.	2025	Knowledge Based Systems
19	Label-consistent kernel transform learning-based sparse hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Maggu J., Goel A., Kumar R.	2025	Knowledge and Information Systems

20	View-label driven cross-space structure alignment for incomplete multi-view partial multi-label classification	Ding S., Chen J., Gao T., Ye Y., Lu X.	2025	Journal of King Saud University Computer and Information Sciences
21	Asymmetric semantic preserving hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Deng Q., Chen Y., Cheng C., Xiao J., Tao M., Fang X.	2025	Multimedia Systems
22	Adaptive Asymmetric Online Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Liu Y., Zhang Y., Fu H., Gu G.	2025	Icmr 2025 Proceedings of the 2025 International Conference on Multimedia Retrieval
23	Visual Grounding with Feature Enhancement and Language-Aware Attribute Guidance	Bu X., Yu J., Liu Y., Xu K.	2025	Icmr 2025 Proceedings of the 2025 International Conference on Multimedia Retrieval
24	Online weighted hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Jiang Z., Weng Z., Li R., Zhuang H., Lin Z.	2025	Pattern Recognition
25	Adaptive Asymmetric Supervised Cross-Modal Hashing with consensus matrix	Li Y., Long J., Huang Y., Yang Z.	2025	Information Processing and Management
26	Efficient parameter-free adaptive hashing for large-scale cross-modal retrieval	Li B., Wu Y., Li Z.	2025	International Journal of Approximate Reasoning
27	Uncertainty-Aware Global-View Reconstruction for Multi-View Multi-Label Feature Selection	Hao P., Liu K., Gao W.	2025	Proceedings of the Aai Conference on Artificial Intelligence
28	Asymmetric Cross-Modal Hashing Based on Formal Concept Analysis	Li Y., Long J., Yang Z.	2025	Proceedings of the Aai Conference on Artificial Intelligence
29	Look Around Before Locating: Considering Content and Structure Information for Visual Grounding	Zheng S., Zhao P., Zheng Z., He P., Cheng H., Cai Y., Huang Q.	2025	Proceedings of the Aai Conference on Artificial Intelligence
30	Deep Evidential Hashing for Trustworthy Cross-Modal Retrieval	Li Y., Zhen L., Sun Y., Peng D., Peng X., Hu P.	2025	Proceedings of the Aai Conference on Artificial Intelligence
31	Semi-Supervised Online Cross-Modal Hashing	Kang X., Liu X., Zhang X., Xue W., Nie X., Yin Y.	2025	Proceedings of the Aai Conference on Artificial Intelligence
32	Semantic decomposition and enhancement hashing for deep cross-modal retrieval	Fei L., He Z., Wong W.K., Zhu Q., Zhao S., Wen J.	2025	Pattern Recognition
33	Rwkv-vg: visual grounding with RWKV-driven encoder-decoder framework	Nian F., Gu Y., Wang W., Liu A., Zhang D., Li F.	2025	Multimedia Systems
34	Multimodal large model pretraining, adaptation and efficiency optimization	Ji L., Xiao S., Feng J., Gao W., Zhang H.	2025	Neurocomputing
35	Prompt-guided bidirectional deep fusion network for referring image segmentation	Wu J., Zhang Y., Kampffmeyer M., Zhao X.	2025	Neurocomputing
36	Cross-Modal Dual Hashing Based on Transfer Knowledge	Zhong J.-Q., Lin Q.-B., Cao W.-M.	2025	Tien Tzu Hsueh Pao Acta Electronica Sinica

37	Global and local semantic enhancement of samples for cross-modal hashing	Teng S., Chen Y., Zheng Z., Zhang W., Kang P., Wu N.	2025	Neurocomputing
38	Overview of Multimodal Machine Learning	Al-Zoghby A.M., Al-Awadly E.M.K., Ebada A.I., Awad W.A.	2025	ACM Transactions on Asian and Low Resource Language Information Processing
39	CMIRNet: Cross-Modal Interactive Reasoning Network for Referring Image Segmentation	Xu M., Xiao T., Liu Y., Tang H., Hu Y., Nie L.	2025	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
40	Graph Convolutional Multi-Label Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Shen X., Chen Y., Liu W., Zheng Y., Sun Q.-S., Pan S.	2025	IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems
41	Multi-Scale Referring Image Segmentation Based on Dual Attention	Hu M., Wang R., Zhang W., Zhang Q.	2025	Jisuanji Fuzhu Sheji Yu Tuxingxue Xuebao Journal of Computer Aided Design and Computer Graphics
42	Multi-Semantic Embedding Hashing for LargeScale Cross-Modal Retrieval	Cui Z., Ma H., Wang Y.	2025	2025 4th International Joint Conference on Information and Communication Engineering Jcice 2025
43	Task-aware Cross-modal Feature Refinement Transformer with Large Language Models for Visual Grounding	Chen W., Xu Z., Xu R., Wu S., Wong H.-S.	2025	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
44	Cyclic Pseudo-Label Generation and Refinement for Weakly Supervised Referring Expression Grounding	Wu J., Ji Z., Wang Y., Pang Y., Han J.	2025	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
45	Three-Stage Semisupervised Cross-Modal Hashing with Pairwise Relations Exploitation	Fan W., Zhang C., Li H., Jia X., Wang G.	2025	IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems
46	Enabling Secure Cross-Modal Search Over Encrypted Data via Federated Learning	Wang X., Li J., Liu Z., Tang Q., Wang X.	2025	IEEE Internet of Things Journal
47	SegVG: Transferring Object Bounding Box to Segmentation for Visual Grounding	Kang W., Liu G., Shah M., Yan Y.	2025	Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics

48	Deep Noisy Multi-label Learning for Robust Cross-Modal Retrieval	Pu R., Peng D., Hua F.	2025	Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics
49	Harlequin: Color-Driven Generation of Synthetic Data for Referring Expression Comprehension	Parolari L., Izzo E., Ballan L.	2025	Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics
50	Phrase Decoupling Cross-Modal Hierarchical Matching and Progressive Position Correction for Visual Grounding	Xie M., Wang M., Li H., Zhang Y., Tao D., Yu Z.	2025	IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
51	A comprehensive construction of deep neural network-based encoder-decoder framework for automatic image captioning systems	Rahman M.M., Uzzaman A., Sami S.I., Khatun F., Bhuiyan M.A.-A.	2024	let Image Processing
52	Online hashing with partially known labels for cross-modal retrieval	Shu Z., Li L., Yu Z.	2024	Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence
53	Deep semantics-preserving cross-modal hashing	Lai Z., Fang X., Kong H.	2024	Big Data Research
54	Discrete online cross-modal hashing with consistency preservation	Kang X., Liu X., Xue W., Zhang X., Nie X., Yin Y.	2024	Pattern Recognition
55	Deep supervised fused similarity hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Ng W.W.Y., Xu Y., Tian X., Wang H.	2024	Multimedia Tools and Applications
56	Category correlations embedded semantic centers hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Fan W., Yang C., Luo K., Zhang M., Li H.	2024	Information Sciences
57	Knowledge graph construction in hyperbolic space for automatic image annotation	Lotfi F., Jamzad M., Beigy H., Farhood H., Sheng Q.Z., Beheshti A.	2024	Image and Vision Computing
58	ResVG: Enhancing Relation and Semantic Understanding in Multiple Instances for Visual Grounding	Zheng M., Zhang J., Chen Q., Peng Y., Liu Y.	2024	Mm 2024 Proceedings of the 32nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia
59	Distribution Consistency Guided Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Sun Y., Liu K., Li Y., Ren Z., Dai J., Peng D.	2024	Mm 2024 Proceedings of the 32nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia
60	Visual Grounding with Multi-modal Conditional Adaptation	Yao R., Xiong S., Zhao Y., Rong Y.	2024	Mm 2024 Proceedings of the 32nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia
61	Robust Contrastive Cross-modal Hashing with Noisy Labels	Wang L., Qin Y., Sun Y., Peng D., Peng X., Hu P.	2024	Mm 2024 Proceedings of the 32nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia

62	A Visual Grounding Method with Contrastive Learning Large Model	Lu Q.-Y., Yuan G.-L., Zhu H., Qin X.-Y., Xue M.-G.	2024	Tien Tzu Hsueh Pao Acta Electronica Sinica
63	Cross-modal hashing retrieval with compatible triplet representation	Hao Z., Jin Y., Yan X., Wang C., Yang S., Ge H.	2024	Neurocomputing
64	Deep cross-modal hashing with multi-task latent space learning	Wu S., Yuan X., Xiao G., Lew M.S., Gao X.	2024	Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence
65	Language conditioned multi-scale visual attention networks for visual grounding	Yao H., Wang L., Cai C., Wang W., Zhang Z., Shang X.	2024	Image and Vision Computing
66	DCMFNet: Deep Cross-Modal Fusion Network for Referring Image Segmentation with Iterative Gated Fusion	Huang Z., Xue M., Liu Y., Xu K., Li J., Yu C.	2024	ACM International Conference Proceeding Series
67	Improving visual grounding with multi-modal interaction and auto-regressive vertex generation	Qin X., Li F., He C., Pei R., Zhang X.	2024	Neurocomputing
68	Supervised Semantic-Embedded Hashing for Multimedia Retrieval	Chen Y., Long J., Guo L., Yang Z.	2024	Knowledge-Based Systems
69	Online Cross-modal Hashing With Dynamic Prototype	Kang X., Liu X., Xue W., Nie X., Yin Y.	2024	ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing Communications and Applications
70	UniQRNet: Unifying Referring Expression Grounding and Segmentation with QRNet	Ye J., Tian J., Yan M., Xu H., Ye Q., Shi Y., Yang X., Wang X., Zhang J., He L., Lin X.	2024	ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing Communications and Applications
71	MFVG: A Visual Grounding Network with Multi-scale Fusion	Chen P., Qi K., Tao X., Xu W., Zhang J.	2024	Icmr 2024 Proceedings of the 2024 International Conference on Multimedia Retrieval
72	Multiple Information Embedded Hashing for Large-Scale Cross-Modal Retrieval	Wang Y., Zhan Y.-W., Chen Z.-D., Luo X., Xu X.-S.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
73	Robust Asymmetric Cross-Modal Hashing Retrieval With Dual Semantic Enhancement	Teng S., Xu T., Zheng Z., Wu N., Zhang W., Teng L.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems
74	Efficient Discriminative Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Huang J., Kang P., Fang X., Han N., Xie S., Gao H.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems
75	Joint Semantic Preserving Sparse Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Hu Z., Cheung Y.-M., Li M., Lan W., Zhang D., Liu Q.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
76	A survey of efficient fine-tuning methods for Vision-Language Models — Prompt and Adapter	Xing J., Liu J., Wang J., Sun L., Chen X., Gu X., Wang Y.	2024	Computers and Graphics (Pergamon)
77	Hierarchical feature selection based on neighborhood interclass spacing from fine to coarse	Lin Z., Lin Y.	2024	Neurocomputing

78	Learning From Box Annotations for Referring Image Segmentation	Feng G., Zhang L., Hu Z., Lu H.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems
79	From methods to datasets: A survey on Image-Caption Generators	Agarwal L., Verma B.	2024	Multimedia Tools and Applications
80	Asymmetric low-rank double-level cooperation for scalable discrete cross-modal hashing	Chen R., Tan J., Zhou Y., Yang Z., Nie F., Chen T.	2024	Expert Systems with Applications
81	Large-Scale Cross-Modal Hashing with Unified Learning and Multi-Object Regional Correlation Reasoning	Li B., Li Z.	2024	Neural Networks
82	Text-assisted attention-based cross-modal hashing	Yuan X., Shan S., Huo Y., Jiang J., Wu S.	2024	International Journal of Multimedia Information Retrieval
83	Asymmetric Supervised Fusion-Oriented Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Yang Z., Deng X., Guo L., Long J.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics
84	Language-guided target segmentation method based on multi-granularity feature fusion	Tan Q., Wang R., Wu A.	2024	Beijing Hangkong Hangtian Daxue Xuebao/Journal of Beijing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics
85	Semi-paired Multi-modal Query Hashing Method	Yu J., Ma J., Xian Y., Hou R., Sun W.	2024	Dianzi Yu Xinxi Xuebao/Journal of Electronics and Information Technology
86	OneRef: Unified One-tower Expression Grounding and Segmentation with Mask Referring Modeling	Xiao L., Yang X., Peng F., Wang Y., Xu C.	2024	Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems
87	SimVG: A Simple Framework for Visual Grounding with Decoupled Multi-modal Fusion	Dai M., Yang L., Xu Y., Feng Z., Yang W.	2024	Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems
88	Referring Image Segmentation With Fine-Grained Semantic Funneling Infusion	Yang J., Zhang L., Lu H.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems
89	Two-Stage Asymmetric Similarity Preserving Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Huang J., Kang P., Han N., Chen Y., Fang X., Gao H., Zhou G.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
90	Towards Language-Guided Visual Recognition via Dynamic Convolutions	Luo G., Zhou Y., Sun X., Wu Y., Gao Y.	2024	International Journal of Computer Vision
91	Robust online hashing with label semantic enhancement for cross-modal retrieval	Li L., Shu Z., Yu Z., Wu X.-j.	2024	Pattern Recognition
92	CMMix: Cross-Modal Mix Augmentation Between Images and Texts for Visual Grounding	Hong T., Wang Y., Sun X., Li X., Ma J.	2024	Communications in Computer and Information Science
93	Self-Paced Multi-Grained Cross-Modal Interaction Modeling for Referring Expression Comprehension	Miao P., Su W., Wang G., Li X., Xi L.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing

94	Online Discriminative Cross-Modal Hashing	Kang X., Liu X., Zhang X., Nie X., Yin Y.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
95	CKDH: CLIP-Based Knowledge Distillation Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Li J., Wong W.K., Jiang L., Fang X., Xie S., Xu Y.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
96	Manufacturing domain instruction comprehension using synthetic data	Johari K., Tong C.T.Z., Bhardwaj R., Subbaraju V., Kim J.-J., Tan U.-X.	2024	Visual Computer
97	Deep Self-Supervised Hashing With Fine-Grained Similarity Mining for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Han L., Wang R., Chen C., Zhang H., Zhang Y., Zhang W.	2024	IEEE Access
98	LGR-NET: Language Guided Reasoning Network for Referring Expression Comprehension	Lu M., Li R., Feng F., Ma Z., Wang X.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
99	BadCM: Invisible Backdoor Attack Against Cross-Modal Learning	Zhang Z., Yuan X., Zhu L., Song J., Nie L.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
100	Cross-Modal Hashing Method With Properties of Hamming Space: A New Perspective	Hu Z., Cheung Y.-M., Li M., Lan W.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence
101	KEY POINTS CENTERED SPARSE HASHING FOR CROSS-MODAL RETRIEVAL	Hu Z., Cheung Y.-M., Li M., Lan W., Zhang D.	2024	ICASSP, IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing - Proceedings
102	Similarity Transitivity Broken-Aware Multi-Modal Hashing	Tu R.-C., Mao X.-L., Liu J., Ji Y., Wei W., Huang H.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
103	Contrastive Incomplete Cross-Modal Hashing	Luo H., Zhang Z., Nie L.	2024	IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
104	ScanFormer: Referring Expression Comprehension by Iteratively Scanning	Su W., Miao P., Dou H., Li X.	2024	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
105	Anchor-based Unsupervised Cross-modal Hashing	Hu P., Peng X., Peng D.-Z.	2024	Ruan Jian Xue Bao Journal of Software
106	When Visual Grounding Meets Gigapixel-Level Large-Scale Scenes: Benchmark and Approach	Tao M., Bai B., Lin H., Wang H., Wang Y., Luo L., Fang L.	2024	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition

107	Semantic Preservation and Hash Fusion Network for Unsupervised Cross-Modal Retrieval	Shu X., Li M.	2024	Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics
108	Dual Semantic Fusion Hashing for Multi-Label Cross-Modal Retrieval	Liu K., Gong Y., Cao Y., Ren Z., Peng D., Sun Y.	2024	Ijcai International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence
109	Unsupervised Online Cross-modal Hashing with Multiple Association Exploitation	Kang X., Liu X., Zhang X., Xue W., Nie X., Wang S., Yin Y.	2024	Proceedings IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo
110	Cross-Modal Retrieval: A Systematic Review of Methods and Future Directions	Wang T., Li F., Zhu L., Li J., Zhang Z., Shen H.T.	2024	Proceedings of the IEEE
111	Vision-Aware Language Reasoning for Referring Image Segmentation	Xu F., Luo B., Zhang C., Xu L., Pu M., Li B.	2023	Neural Processing Letters
112	Dual-graph hierarchical interaction network for referring image segmentation	Shi Z., Wu Q., Li H., Meng F., Ngan K.N.	2023	Displays
113	MAFH: Multilabel aware framework for bit-scalable cross-modal hashing	Li X., Yu J., Lu H., Jiang S., Li Z., Yao P.	2023	Knowledge-Based Systems
114	TransVG++: End-to-End Visual Grounding With Language Conditioned Vision Transformer	Deng J., Yang Z., Liu D., Chen T., Zhou W., Zhang Y., Li H., Ouyang W.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence
115	An incremental approach to hierarchical feature selection by applying fuzzy rough set technique	She Y., Wu J., He X.	2023	Artificial Intelligence Review
116	Adaptive semi-paired query hashing for multi-modal retrieval	Yu J., Huang W., Li Z., Li K., Shu Z., Wang Q., Jiao J.	2023	Digital Signal Processing: A Review Journal
117	Suspected Objects Matter: Rethinking Model's Prediction for One-stage Visual Grounding	Jiao Y., Jie Z., Chen J., Ma L., Jiang Y.-G.	2023	MM 2023 - Proceedings of the 31st ACM International Conference on Multimedia
118	LUNA: Language as Continuing Anchors for Referring Expression Comprehension	Liang Y., Yang Z., Tang Y., Fan J., Li Z., Wang J., Torr P.H.S., Huang S.-L.	2023	MM 2023 - Proceedings of the 31st ACM International Conference on Multimedia
119	Targeted Adversarial Attack Against Deep Cross-Modal Hashing Retrieval	Wang T., Zhu L., Zhang Z., Zhang H., Han J.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
120	Continuous cross-modal hashing	Zheng H., Wang J., Zhen X., Song J., Zheng F., Lu K., Qi G.-J.	2023	Pattern Recognition
121	Fuzzy Rough Sets-Based Incremental Feature Selection for Hierarchical Classification	Huang W., She Y., He X., Ding W.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems
122	Unsupervised Cross-Modal Hashing With Modality-Interaction	Tu R.-C., Jiang J., Lin Q., Cai C., Tian S., Wang H., Liu W.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
123	A Cross-Modal Hash Retrieval Method with Fused Triples	Li W., Mei H., Li Y., Yu J., Zhang X., Xue X., Wang J.	2023	Applied Sciences (Switzerland)

124	Cross-modal attention guided visual reasoning for referring image segmentation	Zhang W., Hu M., Tan Q., Zhou Q., Wang R.	2023	Multimedia Tools and Applications
125	Cross-modal hashing with missing labels	Ni H., Zhang J., Kang P., Fang X., Sun W., Xie S., Han N.	2023	Neural Networks
126	Data-Aware Proxy Hashing for Cross-modal Retrieval	Tu R.-C., Mao X.-L., Ji W., Wei W., Huang H.	2023	SIGIR 2023 - Proceedings of the 46th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval
127	Deep Cross-Modal Proxy Hashing	Tu R.-C., Mao X.-L., Tu R.-X., Bian B., Cai C., Wang H., Wei W., Huang H.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
128	Cross-Modal Recurrent Semantic Comprehension for Referring Image Segmentation	Shang C., Li H., Qiu H., Wu Q., Meng F., Zhao T., Ngan K.N.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
129	Unsupervised Hashing Retrieval via Efficient Correlation Distillation	Xi Z., Wang X., Cheng P.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
130	Referring Expression Comprehension Using Language Adaptive Inference	Su W., Miao P., Dou H., Fu Y., Li X.	2023	Proceedings of the 37th AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence, AAAI 2023
131	Label-wise Deep Semantic-Alignment Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Li L., Sun W.	2023	ICMR 2023 - Proceedings of the 2023 ACM International Conference on Multimedia Retrieval
132	Weakly-Supervised Enhanced Semantic-Aware Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Zhang C., Li H., Gao Y., Chen C.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
133	Referring Segmentation via Encoder-Fused Cross-Modal Attention Network	Feng G., Zhang L., Sun J., Hu Z., Lu H.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence
134	Cross-modal transformer with language query for referring image segmentation	Zhang W., Tan Q., Li P., Zhang Q., Wang R.	2023	Neurocomputing
135	Bidirectional Relationship Inferring Network for Referring Image Localization and Segmentation	Feng G., Hu Z., Zhang L., Sun J., Lu H.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems
136	Entity-Enhanced Adaptive Reconstruction Network for Weakly Supervised Referring Expression Grounding	Liu X., Li L., Wang S., Zha Z.-J., Li Z., Tian Q., Huang Q.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence
137	A fast weighted multi-view Bayesian learning scheme with deep learning for text-based image retrieval from unlabeled galleries	Oussama A., Khaldi B., Kherfi M.L.	2023	Multimedia Tools and Applications

138	Unsupervised Contrastive Cross-Modal Hashing	Hu P., Zhu H., Lin J., Peng D., Zhao Y.-P., Peng X.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence
139	ONION: Online Semantic Autoencoder Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Zhang D., Wu X.-J., Chen G.	2023	ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology
140	Local-global coordination with transformers for referring image segmentation	Liu F., Kong Y., Zhang L., Feng G., Yin B.	2023	Neurocomputing
141	DAH: Discrete Asymmetric Hashing for Efficient Cross-Media Retrieval	Zhang D., Wu X.-J., Xu T., Yin H.-F.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
142	A triple fusion model for cross-modal deep hashing retrieval	Wang H., Zhao K., Zhao D.	2023	Multimedia Systems
143	A Proposal-Free One-Stage Framework for Referring Expression Comprehension and Generation via Dense Cross-Attention	Sun M., Suo W., Wang P., Zhang Y., Wu Q.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
144	Rethinking and Improving Feature Pyramids for One-Stage Referring Expression Comprehension	Suo W., Sun M., Wang P., Zhang Y., Wu Q.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
145	Non-Co-Occurrence Enhanced Multi-Label Cross-Modal Hashing Retrieval Based on Graph Convolutional Network	Li M., Fan J., Lin Z.	2023	IEEE Access
146	Adaptive Marginalized Semantic Hashing for Unpaired Cross-Modal Retrieval	Luo K., Zhang C., Li H., Jia X., Chen C.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
147	Multi-Label Hashing for Dependency Relations Among Multiple Objectives	Peng L., Qian J., Xu Z., Xin Y., Guo L.	2023	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
148	YORO - Lightweight End to End Visual Grounding	Ho C.-H., Appalaraju S., Jasani B., Manmatha R., Vasconcelos N.	2023	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
149	PolyFormer: Referring Image Segmentation as Sequential Polygon Generation	Liu J., Ding H., Cai Z., Zhang Y., Kumar Satzoda R., Mahadevan V., Manmatha R.	2023	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
150	Multimodal referring expression comprehension based on image and text—a review	Wang L., Miao P., Su W., Li X., Ji N., Jiang Y.	2023	Journal of Image and Graphics
151	Contrastive Grouping with Transformer for Referring Image Segmentation	Tang J., Zheng G., Shi C., Yang S.	2023	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition

152	Graph Convolutional Network Semantic Enhancement Hashing for Self-supervised Cross-Modal Retrieval	Hu J., Li M., Zhang J.	2023	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
153	Transformer-Based Discriminative and Strong Representation Deep Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Zhou S., Han Y., Chen N., Huang S., Igorevich K.K., Luo J., Zhang P.	2023	IEEE Access
154	Federated unsupervised cross-modal Hashing	Lei Z., Jingzhi L., Tianshi W., Jingjing L., Huaxiang Z.	2023	Scientia Sinica Informationis
155	Confidence-aware Pseudo-label Learning for Weakly Supervised Visual Grounding	Liu Y., Zhang J., Chen Q., Peng Y.	2023	Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision
156	Language Adaptive Weight Generation for Multi-task Visual Grounding	Su W., Miao P., Dou H., Wang G., Qiao L., Li Z., Li X.	2023	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
157	Nevis'22: A Stream of 100 Tasks Sampled from 30 Years of Computer Vision Research	Bornschein J., Galashov A., Hemsley R., Rannen-Triki A., Chen Y., Chaudhry A., He X.O., Douillard A., Caccia M., Feng Q., Shen J., Rebuffi S.-A., Stacpoole K., de las Casas D., Hawkins W., Lazaridou A., Teh Y.W., Rusu A.A., Pascanu R., Ranzato M.	2023	Journal of Machine Learning Research
158	Neural module networks: A review	Fashandi, Homa	2023	NEUROCOMPUTING
159	SemiMemes: A Semi-supervised Learning Approach for Multimodal Memes Analysis	Pham Thai Hoang Tung; Nguyen Tan Viet; Ngo Tien Anh; Phan Duy Hung	2023	COMPUTATIONAL COLLECTIVE INTELLIGENCE, ICCCI 2023
160	A High-Dimensional Sparse Hashing Framework for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Wang Y., Chen Z.-D., Luo X., Xu X.-S.	2022	IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology
161	Adaptive weight multi-channel center similar deep hashing	Liu X., Cao G., Lin Q., Cao W.	2022	Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation
162	Contrastive Label Correlation Enhanced Unified Hashing Encoder for Cross-modal Retrieval	Wu H., Zhang L., Chen Q., Deng Y., Siebert J., Han Y., Li Z., Kong D., Cao Z.	2022	International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management, Proceedings
163	Discrete Fusion Adversarial Hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Li J., Yu E., Ma J., Chang X., Zhang H., Sun J.	2022	Knowledge-Based Systems
164	Fast Cross-Modal Hashing With Global and Local Similarity Embedding	Wang Y., Chen Z.-D., Luo X., Li R., Xu X.-S.	2022	IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics

165	Cross-Modal Progressive Comprehension for Referring Segmentation	Liu S., Hui T., Huang S., Wei Y., Li B., Li G.	2022	IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence
166	A Review of Multi-Modal Learning from the Text-Guided Visual Processing Viewpoint	Ullah U., Lee J.-S., An C.-H., Lee H., Park S.-Y., Baek R.-H., Choi H.-C.	2022	Sensors
167	DAP 2 CMH: Deep Adversarial Privacy-Preserving Cross-Modal Hashing	Zhu L., Song J., Yang Z., Huang W., Zhang C., Yu W.	2022	Neural Processing Letters
168	MS2GAH: Multi-label semantic supervised graph attention hashing for robust cross-modal retrieval	Duan Y., Chen N., Zhang P., Kumar N., Chang L., Wen W.	2022	Pattern Recognition
169	Referring Segmentation in Images and Videos With Cross-Modal Self-Attention Network	Ye L., Rochan M., Liu Z., Zhang X., Wang Y.	2022	IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence
170	A novel deep translated attention hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Yu H., Ma R., Su M., An P., Li K.	2022	Multimedia Tools and Applications
171	A Survey of Referring Image Segmentation	Qiu S., Zhao Y., Wei S.	2022	Journal of Signal Processing
172	Deep Discrete Cross-Modal Hashing with Multiple Supervision	Yu E., Ma J., Sun J., Chang X., Zhang H., Hauptmann A.G.	2022	Neurocomputing
173	Multi-label modality enhanced attention based self-supervised deep cross-modal hashing	Zou X., Wu S., Zhang N., Bakker E.M.	2022	Knowledge-Based Systems
174	Hierarchical GAN-Tree and Bi-Directional Capsules for multi-label image classification	Wang B., Hu X., Zhang C., Li P., Yu P.S.	2022	Knowledge-Based Systems
175	Deep Cross-Modal Hashing With Hashing Functions and Unified Hash Codes Jointly Learning	Tu R.-C., Mao X.-L., Ma B., Hu Y., Yan T., Wei W., Huang H.	2022	IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
176	Cross-modality synergy network for referring expression comprehension and segmentation	Li Q., Zhang Y., Sun S., Wu J., Zhao X., Tan M.	2022	Neurocomputing
177	Structured Attention Network for Referring Image Segmentation	Lin L., Yan P., Xu X., Yang S., Zeng K., Li G.	2022	IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
178	An Improved Automatic Image Annotation Approach Using Convolutional Neural Network-Slantlet Transform	Adnan M.M., Rahim M.S.M., Khan A.R., Saba T., Fati S.M., Bahaj S.A.	2022	IEEE Access
179	A Model of Semantic-Based Image Retrieval Using C-Tree and Neighbor Graph	Nhi N.T.U., Le T.M., Van T.T.	2022	International Journal on Semantic Web and Information Systems
180	Efficient modal-aware feature learning with application in multimodal hashing	Chu H., Zeng H., Lai H., Tang Y.	2022	Intelligent Data Analysis
181	Improving Visual Grounding with Visual-Linguistic Verification and Iterative Reasoning	Yang L., Xu Y., Yuan C., Liu W., Li B., Hu W.	2022	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
182	Global and Local Feature Based Deep Cross-Modal Hashing	Yu H., Ma R., Su M., An P., Li K.	2022	Communications in Computer and Information Science

183	Referring Expression Comprehension	Wu Q., Wang P., Wang X., He X., Zhu W.	2022	Advances in Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
184	Progressive Language-Customized Visual Feature Learning for One-Stage Visual Grounding	Liao Y., Zhang A., Chen Z., Hui T., Liu S.	2022	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
185	Understanding Synonymous Referring Expressions via Contrastive Features	Chen Y.-W., Tsai Y.-H., Yang M.-H.	2022	International Journal of Computer Vision
186	Two-stage Cross Modal Hashing Retrieval Based on Composite Quantization and Cauchy Distribution	Li X., He J., Fan B.	2022	2022 4th International Conference on Communications, Information System and Computer Engineering, CISCE 2022
187	What kinds of errors do reference resolution models make and what can we learn from them?	Sanchez J., Mazuecos M., Maina H., Benotti L.	2022	Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: NAACL 2022 - Findings
188	Online Robust Specific and Consistent Hashing	Lin H., Meng M., Wu J.	2022	Proceedings - IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo
189	LPGN: Language-Guided Proposal Generation Network for Referring Expression Comprehension	Wang G., Yang C., Feng S., Jiang B.	2022	Proceedings - IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo
190	Multi-view Multi-label Canonical Correlation Analysis for Cross-modal Matching and Retrieval	Sanghavi R., Verma Y.	2022	IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops
191	Deep Label Feature Fusion Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Ren D., Xu W., Wang Z., Sun Q.	2022	IEEE Access
192	ReSTR: Convolution-free Referring Image Segmentation Using Transformers	Kim N., Kim D., Kwak S., Lan C., Zeng W.	2022	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
193	SeqTR: A Simple Yet Universal Network for Visual Grounding	Zhu C., Zhou Y., Shen Y., Luo G., Pan X., Lin M., Chen C., Cao L., Sun X., Ji R.	2022	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
194	Information Fusion: Machine Learning Methods	Li J., Zhang B., Zhang D.	2022	Information Fusion: Machine Learning Methods

195	CoupAlign: Coupling Word-Pixel with Sentence-Mask Alignments for Referring Image Segmentation	Zhang Z., Zhu Y., Liu J., Liang X., Wei K.	2022	Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems
196	Multi-label enhancement based self-supervised deep cross-modal hashing	Zou, Xitao; Wu, Song; Bakker, Erwin M.; Wang, Xinzhi	2022	NEUROCOMPUTING
197	Harmonization Shared Autoencoder Gaussian Process Latent Variable Model with Relaxed Hamming Distance	Li J., Zhang B., Lu G., Xu Y., Wu F., Zhang D.	2021	IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems
198	MOON: Multi-hash codes joint learning for cross-media retrieval	Zhang D., Wu X.-J., Yin H.-F., Kittler J.	2021	Pattern Recognition Letters
199	Local Graph Convolutional Networks for Cross-Modal Hashing	Chen Y., Wang S., Lu J., Chen Z., Zhang Z., Huang Z.	2021	MM 2021 - Proceedings of the 29th ACM International Conference on Multimedia
200	One-Stage Visual Grounding via Semantic-Aware Feature Filter	Ye J., Lin X., He L., Li D., Chen Q.	2021	MM 2021 - Proceedings of the 29th ACM International Conference on Multimedia
201	Two-stage Visual Cues Enhancement Network for Referring Image Segmentation	Jiao Y., Jie Z., Luo W., Chen J., Jiang Y.-G., Wei X., Ma L.	2021	MM 2021 - Proceedings of the 29th ACM International Conference on Multimedia
202	Joint Versus Independent Multiview Hashing for Cross-View Retrieval	Hu P., Peng X., Zhu H., Lin J., Zhen L., Peng D.	2021	IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics
203	Research Progress on Image Captioning	Li Z., Wei H., Zhang C., Ma H., Shi Z.	2021	Jisuanji Yanjiu yu Fazhan/Computer Research and Development
204	Know yourself and know others: Efficient common representation learning for few-shot cross-modal retrieval	Wang S., Lai H., Shi Z.	2021	ICMR 2021 - Proceedings of the 2021 International Conference on Multimedia Retrieval
205	Multi-attention based semantic deep hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Zhu L., Tian G., Wang B., Wang W., Zhang D., Li C.	2021	Applied Intelligence
206	Vse-fs: Fast full-sample visual semantic embedding	Zhai S., Guo G., Yuan F., Liu Y., Wang X.	2021	IEEE Intelligent Systems
207	Task-adaptive Asymmetric Deep Cross-modal Hashing[Formula presented]	Li F., Wang T., Zhu L., Zhang Z., Wang X.	2021	Knowledge-Based Systems
208	Object Feature Based Deep Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Zhu J., Bai H., Zhang Z., Xie B., Zhang J.	2021	Journal of Frontiers of Computer Science and Technology
209	Few-Shot Visual Grounding for Natural Human-Robot Interaction	Tziafas G., Kasaei H.	2021	2021 IEEE International Conference on Autonomous Robot Systems and Competitions, ICARSC 2021

210	Unsupervised cross-modal similarity via Latent Structure Discrete Hashing Factorization	Fang Y., Li B., Li X., Ren Y.	2021	Knowledge-Based Systems
211	High-dimensional sparse cross-modal hashing with fine-grained similarity embedding	Wang Y., Chen Z.-D., Luo X., Xu X.-S.	2021	The Web Conference 2021 - Proceedings of the World Wide Web Conference, WWW 2021
212	Multi-label semantics preserving based deep cross-modal hashing	Zou X., Wang X., Bakker E.M., Wu S.	2021	Signal Processing: Image Communication
213	A Semi-supervised Learning Approach Based on Adaptive Weighted Fusion for Automatic Image Annotation	Li Z., Lin L., Zhang C., Ma H., Zhao W., Shi Z.	2021	ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications and Applications
214	Survey on deep multi-modal data analytics: Collaboration, rivalry, and fusion	Wang Y.	2021	ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications and Applications
215	Semi-Supervised Multi-Modal Multi-Instance Multi-Label Deep Network with Optimal Transport	Yang Y., Fu Z.-Y., Zhan D.-C., Liu Z.-B., Jiang Y.	2021	IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering
216	Asymmetric Supervised Consistent and Specific Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Meng M., Wang H., Yu J., Chen H., Wu J.	2021	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
217	Referring Expression Comprehension: A Survey of Methods and Datasets	Qiao Y., Deng C., Wu Q.	2021	IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
218	Mask Cross-Modal Hashing Networks	Lin Q., Cao W., He Z., He Z.	2021	IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
219	Deep adversarial quantization network for cross-modal retrieval	Zhou Y., Feng Y., Zhou M., Qiang B., Leong Hou U., Zhu J.	2021	ICASSP, IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing - Proceedings
220	TransVG: End-to-End Visual Grounding with Transformers	Deng J., Yang Z., Chen T., Zhou W., Li H.	2021	Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision
221	Encoder fusion network with co-attention embedding for referring image segmentation	Feng G., Hu Z., Zhang L., Lu H.	2021	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
222	Proposal-free One-stage Referring Expression via Grid-Word Cross-Attention	Suo W., Sun M., Wang P., Wu Q.	2021	IJCAI International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence
223	Deep Unified Cross-Modality Hashing by Pairwise Data Alignment	Wang Y., Xue B., Cheng Q., Chen Y., Zhang L.	2021	IJCAI International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence

224	Implementing Deep Neural Network Based Encoder-Decoder Framework for Image Captioning	Rahman M.M., Uzzaman A., Sami S.I.	2021	Proceedings of 2021 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Information, Communication and Systems, SPICSCON 2021
225	Multi-Level Correlation Adversarial Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Ma X., Zhang T., Xu C.	2020	IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
226	Dual Convolutional LSTM Network for Referring Image Segmentation	Ye L., Liu Z., Wang Y.	2020	IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
227	Relaxed Asymmetric Deep Hashing Learning: Point-to-Angle Matching	Li J., Zhang B., Lu G., You J., Xu Y., Wu F., Zhang D.	2020	IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems
228	Cross-Modal Omni Interaction Modeling for Phrase Grounding	Yu T., Hui T., Yu Z., Liao Y., Yu S., Zhang F., Liu S.	2020	MM 2020 - Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Multimedia
229	Label Embedding Online Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Wang Y., Luo X., Xu X.-S.	2020	MM 2020 - Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Multimedia
230	Transferrable Referring Expression Grounding with Concept Transfer and Context Inheritance	Liu X., Li L., Wang S., Zha Z.-J., Meng D., Huang Q.	2020	MM 2020 - Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Multimedia
231	Deep semantic similarity adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Qiang H., Wan Y., Xiang L., Meng X.	2020	Neurocomputing
232	Self-constraining and attention-based hashing network for bit-scalable cross-modal retrieval	Wang X., Zou X., Bakker E.M., Wu S.	2020	Neurocomputing
233	Semantic deep cross-modal hashing	Lin Q., Cao W., He Z., He Z.	2020	Neurocomputing
234	Enabling Secure Cross-Modal Retrieval Over Encrypted Heterogeneous IoT Databases With Collective Matrix Factorization	Guo C., Jia J., Jie Y., Liu C.Z., Choo K.-K.R.	2020	IEEE Internet of Things Journal
235	Improved Deep Hashing with Soft Pairwise Similarity for Multi-Label Image Retrieval	Zhang Z., Zou Q., Lin Y., Chen L., Wang S.	2020	IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
236	An innovative multi-label learning based algorithm for city data computing	Mei M., Zhong Y., He F., Xu C.	2020	Geoinformatica
237	Multi-Task Consistency-Preserving Adversarial Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Xie D., Deng C., Li C., Liu X., Tao D.	2020	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
238	a Review of Hashing Methods for Multimodal Retrieval	Cao W., Feng W., Lin Q., Cao G., He Z.	2020	IEEE Access

239	Image annotation method based on graph volume network	Zhu Z., Hangchi Z.	2020	Proceedings - 2020 International Conference on Intelligent Transportation, Big Data and Smart City, ICITBS 2020
240	Referring image segmentation via cross-modal progressive comprehension	Huang S., Hui T., Liu S., Li G., Wei Y., Han J., Liu L., Li B.	2020	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
241	Bi-Directional Relationship Inferring Network for Referring Image Segmentation	Hu Z., Feng G., Sun J., Zhang L., Lu H.	2020	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
242	Improving One-Stage Visual Grounding by Recursive Sub-query Construction	Yang Z., Chen T., Wang L., Luo J.	2020	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
243	Magnet: Multi-region attention-assisted grounding of natural language queries at phrase level	Shrestha A., Pugdeethosapol K., Fang H., Qiu Q.	2020	Proceedings - International Conference on Pattern Recognition
244	Adaptive Hypergraph Embedded Semi-Supervised Multi-Label Image Annotation	Tang C., Liu X., Wang P., Zhang C., Li M., Wang L.	2019	IEEE Transactions on Multimedia
245	Knowledge-guided pairwise reconstruction network for weakly supervised referring expression grounding	Liu X., Li L., Wang S., Zha Z.-J., Su L., Huang Q.	2019	MM 2019 - Proceedings of the 27th ACM International Conference on Multimedia
246	Fuzzy Rough Set Based Feature Selection for Large-Scale Hierarchical Classification	Zhao H., Wang P., Hu Q., Zhu P.	2019	IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems
247	A fast and accurate one-stage approach to visual grounding	Yang Z., Gong B., Wang L., Huang W., Yu D., Luo J.	2019	Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision
248	Adaptive reconstruction network for weakly supervised referring expression grounding	Liu X., Li L., Wang S., Zha Z.-J., Meng D., Huang Q.	2019	Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision
249	Generating easy-to-understand referring expressions for target identifications	Tanaka M., Itamochi T., Narioka K., Sato I., Ushiku Y., Harada T.	2019	Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision
250	Zero-shot grounding of objects from natural language queries	Sadhu A., Chen K., Nevatia R.	2019	Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision

251	Diverse image annotation with missing labels	Verma Y.	2019	Pattern Recognition
252	A Comparative Study of Clustering Validation Indices and Maximum Entropy for Sintonization of Automatic Segmentation Techniques	Resendiz J.D.H., Castro H.M.M., Leal E.T.	2019	IEEE Latin America Transactions
253	Hierarchical feature extraction based on discriminant analysis	Liu X., Zhao H.	2019	Applied Intelligence
254	Discrete Latent Factor Model for Cross-Modal Hashing	Jiang Q.-Y., Li W.-J.	2019	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
255	Cross-modal self-attention network for referring image segmentation	Ye L., Rochan M., Liu Z., Wang Y.	2019	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
256	Cross-modal hashing with semantic deep embedding	Yan C., Bai X., Wang S., Zhou J., Hancock E.R.	2019	Neurocomputing
257	Hierarchical feature selection with subtree based graph regularization	Tuo Q., Zhao H., Hu Q.	2019	Knowledge-Based Systems
258	GrowBit: Incremental Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Mandal D., Annadani Y., Biswas S.	2019	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
259	Comprehensive semi-supervised multi-modal learning	Yang Y., Wang K.-T., Zhan D.-C., Xiong H., Jiang Y.	2019	IJCAI International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence
260	Dual Asymmetric Deep Hashing Learning	Li J., Zhang B., Lu G., Zhang D.	2019	IEEE Access
261	Deep robust unsupervised multi-modal network	Yang Y., Wu Y.-F., Zhan D.-C., Liu Z.-B., Jiang Y.	2019	33rd AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence, AAAI 2019, 31st Innovative Applications of Artificial Intelligence Conference, IAAI 2019 and the 9th AAAI Symposium on Educational Advances in Artificial Intelligence, EAAI 2019
262	Independent Feature and Label Components for Multi-label Classification	Zhong Y., Xu C., Du B., Zhang L.	2018	Proceedings - IEEE International Conference on Data Mining, ICDM
263	DMTMV: A unified learning framework for deep multi-task multi-view learning	Wu Y.-F., Zhan D.-C., Jiang Y.	2018	Proceedings - 9th IEEE International Conference on Big Knowledge, ICBK 2018

264	Weakly Supervised Phrase Localization with Multi-scale Anchored Transformer Network	Zhao F., Li J., Zhao J., Feng J.	2018	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
265	Referring Image Segmentation via Recurrent Refinement Networks	Li R., Li K., Kuo Y.-C., Shu M., Qi X., Shen X., Jia J.	2018	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
266	Image annotation: Then and now	Bhagat P.K., Choudhary P.	2018	Image and Vision Computing
267	Global and local semantics-preserving based deep hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Ma L., Li H., Meng F., Wu Q., Ngi Ngan K.	2018	Neurocomputing
268	Complex object classification: A multi-modal multi-instance multi-label deep network with optimal transport	Yang Y., Wu Y.-F., Zhan D.-C., Liu Z.-B., Jiang Y.	2018	Proceedings of the ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining
269	Region-based image retrieval using relevance feature weights	Bchir O., Ismail M.M.B., Aljam H.	2018	International Journal of Fuzzy Logic and Intelligent Systems
270	Attention-aware deep adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Zhang X., Lai H., Feng J.	2018	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
271	Supervised deep hashing for hierarchical labeled data	Wang D., Huang H., Lu C., Feng B.-S., Wen G., Nie L., Mao X.-L.	2018	32nd AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence, AAAI 2018
272	Learning to Disambiguate by Asking Discriminative Questions	Li Y., Huang C., Tang X., Loy C.C.	2017	Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision
273	CAPIA: Cloud assisted privacy-preserving image annotation	Tian Y., Hou Y., Yuan J.	2017	2017 IEEE Conference on Communications and Network Security, CNS 2017
274	Deep cross-modal hashing	Jiang Q.-Y., Li W.-J.	2017	Proceedings - 30th IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR 2017

275	Comprehension-guided referring expressions	Luo R., Shakhnarovich G.	2017	Proceedings - 30th IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR 2017
276	GuessWhat?! Visual object discovery through multi-modal dialogue	De Vries H., Strub F., Chandar S., Pietquin O., Larochelle H., Courville A.	2017	Proceedings - 30th IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR 2017
277	Pattern graph-based image retrieval system combining semantic and visual features	Allani O., Zghal H.B., Mellouli N., Akdag H.	2017	Multimedia Tools and Applications
278	Hierarchical Multi-label Classification using Fully Associative Ensemble Learning	Zhang L., Shah S.K., Kakadiaris I.A.	2017	Pattern Recognition
279	Robust Web Image Annotation via Exploring Multi-Facet and Structural Knowledge	Hu M., Yang Y., Shen F., Zhang L., Shen H.T., Li X.	2017	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
280	Multi label learning and multi feature extraction for automatic image annotation	Renuse S., Bogiri N.	2017	2017 International Conference on Computing, Communication, Control and Automation, ICCUBEA 2017
281	Visual and semantic context modeling for scene-centric image annotation	Zand M., Doraisamy S., Abdul Halin A., Mustafa M.R.	2017	Multimedia Tools and Applications
282	An attention-based regression model for grounding textual phrases in images	Endo K., Aono M., Nichols E., Funakoshi K.	2017	IJCAI International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence
283	Bayesian aggregation of categorical distributions with applications in crowdsourcing	Augustin A., Venanzi M., Rogers A., Jennings N.R.	2017	IJCAI International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence
284	LIP6@CLEF2017: Multi-modal spatial role labeling using word embeddings working notes	Zablocki E., Bordes P., Soulier L., Piwowarski B., Gallinari P.	2017	CEUR Workshop Proceedings
285	Spatial language understanding with multimodal graphs using declarative learning based programming	Kordjamshidi P., Rahgooy T., Manzoor U.	2017	EMNLP 2017 - Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Structured Prediction
286	Generation and comprehension of unambiguous object descriptions	Mao J., Huang J., Toshev A., Camburu O., Yuille A., Murphy K.	2016	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition

287	Natural language object retrieval	Hu R., Xu H., Rohrbach M., Feng J., Saenko K., Darrell T.	2016	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
288	On the coupled use of signal and semantic concepts to bridge the semantic and user intention gaps for visual content retrieval	Jarrar R., Belkhatir M.	2016	International Journal of Multimedia Information Retrieval
289	Facial expression recognition based-on saliency guided support vector machine	Dou Y., Zhou M., Wang J., Qiang J.	2016	Proceedings - 2016 9th International Symposium on Computational Intelligence and Design, ISCID 2016
290	Multi-Label Dictionary Learning for Image Annotation	Jing X.-Y., Wu F., Li Z., Hu R., Zhang D.	2016	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
291	Integrating global and local visual features with semantic hierarchies for two-level image annotation	Qian Z., Zhong P., Chen J.	2016	Neurocomputing
292	Segmentation from natural language expressions	Hu R., Rohrbach M., Darrell T.	2016	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
293	A generic framework for ontology-based information retrieval and image retrieval in web data	Vijayarajan V., Dinakaran M., Tejaswin P., Lohani M.	2016	Human-centric Computing and Information Sciences
294	Resolving references to objects in photographs using the words-as-classifiers model	Schlangen D., Zarriess S., Kennington C.	2016	54th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, ACL 2016 - Long Papers
295	Easy things first: Installments improve referring expression generation for objects in photographs	Zarriess S., Schlangen D.	2016	54th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, ACL 2016 - Long Papers
296	A new method for automatic image annotation using region features and wordnet semantic similarity	Xu G., Zhang Z., Li X., Xu L.	2016	International Journal of Simulation: Systems, Science and Technology
297	Towards generating colour terms for referents in photographs: Prefer the expected or the unexpected?	Zarriess S., Schlangen D.	2016	INLG 2016 - 9th International Natural Language Generation Conference, Proceedings of the Conference

298	Multimodal compact bilinear pooling for visual question answering and visual grounding	Fukui A., Park D.H., Yang D., Rohrbach A., Darrell T., Rohrbach M.	2016	EMNLP 2016 - Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, Proceedings
299	PIR: A domain specific language for multimedia information retrieval	Huang X., Zhao T., Cao Y.	2015	Web Design and Development: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications
300	An exploratory study to identify relevant cues for the deletion of faces for multimedia retrieval	Ritter M., Bahr G.S.	2015	2015 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo Workshops, ICMEW 2015
301	A benchmark data set to evaluate the illumination robustness of image processing algorithms for object segmentation and classification	Khan A.M., Mikut R., Reischl M.	2015	PLoS ONE
302	Decision making for content management systems: Criteria identification and categorisation	Angelopoulos S., Kitsios F.	2015	Proceedings of the Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences
303	Learning descriptive visual representation for image classification and annotation	Lu Z., Wang L.	2015	Pattern Recognition
304	Automatic image annotation using semi-supervised generative modeling	Hamid Amiri S., Jamzad M.	2015	Pattern Recognition
305	Semantic sparse recoding of visual content for image applications	Lu Z., Han P., Wang L., Wen J.-R.	2015	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
306	Automatic image annotation for description of Urban and outdoor scenes	Cruz-Perez C., Starostenko O., Alarcon-Aquino V., Rodriguez-Asomoza J.	2015	Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering
307	Image with a Message: Towards detecting non-literal image usages by visual linking	Weiland L., Dietz L., Ponzetto S.P.	2015	A Workshop of the 2015 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, EMNLP 2015 - Workshop on Vision and Language 2015, VL 2015: Vision and Language Meet Cognitive Systems - Proceedings
308	Linking entities across images and text	Weegar R., Astrom K., Nuges P.	2015	CoNLL 2015 - 19th Conference on Computational Natural Language Learning, Proceedings

309	Automatic Image Annotation Using an Evolutionary Algorithm (IAGA)	Bahrami S., Saniee Abadeh M.	2014	2014 7th International Symposium on Telecommunications, IST 2014
310	Locating people in video from semantic descriptions: A new database and approach	Halstead M., Denman S., Sridharan S., Fookes C.	2014	Proceedings - International Conference on Pattern Recognition
311	Image segmentation and labeling using free-form semantic annotation	Tegen A., Weegar R., Hammarlund L., Oskarsson M., Jiang F., Medved D., Nugues P., Astrom K.	2014	Proceedings - International Conference on Pattern Recognition
312	Towards modelling visual ambiguity for visual object Detection	Chatzilari E., Nikolopoulos S., Kompatsiaris Y., Kittler J.	2014	ACM International Conference Proceeding Series
313	Assessing the relationships among tag syntax, semantics, and perceived usefulness	Jorgensen C., Stvilia B., Wu S.	2014	Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology
314	A Novel Topology in Modular Ann Approach for Multi-Modal Concept Identification and Image Retrieval	Hussain S.S., Hashmani M., Moinuddin M., Raza K.	2014	Intelligent Automation and Soft Computing
315	Probabilistic component identification	Sajnani H.S., Lopes C.V.	2014	ACM International Conference Proceeding Series
316	Labeling complicated objects: Multi-view Multi-Instance Multi-Label learning	Nguyen C.-T., Wang X., Liu J., Zhou Z.-H.	2014	Proceedings of the National Conference on Artificial Intelligence
317	On forensics investigation models	Dieko E., Boniface A.K., Aderonke T.F., Otasowie I.	2014	Lecture Notes in Engineering and Computer Science
318	Multi-instance active learning with online labeling for object recognition	Salmani K., Sridharan M.	2014	Proceedings of the 27th International Florida Artificial Intelligence Research Society Conference, FLAIRS 2014
319	Quad tree based image retrieval using hierarchical fuzzy C-means	Geetha P., Narayanan V.	2014	International Journal of Applied Engineering Research
320	Referitgame: Referring to objects in photographs of natural scenes	Kazemzadeh S., Ordonez V., Matten M., Berg T.L.	2014	EMNLP 2014 - 2014 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, Proceedings of the Conference
321	Visual entity linking: A preliminary study	Weegar R., Hammarlund L., Tegen A., Oskarsson M., Astrom K., Nugues P.	2014	AAAI Workshop - Technical Report

322	Fully associative ensemble learning for Hierarchical multi-label classification	Zhang L., Shah S.K., Kakadiaris I.A.	2014	BMVC 2014 - Proceedings of the British Machine Vision Conference 2014
323	Tag taxonomy aware dictionary learning for region tagging	Zheng J., Jiang Z.	2013	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
324	Lyric-based automatic music image generator for music browser using scene knowledge	Kasai H.	2013	IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics
325	Label localization with weakly spatial constrained graph propagation	Yu L., Liu J., Xu C., Zhou X.	2013	Proceedings - IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo
326	Feature reduction and selection for automatic image annotation	Chen G.-B., Chien B.-C.	2013	Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies
327	Unified Dictionary Learning and Region Tagging with Hierarchical Sparse Representation	Cao X., Wei X., Han Y., Yang Y., Sebe N., Hauptmann A.	2013	Computer Vision and Image Understanding
328	Local image tagging via graph regularized joint group sparsity	Yang Y., Huang Z., Yang Y., Liu J., Shen H.T., Luo J.	2013	Pattern Recognition
329	Combination of classification and regression in decision tree for multi-labeling image annotation and retrieval	Fakhari A., Moghadam A.M.E.	2013	Applied Soft Computing Journal
330	Label localization by appearance guided graph inferring	Yu L., Liu J., Xu C.	2013	2013 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing, ICIP 2013 - Proceedings
331	Using tagged images of low visual ambiguity to boost the learning efficiency of object detectors	Chatzilari E.	2013	MM 2013 - Proceedings of the 2013 ACM Multimedia Conference
332	Image annotation by semantic sparse recoding of visual content	Lu Z., Peng Y.	2012	MM 2012 - Proceedings of the 20th ACM International Conference on Multimedia
333	Automated annotation of natural images using an extended annotation model	Mihai G., Stanescu L.	2012	International Journal of Computer Science and Applications
334	Noisy tag alignment with image regions	Liu Y., Liu J., Li Z., Lu H.	2012	Proceedings - IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo
335	Random forest for image annotation	Fu H., Zhang Q., Qiu G.	2012	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

336	Graph-guided sparse reconstruction for region tagging	Han Y., Wu F., Shao J., Tian Q., Zhuang Y.	2012	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
337	Multi-modal region selection approach for training object detectors	Chatzilari E., Nikolopoulos S., Kompatsiaris Y., Kittler J.	2012	Proceedings of the 2nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia Retrieval, ICMR 2012
338	Uso combinado de tecnologías semánticas y análisis visual para la anotación automática de imágenes y su recuperación	Rodriguez-Vaamonde S., Ruiz-Ibanez P., Gonzalez-Rodriguez M.	2012	Profesional de la Informacion
339	Fusing object detection and region appearance for image-text alignment	Del Pero L., Lee P., Magahern J., Hartley E., Barnard K.	2011	MM'11 - Proceedings of the 2011 ACM Multimedia Conference and Co-Located Workshops
340	Automated annotation system for natural images	Mihai G., Stanescu L.	2011	2011 Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems, FedCSIS 2011
341	Hierarchical decision tree (HDT) approach for image annotation	Fakhari A., Eftekhari-Moghaddam A.-M.	2011	2011 7th Iranian Conference on Machine Vision and Image Processing, MVIP 2011 - Proceedings
342	On the use of conceptual information in a concept-based image indexing and retrieval framework	Jarrar R., Belkhatir M., Messom C.H.	2011	Proceedings - International Conference on Image Processing, ICIP
343	Automated system for annotating and retrieving images	Mihai G., Stanescu L., Dan Burdescu D., Spahiu C.S.	2011	2011 IEEE International Conference on Signal and Image Processing Applications, ICSIPA 2011
344	Custom ontologies for an automated image annotation system	Mihai G., Stanescu L., Burdescu D.D., Brezovan M.	2011	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
345	Semi-supervised object recognition using flickr images	Chatzilari E., Nikolopoulos S., Papadopoulos S., Zigkolis C., Kompatsiaris Y.	2011	Proceedings - International Workshop on Content-Based Multimedia Indexing

346	Semantic image classification of a Relief-F feature weighting based SVM method for performance	Liu J., Du J.-P.	2011	Zhongnan Daxue Xuebao (Ziran Kexue Ban)/Journal of Central South University (Science and Technology)
347	Contextual kernel and spectral methods for learning the semantics of images	Lu Z., Ip H.H.S., Peng Y.	2011	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing
348	Tag localization with spatial correlations and joint group sparsity	Yang Y., Yang Y., Huang Z., Shen H.T., Nie F.	2011	Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
349	Special issue on image and video retrieval evaluation	Hanbury A., Muller H., Clough P.	2010	Computer Vision and Image Understanding
350	Multiscale segmentation based on mode-shift clustering	Tarnawski W., Miroslaw L., Pawlikowski R., Ociepa K.	2010	Proceedings of the International Multiconference on Computer Science and Information Technology, IMCSIT 2010
351	Seven Years of Image Retrieval Evaluation	Clough, Paul; Mueller, Henning; Sanderson, Mark	2010	IMAGECLEF: EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION IN VISUAL INFORMATION RETRIEVAL

18.- TIA-INAOE's Participation at ImageCLEF 2009

Escalante H.J., Gonzalez J.A., Hernandez C.A., Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E., Ruiz E., Sucar L.E., Villasenor L.
2009, Ceur Workshop Proceedings

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Overview of the CLEF 2009 large-scale visual concept detection and annotation task	Nowak S., Dunker P.	2010	Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics
2	Overview of the CLEF 2009 Large-scale visual concept detection and annotation task	Nowak S., Dunker P.	2009	Ceur Workshop Proceedings

19.- Towards Annotation-based query and document expansion for image retrieval

Escalante H.J., Hernandez C., Lopez A., Marin H., Montes M., Morales E., Sucar E., Villasenor L.

2008, Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics

Citas: 3

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Infographics retrieval: A new methodology	Li Z., Carberry S., Fang H., McCoy K.F., Peterson K.	2014	Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics
2	Identifying important features for graph retrieval	Li Z., Carberry S., Fang H., Mccoy K.F.	2014	Coling 2014 25th International Conference on Computational Linguistics Proceedings of Coling 2014 Technical Papers
3	MAGMA-Efficient method for image annotation in low dimensional feature space based on multivariate Gaussian models	Broda B., Kwasnicka H., Paradowski M., Stanek M.	2009	Proceedings of the International Multiconference on Computer Science and Information Technology Imcsit 09

20.- Overview of the ImageCLEF 2007 object retrieval task

Deselaers T., Hanbury A., Viitaniemi V., Benczur A., Brendel M., Daroczy B., Escalante Balderas H.J., Gevers T., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Hoi S.C.H., Laaksonen J., Li M., Marin Castro H.M., Ney H., Rui X., Sebe N., Stottinger J., Wu L.

2008, Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	What Happened in CLEF... For Another While?	Ferro N.	2024	Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics
2	Ambiguous proximity distribution	Wang Q., Li Y.	2014	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

21.- Markov random fields and spatial information to improve automatic image annotation

Hernandez-Gracidas C., Sucar L.E.

2007, Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

Citas: 11

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Markov random fields		2021	Advances in Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
2	Intra and inter spatial color descriptor for content based image retrieval	Ben Rejeb I., Ouni S., Zagrouba E.	2019	Proceedings of IEEE/ACS International Conference on Computer Systems and Applications, AICCSA
3	The spatial relation features for describing objects relationships within image	Saad M.N., Muda Z., Ashaari N.S., Hamid H.A., Hasan N.H.B.A.	2015	Proceedings - 5th International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Informatics: Bridging the Knowledge between Academic, Industry, and Community, ICEEI 2015
4	Markov random fields		2015	Advances in Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
5	Linking entities across images and text	Weegar R., Astrom K., Nuges P.	2015	CoNLL 2015 - 19th Conference on Computational Natural Language Learning, Proceedings
6	Fusing PLSA model and Markov random fields for automatic image annotation	Tian D., Zhao X., Shi Z.	2014	High Technology Letters
7	A survey of refining image annotation techniques	Tian D.P.	2014	International Journal of Multimedia and Ubiquitous Engineering
8	A new energy model for the hidden markov random fields	Sublime J., Cornuejols A., Bennani Y.	2014	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
9	Simple object recognition based on spatial relations and visual features represented using irregular pyramids	Morales-Gonzalez A., Garcia-Reyes E.B.	2013	Multimedia Tools and Applications

10	Assessing the role of spatial relations for the object recognition task	Morales-Gonzalez A., Garcia-Reyes E.	2010	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
11	Image retrieval using Markov random fields and global image features	Llorente A., Manmatha R., Ruger S.	2010	CIVR 2010 - 2010 ACM International Conference on Image and Video Retrieval

22.- TIA-INAOE's participation at ImageCLEF 2007

Escalante H.J., Hernandez C.A., Lopez A., Marin H.M., Montes M., Morales E., Sucar L.E., Villasenor L.
2007, Ceur Workshop Proceedings

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Overview of the ImageCLEFphoto 2007 photographic retrieval task	Grubinger M., Clough P., Hanbury A., Muller H.	2007	Ceur Workshop Proceedings

23.- Overview of the ImageCLEF 2007 object retrieval task

Deselaers T., Hanbury A., Viitaniemi V., Benczur A., Brendel M., Daroczy B., Escalante Balderas H.J., Gevers T., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Hoi S.C.H., Laaksonen J., Li M., Marin Castro H.M., Ney H., Rui X., Sebe N., Stottinger J., Wu L.
2007, CEUR Workshop Proceedings

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Revisiting the Feature and Content Gap for Landmark-Based and Image-to-Image Retrieval in Medical CBIR	Greenspan H.	2009	International Journal of Healthcare Information Systems and Informatics (IJHISI)

DOCUMENTOS CON CO-CITAS Y AUTOCITAS

1.- Stable Numerical Identification of Sources in Non-Homogeneous Media

Conde Mones J.J., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Morin Castillo M.M., Oliveros Oliveros J.J., Juarez Valencia L.H.
2022, Mathematics

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	A regularization strategy for inverse source problems with applications in optics	Vazquez, J. A. Acevedo; Oliveros, J. J. Oliveros; Mones, J. J. Conde; Castillo, M. M. Morin	2025	REVISTA MEXICANA DE FISICA

2.- Stable identification of sources located on interface of nonhomogeneous media

Conde Mones J.J., Estrada Aguayo E.R., Oliveros Oliveros J.J., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Morin Castillo M.M.
2021, Mathematics

Citas: 5

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Numerical Analysis of a Fractional Cauchy Problem for the Laplace Equation in an Annular Circular Region	Conde Mones J.J., Acevedo Vazquez J.A., Hernandez Montero E., Morin Castillo M.M., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Oliveros Oliveros J.J.	2025	Fractal and Fractional
2	FPGA-Based Hardware Implementation of a Stable Inverse Source Problem Algorithm in a Non-Homogeneous Circular Region	Oliveros-Oliveros J.J., Conde-Sanchez J.R., Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Morin-Castillo M.M., Conde-Mones J.J.	2024	Applied Sciences (Switzerland)
3	Stable identification of sources located on the cerebral cortex from EEG over the scalp	Cruz J.A.A., Castillo M.M.M., Oliveros J.J.O., Arias J.E.M.G.	2023	Revista Mexicana de Fisica
4	Stable Numerical Identification of Sources in Non-Homogeneous Media	Conde Mones J.J., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Morin Castillo M.M., Oliveros Oliveros J.J., Juarez Valencia L.H.	2022	Mathematics
5	Analysis of Dipolar Sources in the Solution of the Electroencephalographic Inverse Problem	Morin-Castillo M.M., Arriaga-Hernandez J., Cuevas-Otahola B., Oliveros-Oliveros J.J.	2022	Mathematics

3.- An FPGA-based analysis of trade-offs in the presence of ill-conditioning and different precision levels in computations

Alfredo-Badillo I., Conde-Mones J.J., Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Morin-Castillo M.M., Oliveros-Oliveros J.J., Feregrino-Urbe C.
2020, PLoS ONE

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	A regularization strategy for inverse source problems with applications in optics	Acevedo Vazquez J.A., Oliveros Oliverosa J.J., Conde Monesa J.J., Morin Castillob M.M.	2025	Revista Mexicana De Fisica
2	FPGA-Based Hardware Implementation of a Stable Inverse Source Problem Algorithm in a Non-Homogeneous Circular Region	Oliveros-Oliveros J.J., Conde-Sanchez J.R., Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Morin-Castillo M.M., Conde-Mones J.J.	2024	Applied Sciences (Switzerland)

4.- On-road obstacle detection video system for traffic accident prevention

Rosales L.A.M., Alfredo Badillo I., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Rangel H.R., Lobato Baez M.
2018, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Real time FPGA-Ann architecture for outdoor obstacle detection focused in road safety	Alfredo-Badillo I., Morales-Rosales L.A., Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Cruz-Victoria J.C., Pacheco-Bautista D., Morales-Sandoval M.	2019	Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems

5.- The Windows-Users and -Intruder simulations Logs dataset (WUIL): An experimental framework for masquerade detection mechanisms

Camina J.B., Hernandez-Gracidas C., Monroy R., Trejo L.
2014, Expert Systems with Applications

Citas: 8

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Cluster validation in clustering-based one-class classification	Rodriguez-Ruiz J., Monroy R., Medina-Perez M.A., Loyola-Gonzalez O., Cervantes B.	2019	Expert Systems
2	Bagging-RandomMiner: a one-class classifier for file access-based masquerade detection	Camina J.B., Medina-Perez M.A., Monroy R., Loyola-Gonzalez O., Villanueva L.A.P., Gurrola L.C.G.	2019	Machine Vision and Applications
3	Classification Based on Multivariate Contrast Patterns	Canete-Sifuentes L., Monroy R., Medina-Perez M.A., Loyola-Gonzalez O., Vera Voronisky F.	2019	IEEE Access
4	Experimenting with masquerade detection via user task usage	Rodriguez J., Canete L., Monroy R., Medina-Perez M.A.	2017	International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing
5	Bagging-TPMiner: a classifier ensemble for masquerader detection based on typical objects	Medina-Perez M.A., Monroy R., Camina J.B., Garcia-Borroto M.	2017	Soft Computing

6	Ensemble of one-class classifiers for personal risk detection based on wearable sensor data	Rodriguez J., Barrera-Animas A.Y., Trejo L.A., Medina-Perez M.A., Monroy R.	2016	Sensors (Switzerland)
7	Temporal and Spatial Locality: An Abstraction for Masquerade Detection	Camina J.B., Monroy R., Trejo L.A., Medina-Perez M.A.	2016	IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security
8	Towards a masquerade detection system based on user's tasks	Camina J.B., Rodriguez J., Monroy R.	2014	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

6.- Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations

Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Sucar L.E., Montes-Y-Gomez M.
2013, Multimedia Tools and Applications

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Markov Random Fields	Sucar L.E.	2021	Advances in Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
2	Exploiting label semantic relatedness for unsupervised image annotation with large free vocabularies	Pellegrin L., Escalante H.J., Montes-y-Gomez M., Gonzalez F.A.	2019	Multimedia Tools and Applications

7.- The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark

Escalante H.J., Hernandez C.A., Gonzalez J.A., Lopez-Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E.F., Enrique Sucar L., Villasenor L., Grubinger M.
2010, Computer Vision and Image Understanding

Citas: 13

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Chained ensemble classifier for image annotation	Marin-Castro H.M., Hernandez-Resendiz J.D., Escalante-Balderas H.J., Pellegrin L., Tello-Leal E.	2019	Multimedia Tools and Applications
2	Exploiting label semantic relatedness for unsupervised image annotation with large free vocabularies	Pellegrin L., Escalante H.J., Montes-y-Gomez M., Gonzalez F.A.	2019	Multimedia Tools and Applications
3	Image annotation as text-image matching: Challenge design and results	Pellegrin L., Loyola-Gonzalez O., Ortiz-Bejar J., Medina-Perez M.A., Gutierrez-Rodriguez A.E., Tellez E.S., Graff M., Miranda-Jimenez S., Moctezuma D., Garcia-Limon M., Morales-Reyes A., Reyes-Garcia C.A., Morales E., Escalante H.J.	2019	Computacion y Sistemas

4	Automated Detection of Hummingbirds in Images: A Deep Learning Approach	Serrano S.A., Benitez-Jimenez R., Nunez-Rosas L., del Coro Arizmendi M., Greeney H., Reyes-Meza V., Morales E., Escalante H.J.	2018	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
5	Overview of the 2017 RedICA text-image matching (RICATIM) challenge	Pellegrin L., Escalante H.J., Morales A., Morales E.F., Reyes-Garcia C.A.	2017	2017 IEEE International Autumn Meeting on Power, Electronics and Computing, ROPEC 2017
6	Multidimensional hierarchical classification	Hernandez J., Sucar L.E., Morales E.F.	2014	Expert Systems with Applications
7	A hybrid global-local approach for hierarchical classification	Hernandez J., Sucar L.E., Morales E.F.	2013	FLAIRS 2013 - Proceedings of the 26th International Florida Artificial Intelligence Research Society Conference
8	Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations	Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Sucar L.E., Montes-Y-Gomez M.	2013	Multimedia Tools and Applications
9	Semantic cohesion for image annotation and retrieval	Escalante H.J., Sucar L.E., Montes-Y-gomez M.	2012	Computacion y Sistemas
10	Multimodal indexing based on semantic cohesion for image retrieval	Escalante H.J., Montes M., Sucar E.	2012	Information Retrieval
11	Simplified quadtree image segmentation for image annotation	Conde Marquez G.R., Escalante H.J., Sucar L.E.	2011	CEUR Workshop Proceedings
12	An energy-based model for region-labeling	Escalante H.J., Montes-Y-Gomez M., Sucar L.E.	2011	Computer Vision and Image Understanding
13	Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante H.J., Gonzalez J.A., Hernandez C.A., Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E., Sucar L.E., Villasenor-Pineda L.	2009	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

8.- Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval

Escalante H.J., Gonzalez J.A., Hernandez C.A., Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E., Sucar L.E., Villasenor-Pineda L.

2009, Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Multimodal indexing based on semantic cohesion for image retrieval	Escalante H.J., Montes M., Sucar E.	2012	Information Retrieval
2	The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark	Escalante H.J., Hernandez C.A., Gonzalez J.A., Lopez-Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E.F., Enrique Sucar L., Villasenor L., Grubinger M.	2010	Computer Vision and Image Understanding

9.- Towards Annotation-based query and document expansion for image retrieval

Escalante H.J., Hernandez C., Lopez A., Marin H., Montes M., Morales E., Sucar E., Villasenor L.

2008, Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics

Citas: 4

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Multimodal indexing based on semantic cohesion for image retrieval	Escalante H.J., Montes M., Sucar E.	2012	Information Retrieval
2	Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante H.J., Gonzalez J.A., Hernandez C.A., Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E., Sucar L.E., Villasenor-Pineda L.	2009	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
3	Late fusion of heterogeneous methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante H.J., Hernandez C.A., Sucar L.E., Montes M.	2008	Proceedings of the 1st International ACM Conference on Multimedia Information Retrieval, MIR2008, Co-located with the 2008 ACM International Conference on Multimedia, MM'08
4	TIA-INAOE's participation at ImageCLEF 2008	Jair Escalante H., Gonzalez J.A., Hernandez C.A., Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E., Sucar L.E., Villasenor L.	2008	CEUR Workshop Proceedings

10.- Overview of the ImageCLEF 2007 object retrieval task

Deselaers T., Hanbury A., Viitaniemi V., Benczur A., Brendel M., Daroczy B., Escalante Balderas H.J., Gevers T., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Hoi S.C.H., Laaksonen J., Li M., Marin Castro H.M., Ney H., Rui X., Sebe N., Stottinger J., Wu L.

2008, Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

Citas: 3

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark	Escalante H.J., Hernandez C.A., Gonzalez J.A., Lopez-Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E.F., Enrique Sucar L., Villaseñor L., Grubinger M.	2010	Computer Vision and Image Understanding
2	Object and Concept Recognition for Image Retrieval	Nowak, Stefanie; Hanbury, Allan; Deselaers, Thomas	2010	IMAGECLEF: EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION IN VISUAL INFORMATION RETRIEVAL
3	The visual concept detection task in ImageCLEF 2008	Deselaers T., Hanbury A.	2009	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

11.- TIA-INAOE's participation at ImageCLEF 2008

Jair Escalante H., Gonzalez J.A., Hernandez C.A., Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E., Sucar L.E., Villaseñor L.

2008, Ceur Workshop Proceedings

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Selecting the N-top retrieval result lists for an effective data fusion	Juarez-Gonzalez A., Montes-y-Gomez M., Villaseñor-Pineda L., Pinto-Avendano D., Perez-Coutino M.	2010	Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics
2	On the selection of the best retrieval result per query -an alternative approach to data fusion-	Juarez-Gonzalez A., Montes-Y-Gomez M., Villaseñor-Pineda L., Ortiz-Arroyo D.	2009	Lecture Notes in Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics

12.- Markov random fields and spatial information to improve automatic image annotation

Hernandez-Gracidas C., Sucar L.E.

2007, Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

Citas: 12

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Markov Random Fields	Sucar L.E.	2021	Advances in Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
2	Image Annotation by a Hierarchical and Iterative Combination of Recognition and Segmentation	Morales-Gonzalez A., Garcia-Reyes E., Sucar L.E.	2018	International Journal of Pattern Recognition and Artificial Intelligence
3	Improving image segmentation for boosting image annotation with irregular pyramids	Morales-Gonzalez A., Garcia-Reyes E., Sucar L.E.	2013	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
4	Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations	Hernandez-Gracidas C.A., Sucar L.E., Montes-Y-Gomez M.	2013	Multimedia Tools and Applications
5	Multi-class particle swarm model selection for automatic image annotation	Escalante H.J., Montes M., Sucar L.E.	2012	Expert Systems with Applications
6	Document ranking refinement using a Markov random field model	Villatoro E., Juarez A., Montes M., Villasenor L., Sucar L.E.	2012	Natural Language Engineering
7	Hierarchical markov random fields with irregular pyramids for improving image annotation	Morales-Gonzalez A., Garcia-Reyes E., Sucar L.E.	2012	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
8	An energy-based model for region-labeling	Escalante H.J., Montes-Y-Gomez M., Sucar L.E.	2011	Computer Vision and Image Understanding
9	The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark	Escalante H.J., Hernandez C.A., Gonzalez J.A., Lopez-Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E.F., Enrique Sucar L., Villasenor L., Grubinger M.	2010	Computer Vision and Image Understanding
10	Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante H.J., Gonzalez J.A., Hernandez C.A., Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E., Sucar L.E., Villasenor-Pineda L.	2009	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)

11	Late fusion of heterogeneous methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante H.J., Hernandez C.A., Sucar L.E., Montes M.	2008	Proceedings of the 1st International ACM Conference on Multimedia Information Retrieval, MIR2008, Co-located with the 2008 ACM International Conference on Multimedia, MM'08
12	TIA-INAOE's participation at ImageCLEF 2008	Jair Escalante H., Gonzalez J.A., Hernandez C.A., Lopez A., Montes M., Morales E., Sucar L.E., Villasenor L.	2008	CEUR Workshop Proceedings

13.- Overview of the ImageCLEF 2007 object retrieval task

Deselaers T., Hanbury A., Viitaniemi V., Benczur A., Brendel M., Daroczy B., Escalante Balderas H.J., Gevers T., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Hoi S.C.H., Laaksonen J., Li M., Marin Castro H.M., Ney H., Rui X., Sebe N., Stottinger J., Wu L.
2007, CEUR Workshop Proceedings

Citas: 4

	Document Title	Authors	Year	Source
1	Automatic medical image annotation in ImageCLEF 2007: Overview, results, and discussion	Deselaers T., Deserno T.M., Muller H.	2008	Pattern Recognition Letters
2	Overview of the ImageCLEF 2007 object retrieval task	Deselaers T., Hanbury A., Viitaniemi V., Benczur A., Brendel M., Daroczy B., Escalante Balderas H.J., Gevers T., Hernandez Gracidas C.A., Hoi S.C.H., Laaksonen J., Li M., Marin Castro H.M., Ney H., Rui X., Sebe N., Stottinger J., Wu L.	2008	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)
3	SZTAKI @ ImageCLEF 2008 visual concept detection	Daroczy B., Fekete Z., Brendel M.	2008	CEUR Workshop Proceedings
4	The visual concept detection task in ImageCLEF 2008	Deselaers T., Hanbury A.	2008	CEUR Workshop Proceedings

DOCUMENTOS CON CITAS ORIGINALES GOOGLE SCHOLAR

1.- Diagnosis and Study of Mechanical Vibrations in Cargo Vehicles Using ISO 2631-1: 1997

Alejandro Medina Santiago, Jorge Antonio Orozco Torres, Carlos Arturo Hernández Gracidas, Salvador Hernández Garduza, Javier Duarte Franco
2023, Sensors

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Analytical Investigation of Vertical Force Control in In-Wheel Motors for Enhanced Ride Comfort	Bunlapyanan, C., Chantranuwathana, S., & Phanomchoeng, G. (2024). Analytical Investigation of Vertical Force Control in In-Wheel Motors for Enhanced Ride Comfort. Applied Sciences, 14(15), 6582.	2024

2.- Efficient deep learning architectures for fast identification of bacterial strains in resource-constrained devices

Rafael Gallardo García, Sofia Jarquín Rodríguez, Beatriz Beltrán Martínez, Carlos Hernández Gracidas, Rodolfo Martínez Torres
2022, Multimedia Tools and Applications

Citas: 10

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Dilated multilevel fused network for virus classification using transmission electron microscopy images	Usman, M., Sultan, H., Hong, J. S., Kim, S. G., Akram, R., Gondal, H. A. H., ... & Park, K. R. (2024). Dilated multilevel fused network for virus classification using transmission electron microscopy images. Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence, 138, 109348.	2024
2	Comparison of Efficient Deep Learning Architectures for Lactobacillus Species Identification	Rusmawati, D. A., Ariawan, I., & Firmanda, A. (2024). Comparison of Efficient Deep Learning Architectures for Lactobacillus Species Identification. Karbala International Journal of Modern Science, 10(4), 9.	2024
3	Прогнозування та оцінювання трансферних ризиків	Кармазін, В. А. (2024). Прогнозування та оцінювання трансферних ризиків.	2024
4	Deep Learning-Based Automated Approach for Classifying Bacterial Images	Abougarair, A. J., Oun, A. A., Sawan, S. I., & Ma'arif, A. (2024). Deep Learning-Based Automated Approach for Classifying Bacterial Images. International Journal of Robotics and Control Systems, 4(2), 849-876.	2024
5	A deep learning model for bacterial classification using Big Transfer (BiT)	Visitsattapongse, S., Bunkum, M., Pintavirooj, C., & Paing, M. P. (2024). A deep learning model for bacterial classification using Big Transfer (BiT). IEEE Access.	2024
6	Knowing the Unknown: Open-set Bacteria Classification in Gram Stain Microscopic Images	Alhammad, S., & Lovell, B. C. (2023, June). Knowing the Unknown: Open-set Bacteria Classification in Gram Stain Microscopic Images. In 2023 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN) (pp. 1-8). IEEE.	2023

7	Bacterial strain classification using convolutional neural network for automatic bacterial disease diagnosis	Trivedi, S., Patel, N., & Faruqui, N. (2023, January). Bacterial strain classification using convolutional neural network for automatic bacterial disease diagnosis. In 2023 13th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence) (pp. 325-332). IEEE.	2023
8	Machine learning algorithms in microbial classification: a comparative analysis	Wu, Y., & Gadsden, S. A. (2023). Machine learning algorithms in microbial classification: a comparative analysis. <i>Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence</i> , 6.	2023
9	Automated bacteria genera classification using histogram-oriented optimized capsule network	Chaudhari, J. P., Mewada, H., Patel, A. V., & Mahant, K. (2023). Automated bacteria genera classification using histogram-oriented optimized capsule network. <i>Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal</i> , 46, 101500.	2023
10	A Systematic Literature Review of Deep Learning-Based Detection and Classification Methods for Bacterial Colonies	Nagro, S. A. (2022). A Systematic Literature Review of Deep Learning-Based Detection and Classification Methods for Bacterial Colonies. <i>International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications</i> , 13(10).	2022

3.- A SHA-256 Hybrid-Redundancy Hardware Architecture for Detecting and Correcting Errors

Ignacio Algreto-Badillo, Miguel Morales-Sandoval, Alejandro Medina-Santiago, Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, Mariana Lobato-Baez, Luis Alberto Morales-Rosales
2022, Sensors

Citas: 7

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	A Survey of Blockchain Applicability, Challenges, and Key Threats	Morar, C. D., & Popescu, D. E. (2024). A Survey of Blockchain Applicability, Challenges, and Key Threats. <i>Computers</i> , 13(9), 223.	2024
2	A Comprehensive analysis of Cryptographic Algorithms: Evaluating Security, Efficiency, and Future Challenges	Ramakrishna, D., & Shaik, M. A. (2024). A Comprehensive analysis of Cryptographic Algorithms: Evaluating Security, Efficiency, and Future Challenges. <i>IEEE Access</i> .	2024
3	SignChain: Enhanced Digital Signature System Security with HashIDs in Blockchain	Darmawan, I., Maulana, F., Rahmatulloh, A., Gunawan, R., & Rizal, R. (2024, August). SignChain: Enhanced Digital Signature System Security with HashIDs in Blockchain. In 2024 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Cloud Computing, and Data Analytics (ICoABCD) (pp. 7-12). IEEE.	2024
4	HW/SW Co-Design of the Secure Hash Function SHA-256	Issad, M., Anane, N., Guenfoud, N., & Debyeche, M. (2024, November). HW/SW Co-Design of the Secure Hash Function SHA-256. In 2024 3rd International Conference on Advanced Electrical Engineering (ICAEE) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.	2024
5	13. From Transparency to Irreversibility: The Role of Blockchain in Nuclear Disarmament	VAN GELUWE, O. C. É. A. N. E. (2023). 13. From Transparency to Irreversibility: The Role of Blockchain in Nuclear Disarmament. <i>EXPANDING PERSPECTIVES ON NUCLEAR DISARMAMENT</i> , 137.	2023

6	Securing the cyber resilience of a blockchain-based railroad non-stop customs clearance system	Kim, S., & Kim, D. (2023). Securing the cyber resilience of a blockchain-based railroad non-stop customs clearance system. <i>Sensors</i> , 23(6), 2914.	2023
7	Intelligent Crypto Currency Mining Farm for E-Vehicle	Rajasekar, T., Ahila, A., Dhanya, G., & Dharsana, K. (2023, August). Intelligent Crypto Currency Mining Farm for E-Vehicle. In <i>2023 Second International Conference on Augmented Intelligence and Sustainable Systems (ICAISS)</i> (pp. 1869-1875). IEEE.	2023

4.- Searching for memory-lighter architectures for OCR-augmented image captioning

Rafael Gallardo García, Beatriz Beltrán Martínez, Carlos Hernández Gracidas, Darnes Vilariño Ayala
2026, *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Eaes: Effective augmented embedding spaces for text-based image captioning	Nguyen, K., Bui, D. C., Trinh, T., & Vo, N. D. (2022). Eaes: Effective augmented embedding spaces for text-based image captioning. <i>IEEE Access</i> , 10, 32443-32452.	2022

5.- CMOS Implementation of ANNs Based on Analog Optimization of N-Dimensional Objective Functions

Alejandro Medina-Santiago, Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, Luis Alberto Morales-Rosales, Ignacio Algreto-Badillo, Monica Amador García, Jorge Antonio Orozco Torres
2021, *Sensors*

Citas: 3

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Breast Cancer Diagnosis with Machine Learning Using Feed-Forward Multilayer Perceptron Analog Artificial Neural Network	Djimeli-Tsajio Alain, B., Silas, K. L. T., Jean-Pierre, L. T., Thierry, N., & Ejuh, G. W. (2024). Breast Cancer Diagnosis with Machine Learning Using Feed-Forward Multilayer Perceptron Analog Artificial Neural Network.	2024
2	Neuron Network with a Synapse of CMOS transistor and Anti-Parallel Memristors for Low power Implementations	Rai, V. K., & Sakthivel, R. (2022). Neuron Network with a Synapse of CMOS transistor and Anti-Parallel Memristors for Low power Implementations. <i>Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers</i> , 31(12), 2250206.	2022
3	Study of the Complexity of CMOS Neural Network Implementations Featuring Heart Rate Detection	Baryczkowski, P., Szczepaniak, S., Matykievicz, N., Perz, K., & Szczyński, S. (2023). Study of the Complexity of CMOS Neural Network Implementations Featuring Heart Rate Detection. <i>Electronics</i> , 12(20), 4291.	2023

6.- Towards Multilingual Image Captioning Models that Can Read

Rafael Gallardo García, Beatriz Beltrán Martínez, Carlos Hernández Gracidas, Darnes Vilariño Ayala
2021,

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Review of Recent Datasets Used in Image Captioning Models	Srivastava, S. (2024, December). Review of Recent Datasets Used in Image Captioning Models. In 2024 International Conference on Sustainable Communication Networks and Application (ICSCNA) (pp. 315-321). IEEE.	2024
2	Eaes: Effective augmented embedding spaces for text-based image captioning	Nguyen, K., Bui, D. C., Trinh, T., & Vo, N. D. (2022). Eaes: Effective augmented embedding spaces for text-based image captioning. IEEE Access, 10, 32443-32452.	2022

7.- Reactive Obstacle-Avoidance Systems for Wheeled Mobile Robots based on Artificial Intelligence

A Medina-Santiago, Luis Alberto Morales-Rosales, Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, Ignacio Algreto-Badillo, Ana Dalia Pano-Azucena, Jorge Antonio Orozco Torres
2021, Applied Sciences

Citas: 7

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	LiDAR-based obstacle avoidance with autonomous vehicles: A comprehensive review	Leong, P. Y., & Ahmad, N. S. (2024). LiDAR-based obstacle avoidance with autonomous vehicles: A comprehensive review. IEEE Access.	2024
2	Path Planning for Robotic Fish Based on Improved PRM Algorithm Fused with DWA Algorithm	Zhou, G., Wang, C., Gan, J., & Li, X. (2024, June). Path Planning for Robotic Fish Based on Improved PRM Algorithm Fused with DWA Algorithm. In International Conference on Computing, Control and Industrial Engineering (pp. 495-502). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.	2024
3	Адаптивне просторове керування ультразвуковим очищенням виробів складної конфігурації	Кравченко, О. М. (2023). Адаптивне просторове керування ультразвуковим очищенням виробів складної конфігурації.	2023
4	Natural Language Understanding for Navigation of Service Robots in Low-Resource Domains and Languages: Scenarios in Spanish and Nahuatl	Hernández, A., Ortega-Mendoza, R. M., Villatoro-Tello, E., Camacho-Bello, C. J., & Pérez-Cortés, O. (2024). Natural Language Understanding for Navigation of Service Robots in Low-Resource Domains and Languages: Scenarios in Spanish and Nahuatl. Mathematics, 12(8), 1136.	2024
5	Implementation of convolutional neural network (CNN) algorithm for autonomous robot	Dewi, T. K., Saptaji, K., Simarmata, A., & Fikri, M. R. (2024). Implementation of convolutional neural network (CNN) algorithm for autonomous robot. Journal of Mechanical Engineering (JMecE), 21(2), 217-237.	2024
6	Intelligent Motion Control System for the Mobile Robotic Platform.	Tsmots, I., Teslyuk, V., Opotyak, Y., & Rabyk, V. (2023). Intelligent Motion Control System for the Mobile Robotic Platform. In COLINS (3) (pp. 555-569).	2023

7	The Impact of the Distance Sensors Orientation on the Obstacle Avoidance Ability of the Robot	Zhang, G., & Zhu, Z. (2022, August). The Impact of the Distance Sensors Orientation on the Obstacle Avoidance Ability of the Robot. In 2022 International Conference on Machine Learning and Intelligent Systems Engineering (MLISE) (pp. 52-56). IEEE.	2022
---	---	---	------

8.- An FPGA-based analysis of trade-offs in the presence of ill-conditioning and different precision levels in computations

Ignacio Algreto-Badillo, José Julio Conde-Mones, Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, María Monserrat Morín-Castillo, José Jacobo Oliveros-Oliveros, Claudia Feregrino-Urbe
2020, PloS one

Citas: 3

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Facultad de Ciencias de la Electrónica Licenciatura en Electrónica	en Electrónica, L. (2022). Facultad de Ciencias de la Electrónica Licenciatura en Electrónica (Doctoral dissertation, Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla).	2022
2	Acceleration of Nuclear Reactor Simulation and Uncertainty Quantification Using Low-Precision Arithmetic	Cherezov, A., Vasiliev, A., & Ferroukhi, H. (2023). Acceleration of Nuclear Reactor Simulation and Uncertainty Quantification Using Low-Precision Arithmetic. Applied Sciences, 13(2), 896.	2023
3	Acceleration of the Nuclear Reactor Uncertainty Quantification using Low Precision Hardware	Cherezov, A., Vasiliev, A., & Ferroukhi, H. (2022). Acceleration of the Nuclear Reactor Uncertainty Quantification using Low Precision Hardware. Available at SSRN 4278458.	2022

9.- Real time FPGA-ANN architecture for outdoor obstacle detection focused in road safety

Algreto-Badillo Ignacio, Morales-Rosales Luis Alberto, Hernandez-Gracidas Carlos Arturo, Cruz-Victoria Juan Crescenciano, Pacheco-Bautista Daniel, Morales-Sandoval Miguel
2019, Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems

Citas: 7

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	System-Independent Irradiance Sensorless ANN-Based MPPT for Photovoltaic Systems in Electric Vehicles. Energies 2021, 14, 4820	Cortés, B., Tapia, R., & Flores, J. J. (2021). System-Independent Irradiance Sensorless ANN-Based MPPT for Photovoltaic Systems in Electric Vehicles. Energies 2021, 14, 4820.	2021
2	Intelligent, smart and scalable cyber-physical systems	Vijayakumar, V., Subramaniaswamy, V., Abawajy, J., & Yang, L. (2019). Intelligent, smart and scalable cyber-physical systems.	2019
3	A CMOS Image Readout Circuit with On-Chip Defective Pixel Detection and Correction	López-Portilla, B. M., Valenzuela, W., Zarkesh-Ha, P., & Figueroa, M. (2023). A CMOS Image Readout Circuit with On-Chip Defective Pixel Detection and Correction. Sensors, 23(2), 934.	2023
4	An automatic assessment of road condition from aerial imagery using modified VGG architecture in faster-RCNN framework	Malini, A., Priyadharshini, P., & Sabeena, S. (2021). An automatic assessment of road condition from aerial imagery using modified VGG architecture in faster-RCNN framework. Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems, 40(6), 11411-11422.	2021

5	System-Independent Irradiance Sensorless ANN-Based MPPT for Photovoltaic Systems in Electric Vehicles	Cortés, B., Tapia, R., & Flores, J. J. (2021). System-Independent Irradiance Sensorless ANN-Based MPPT for Photovoltaic Systems in Electric Vehicles. <i>Energies</i> , 14(16), 4820.	2021
6	Fixed point multi-bit approximate adder based convolutional neural network accelerator for digit classification inference	Nagarajan, M., Sasikumar, A., Muralidharan, D., & Rajappa, M. (2020). Fixed point multi-bit approximate adder based convolutional neural network accelerator for digit classification inference. <i>Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems</i> , 39(6), 8521-8528.	2020
7	ParaLarH: parallel FPGA router based upon Lagrange heuristics	Agrawal, R., Ahuja, K., Maheshwari, D., & Kumar, A. (2020). ParaLarH: parallel FPGA router based upon Lagrange heuristics. arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.11893.	2020

10.- On-road obstacle detection video system for traffic accident prevention

Luis Alberto Morales-Rosas, Ignacio Algreto-Badillo, Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, Héctor Rodríguez-Rangel, Mariana Lobato-Baez
2026, Recent Advances in Machine Learning and Soft Computing, of Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems

Citas: 9

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	In-vehicle edge system for real-time dashcam video analysis	Lee, S., King, J., Lee, Y. C., Han, H., & Kang, S. (2025). In-vehicle edge system for real-time dashcam video analysis. <i>Internet of Things</i> , 29, 101467.	2025
2	Nighttime trajectory extraction framework for traffic investigations at intersections based on improved SSD and DeepSort	Hu, X., & Zhang, Q. (2023). Nighttime trajectory extraction framework for traffic investigations at intersections based on improved SSD and DeepSort. <i>Signal, Image and Video Processing</i> , 17(6), 2907-2914.	2023
3	Distributed edge-based video analytics on the move	King, J., & Lee, Y. C. (2022). Distributed edge-based video analytics on the move. arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.14414.	2022
4	Small obstacles detection on roads scenes using semantic segmentation for the safe navigation of autonomous vehicles	Yasmin, S., Durrani, M. Y., Gillani, S., Bukhari, M., Maqsood, M., & Zghaibeh, M. (2022). Small obstacles detection on roads scenes using semantic segmentation for the safe navigation of autonomous vehicles. <i>Journal of Electronic Imaging</i> , 31(6), 061806-061806.	2022
5	Vision transformer for detecting critical situations and extracting functional scenario for automated vehicle safety assessment	Kang, M., Lee, W., Hwang, K., & Yoon, Y. (2022). Vision transformer for detecting critical situations and extracting functional scenario for automated vehicle safety assessment. <i>Sustainability</i> , 14(15), 9680.	2022
6	Implementing Development Status Scheme Based on Vehicle Ranging Technology	Ning, C. Y., Shang, J. J., Jiang, S. J., Pham, D. T., & Nguyen, T. X. H. (2022). Implementing Development Status Scheme Based on Vehicle Ranging Technology. In <i>Proceedings of International Conference on Computational Intelligence: ICCI 2020</i> (pp. 281-288). Springer Singapore.	2022

7	Object Detection for Autonomous Vehicles Using Deep Learning Algorithm	Sai Pavan, E. J., Ramya, P., Valarmathi, B., Chellatamilan, T., & Santhi, K. (2021). Object Detection for Autonomous Vehicles Using Deep Learning Algorithm. In Computational Vision and Bio-Inspired Computing: ICCVBIC 2020 (pp. 327-339). Springer Singapore.	2021
8	An automatic assessment of road condition from aerial imagery using modified VGG architecture in faster-RCNN framework	Malini, A., Priyadarshini, P., & Sabeena, S. (2021). An automatic assessment of road condition from aerial imagery using modified VGG architecture in faster-RCNN framework. Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems, 40(6), 11411-11422.	2021
9	Improvement of disability rights via geographic information science	Kocaman, S., & Ozdemir, N. (2020). Improvement of disability rights via geographic information science. Sustainability, 12(14), 5807.	2020

11.- Self-navigating Robot based on Fuzzy Rules Designed for Autonomous Wheelchair Mobility

Ignacio Algreto-Badillo, Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, Luis Alberto Morales-Rosales, Ernesto Cortés-Pérez, J Jesús Arellano Pimentel
2016, International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security

Citas: 3

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Exploring the differences between human and machine intelligence: towards technological singularity	Priyadarshini, I. (2021). Exploring the differences between human and machine intelligence: towards technological singularity. University of Delaware.	2021
2	Intelligence in cyberspace: the road to cyber singularity	Priyadarshini, I., & Cotton, C. (2021). Intelligence in cyberspace: the road to cyber singularity. Journal of Experimental & Theoretical Artificial Intelligence, 33(4), 683-717.	2021
3	Navigating a service robot for indoor complex environments	Chien, J. C., Dang, Z. Y., & Lee, J. D. (2019). Navigating a service robot for indoor complex environments. Applied Sciences, 9(3), 491.	2019

12.- The Windows-Users and-Intruder simulations Logs dataset (WUIL): An experimental framework for masquerade detection mechanisms

J Benito Camiña, Carlos Hernández-Gracidas, Raúl Monroy, Luis Trejo
2014, Expert Systems with Applications

Citas: 33

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Insider Threat Defense Strategies: Survey and Knowledge Integration	Song, C., Zhang, J., Ma, L., Hu, X., Zheng, J., & Yang, L. (2024, July). Insider Threat Defense Strategies: Survey and Knowledge Integration. In International Conference on Knowledge Science, Engineering and Management (pp. 106-122). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.	2024
2	内部安全威胁与室内人群移动轨迹基准数据集	赵颖, 赵鑫, 杨奎, 陈思明, 张卓, & 黄鑫. (2022). 内部安全威胁与室内人群移动轨迹基准数据集. Journal of Terahertz Science and Electronic Information Technology, 20(12).	2022

3	基于主机的高级持续威胁检测技术综述	徐志强, & 文雨. (2022). 基于主机的高级持续威胁检测技术综述. <i>Computer Science and Application</i> , 12, 233.	2022
4	Machine learning and anomaly detection for insider threat detection	Bartoszewski, F. W. (2022). Machine learning and anomaly detection for insider threat detection (Doctoral dissertation, Heriot-Watt University).	2022
5	Towards modeling host-based data for cyber-psychological assessment in cyber threat detection	Roy, K. C. (2022). Towards modeling host-based data for cyber-psychological assessment in cyber threat detection (Doctoral dissertation, The University of Texas at San Antonio).	2022
6	User-centered intrusion detection using heterogeneous data	Garchery, M. (2020). User-centered intrusion detection using heterogeneous data (Doctoral dissertation, Universität Passau).	2020
7	Intrusion Detection: Detecting Network Intruders Behind Anonymity Networks and Identifying Intruders on the Hosts by Modeling User Behaviors	Cao, Z. (2020). Intrusion Detection: Detecting Network Intruders Behind Anonymity Networks and Identifying Intruders on the Hosts by Modeling User Behaviors (Doctoral dissertation).	2020
8	UN NUEVO ALGORITMO BASADO EN APRENDIZAJE DE ENSAMBLE PARA EL PROBLEMA DE DETECCIÓN DE ANOMALÍAS.	PEREYRA VILLANUEVA, L. A. (2019). UN NUEVO ALGORITMO BASADO EN APRENDIZAJE DE ENSAMBLE PARA EL PROBLEMA DE DETECCIÓN DE ANOMALÍAS (Doctoral dissertation, Universidad Autónoma de Chihuahua).	2019
9	Comparing security concerns in the adoption of public cloud computing based on region of residence	Jacob, J. (2016). Comparing security concerns in the adoption of public cloud computing based on region of residence (Doctoral dissertation, Northcentral University).	2016
10	Contextual profiling of homogeneous user groups for masquerade detection	Ruthven, P. B. (2014). Contextual profiling of homogeneous user groups for masquerade detection (Master's thesis).	2014
11	Addressing insider attacks via forensic-ready risk management	Daubner, L., Macak, M., Matulevičius, R., Buhnova, B., Maksović, S., & Pitner, T. (2023). Addressing insider attacks via forensic-ready risk management. <i>Journal of Information Security and Applications</i> , 73, 103433.	2023
12	A Behavioral Graph Model for Host-Based Intrusion Detection.	Cao, Z., & Huang, S. H. S. (2023). A Behavioral Graph Model for Host-Based Intrusion Detection. <i>Journal of Information Assurance & Security</i> , 18(2).	2023
13	Detecting Masquerading Traitors from Process Visualization of Computer Usage	Macak, M., Ošlejšek, R., & Buhnova, B. (2023, November). Detecting Masquerading Traitors from Process Visualization of Computer Usage. In 2023 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications (TrustCom) (pp. 1935-1940). IEEE.	2023
14	Host-Based Intrusion Detection: A Behavioral Approach Using Graph Model	Cao, Z., & Stephen Huang, S. H. (2022, December). Host-Based Intrusion Detection: A Behavioral Approach Using Graph Model. In International Conference on Hybrid Intelligent Systems (pp. 1337-1346). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.	2022
15	Using binary classifiers for one-class classification	Kang, S. (2022). Using binary classifiers for one-class classification. <i>Expert Systems with Applications</i> , 187, 115920.	2022

16	内部威胁发现检测方法研究综述.	郭世泽, 张磊, 潘雨, 陶蔚, 白玮, 郑奇斌, ... & 潘志松. (2022). 内部威胁发现检测方法研究综述. <i>Journal of Data Acquisition & Processing/Shu Ju Cai Ji Yu Chu Li</i> , 37(3).	2022
17	Detection of insider threats using deep learning: a review	Lavanya, P., & Shankar Sriram, V. S. (2022). Detection of insider threats using deep learning: a review. <i>Computational Intelligence in Data Mining: Proceedings of ICCIDM 2021</i> , 41-57.	2022
18	A benchmark for visual analysis of insider threat detection.	Zhao, Y., Yang, K., Chen, S., Zhang, Z., Huang, X., Li, Q., ... & Fan, X. (2022). A benchmark for visual analysis of insider threat detection. <i>Sci. China Inf. Sci.</i> , 65(9), 1-3.	2022
19	Analysis and Evaluation for Detection Techniques on Host Anomalous Behavior Using Machine Learning	Li, B., Zhuang, H., Liu, R., & Liao, J. (2022, September). Analysis and Evaluation for Detection Techniques on Host Anomalous Behavior Using Machine Learning. In <i>2022 2nd International Conference on Computer Science, Electronic Information Engineering and Intelligent Control Technology (CEI)</i> (pp. 765-775). IEEE.	2022
20	Gsketch: A comprehensive graph analytic approach for masquerader detection based on file access graph	Jiang, J., Wang, X., Wang, Y., Lv, Q., Liu, M., Wang, T., & Wang, L. (2021, September). Gsketch: A comprehensive graph analytic approach for masquerader detection based on file access graph. In <i>2021 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)</i> (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2021
21	Qualitative data clustering to detect outliers	Nowak-Brzezińska, A., & Łazarz, W. (2021). Qualitative data clustering to detect outliers. <i>Entropy</i> , 23(7), 869.	2021
22	Comparative evaluation of different classification techniques for masquerade attack detection	Elmasry, W., Akbulut, A., & Zaim, A. H. (2020). Comparative evaluation of different classification techniques for masquerade attack detection. <i>International Journal of Information and Computer Security</i> , 13(2), 187-209.	2020
23	Empirical detection techniques of insider threat incidents	Alsowail, R. A., & Al-Shehari, T. (2020). Empirical detection techniques of insider threat incidents. <i>IEEE Access</i> , 8, 78385-78402.	2020
24	Obfuscation of malicious behaviors for thwarting masquerade detection systems based on locality features	Maestre Vidal, J., & Sotelo Monge, M. A. (2020). Obfuscation of malicious behaviors for thwarting masquerade detection systems based on locality features. <i>Sensors</i> , 20(7), 2084.	2020
25	Insight into insiders and it: A survey of insider threat taxonomies, analysis, modeling, and countermeasures	Homoliak, I., Toffalini, F., Guarnizo, J., Elovici, Y., & Ochoa, M. (2019). Insight into insiders and it: A survey of insider threat taxonomies, analysis, modeling, and countermeasures. <i>ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)</i> , 52(2), 1-40.	2019
26	Detecting intruders by user file access patterns	Huang, S. H. S., Cao, Z., Raines, C. E., Yang, M. N., & Simon, C. (2019). Detecting intruders by user file access patterns. In <i>Network and System Security: 13th International Conference, NSS 2019, Sapporo, Japan, December 15-18, 2019, Proceedings 13</i> (pp. 320-335). Springer International Publishing.	2019

27	Detecting Intruders by User File Access Patterns	Simon, C. (2019, December). Detecting Intruders by User File Access Patterns. In Network and System Security: 13th International Conference, NSS 2019, Sapporo, Japan, December 15-18, 2019, Proceedings (Vol. 11928, p. 320). Springer Nature.	2019
28	Employee profiling via aspect-based sentiment and network for insider threats detection	Soh, C., Yu, S., Narayanan, A., Duraisamy, S., & Chen, L. (2019). Employee profiling via aspect-based sentiment and network for insider threats detection. Expert Systems with Applications, 135, 351-361.	2019
29	An insider threat detection method based on user behavior analysis	Jiang, W., Tian, Y., Liu, W., & Liu, W. (2018). An insider threat detection method based on user behavior analysis. In Intelligent Information Processing IX: 10th IFIP TC 12 International Conference, IIP 2018, Nanning, China, October 19-22, 2018, Proceedings 10 (pp. 421-429). Springer International Publishing.	2018
30	Detection of masqueraders based on graph partitioning of file system access events	Toffalini, F., Homoliak, I., Harilal, A., Binder, A., & Ochoa, M. (2018, May). Detection of masqueraders based on graph partitioning of file system access events. In 2018 IEEE Security and Privacy Workshops (SPW) (pp. 217-227). IEEE.	2018
31	Insider threat detection and its future directions	Ko, L. L., Divakaran, D. M., Liao, Y. S., & Thing, V. L. (2017). Insider threat detection and its future directions. International Journal of Security and Networks, 12(3), 168-187.	2017
32	Online masquerade detection resistant to mimicry	Vidal, J. M., Orozco, A. L. S., & Villalba, L. J. G. (2016). Online masquerade detection resistant to mimicry. Expert Systems with Applications, 61, 162-180.	2016
33	内部威胁检测研究	杨光, 马建刚, 于爱民, & 孟丹. (2016). 内部威胁检测研究. Journal of Cyber Security 信息安全学报, 1(3).	2016

13.- Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations

Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, Luis Enrique Sucar, Manuel Montes-y-Gómez

2013, Multimedia tools and applications

Citas: 13

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Selecting and tailoring of images for online news content: a mixed-methods investigation of the needs and behaviour of image users in online journalism	Frankowska-Takhari, S. (2018). Selecting and tailoring of images for online news content: a mixed-methods investigation of the needs and behaviour of image users in online journalism.	2018
2	ROBUST IMAGE FEATURE DESCRIPTION, MATCHING AND APPLICATIONS	Dubey, S. R. (2016). ROBUST IMAGE FEATURE DESCRIPTION, MATCHING AND APPLICATIONS (Doctoral dissertation, INDIAN INSTITUTE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY).	2016
3	SEMANTIC-BASED IMAGE RETRIEVAL FOR MULTI-WORD TEXT QUERIES	ZAND, M. (2015). SEMANTIC-BASED IMAGE RETRIEVAL FOR MULTI-WORD TEXT QUERIES.	2015
4	Recent improvements in Image Retrieval	ComputerScienceandTechnology, T. (2014). Recent improvements in Image Retrieval.	2014

5	Pattern graph-based image retrieval system combining semantic and visual features	Allani, O., Zghal, H. B., Mellouli, N., & Akdag, H. (2017). Pattern graph-based image retrieval system combining semantic and visual features. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 76, 20287-20316.	2017
6	A combinatorial reasoning mechanism with topological and metric relations for change detection in river planforms: an application to globeland30's water bodies	Leng, L., Yang, G., & Chen, S. (2017). A combinatorial reasoning mechanism with topological and metric relations for change detection in river planforms: an application to globeland30's water bodies. <i>ISPRS international journal of geo-information</i> , 6(1), 13.	2017
7	Incorporating Spatial Distribution Feature with Local Patterns for Content-Based Image Retrieval	Wan, S., Jin, P., Xia, Y., & Yue, L. (2016). Incorporating Spatial Distribution Feature with Local Patterns for Content-Based Image Retrieval. <i>Chinese Journal of Electronics</i> , 25(5), 873-879.	2016
8	A multi-channel based illumination compensation mechanism for brightness invariant image retrieval	Dubey, S. R., Singh, S. K., & Singh, R. K. (2015). A multi-channel based illumination compensation mechanism for brightness invariant image retrieval. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 74, 11223-11253.	2015
9	Comparative assessment of efficiency for content based image retrieval systems using different wavelet features and pre-classifier	Chowdhury, M., & Kundu, M. K. (2015). Comparative assessment of efficiency for content based image retrieval systems using different wavelet features and pre-classifier. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 74, 11595-11630.	2015
10	Characteristics classification of durian varieties images for knowledge representation by using conceptual graph	Ibrahim, N. S., Abu Bakar, Z., & Abd Rahman, N. (2014). Characteristics classification of durian varieties images for knowledge representation by using conceptual graph. In <i>Information Retrieval Technology: 10th Asia Information Retrieval Societies Conference, AIRS 2014, Kuching, Malaysia, December 3-5, 2014. Proceedings 10</i> (pp. 124-135). Springer International Publishing.	2014
11	Recent Improvements in Image Retrieval	Zeng, Y. S., & Ying, X. L. (2014). Recent Improvements in Image Retrieval. <i>Advanced Materials Research</i> , 989, 4069-4073.	2014
12	: A New Description Logic for Spatial Reasoning in Images	Hudelot, C., Atif, J., & Bloch, I. (2014, September). : A New Description Logic for Spatial Reasoning in Images. In <i>European Conference on Computer Vision</i> (pp. 370-384). Cham: Springer International Publishing.	2014
13	Trends in semantic and digital media technologies	Grzegorzec, M., Granitzer, M., Rüger, S., Sintek, M., Declerck, T., & Romanelli, M. (2013). Trends in semantic and digital media technologies. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 62, 311-318.	2013

14.- Data fusion and label weighting for image retrieval based on spatio-conceptual information

Carlos Hernández-Gracidas, Antonio Juárez, L Enrique Sucar, Manuel Montes-y-Gómez, Luis Villaseñor

2010,

Citas: 7

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Towards Automated Semantic Explainability of Multimedia Feature Graphs. Information 2021, 1, 0	Wagenpfeil, S., Mc Kevitt, P., & Hemmje, M. (2021). Towards Automated Semantic Explainability of Multimedia Feature Graphs. Information 2021, 1, 0.	2021
2	Smart Multimedia Information Retrieval	Wagenpfeil, S., Kevitt, P. M., & Hemmje, M. (2023). Smart Multimedia Information Retrieval. Analytics, 2(1), 198-224.	2023
3	Explainable multimedia feature fusion for medical applications	Wagenpfeil, S., Mc Kevitt, P., Cheddad, A., & Hemmje, M. (2022). Explainable multimedia feature fusion for medical applications. Journal of Imaging, 8(4), 104.	2022
4	Query Construction and Result Presentation based on Graph Codes.	Wagenpfeil, S., Engel, F., McKevitt, P., & Hemmje, M. L. (2021, March). Query Construction and Result Presentation based on Graph Codes. In BIRDS+ WEPIR@ CHIIR (pp. 52-66).	2021
5	Fast and effective retrieval for large multimedia collections	Wagenpfeil, S., Vu, B., Mc Kevitt, P., & Hemmje, M. (2021). Fast and effective retrieval for large multimedia collections. Big Data and Cognitive Computing, 5(3), 33.	2021
6	Graph codes-2d projections of multimedia feature graphs for fast and effective retrieval	Wagenpfeil, S., Engel, F., McKevitt, P., & Hemmje, M. (2021). Graph codes-2d projections of multimedia feature graphs for fast and effective retrieval. International Journal of Computer and Information Engineering, 15(12), 636-648.	2021
7	Towards automated semantic explainability of multimedia feature graphs	Wagenpfeil, S., Mc Kevitt, P., & Hemmje, M. (2021). Towards automated semantic explainability of multimedia feature graphs. Information, 12(12), 502.	2021

15.- The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark

Hugo Jair Escalante, Carlos A Hernández, Jesus A Gonzalez, Aurelio López-López, Manuel Montes, Eduardo F Morales, L Enrique Sucar, Luis Villaseñor, Michael Grubinger

2010, Computer Vision and Image Understanding

Citas: 395

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Semantic decomposition and enhancement hashing for deep cross-modal retrieval	Fei, L., He, Z., Wong, W. K., Zhu, Q., Zhao, S., & Wen, J. (2025). Semantic decomposition and enhancement hashing for deep cross-modal retrieval. Pattern Recognition, 160, 111225.	2025
2	Phrase Decoupling Cross-Modal Hierarchical Matching and Progressive Position Correction for Visual Grounding	Xie, M., Wang, M., Li, H., Zhang, Y., Tao, D., & Yu, Z. (2025). Phrase Decoupling Cross-Modal Hierarchical Matching and Progressive Position Correction for Visual Grounding. IEEE Transactions on Multimedia.	2025
3	Prompt-guided bidirectional deep fusion network for referring image segmentation	Wu, J., Zhang, Y., Kampffmeyer, M., & Zhao, X. (2025). Prompt-guided bidirectional deep fusion network for referring image segmentation. Neurocomputing, 616, 128899.	2025

4	Online weighted hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Jiang, Z., Weng, Z., Li, R., Zhuang, H., & Lin, Z. (2025). Online weighted hashing for cross-modal retrieval. <i>Pattern Recognition</i> , 161, 111232.	2025
5	Global and local semantic enhancement of samples for cross-modal hashing	Teng, S., Chen, Y., Zheng, Z., Zhang, W., Kang, P., & Wu, N. (2025). Global and local semantic enhancement of samples for cross-modal hashing. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 614, 128678.	2025
6	SimVG: A Simple Framework for Visual Grounding with Decoupled Multi-modal Fusion	Dai, M., Yang, L., Xu, Y., Feng, Z., & Yang, W. (2025). SimVG: A Simple Framework for Visual Grounding with Decoupled Multi-modal Fusion. <i>Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems</i> , 37, 121670-121698.	2025
7	Adaptive Asymmetric Supervised Cross-Modal Hashing with consensus matrix	Li, Y., Long, J., Huang, Y., & Yang, Z. (2025). Adaptive Asymmetric Supervised Cross-Modal Hashing with consensus matrix. <i>Information Processing & Management</i> , 62(3), 104037.	2025
8	Multimodal large model pretraining, adaptation and efficiency optimization	Ji, L., Xiao, S., Feng, J., Gao, W., & Zhang, H. (2025). Multimodal large model pretraining, adaptation and efficiency optimization. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 619, 129138.	2025
9	Efficient Parameter-free Adaptive Hashing for Large-Scale Cross-Modal Retrieval	Li, B., Wu, Y., & Li, Z. (2025). Efficient Parameter-free Adaptive Hashing for Large-Scale Cross-Modal Retrieval. <i>International Journal of Approximate Reasoning</i> , 109383.	2025
10	Harlequin: Color-driven Generation of Synthetic Data for Referring Expression Comprehension	Parolari, L., Izzo, E., & Ballan, L. (2025). Harlequin: Color-driven Generation of Synthetic Data for Referring Expression Comprehension. In <i>International Conference on Pattern Recognition</i> (pp. 292-307). Springer, Cham.	2025
11	End-to-end Visual Grounding Based on Query Text Guidance and Multi-stage Reasoning	Wang, C., Luo, W., Zhu, J. R., Xia, Y. C., He, J., & Gu, L. C. (2024). End-to-end Visual Grounding Based on Query Text Guidance and Multi-stage Reasoning. <i>Journal of Computers</i> , 35(1), 83-95.	2024
12	Referring expression segmentation: from conventional to generalized	Liu, C. (2024). Referring expression segmentation: from conventional to generalized.	2024
13	半配对的多模态询问哈希方法	庾骏, 马江涛, 咸阳, 侯瑞霞, & 孙伟. (2024). 半配对的多模态询问哈希方法. <i>电子与信息学报</i> , 46(2), 481-491.	2024
14	Deep cross-modal hashing with multi-task latent space learning	Wu, S., Yuan, X., Xiao, G., Lew, M. S., & Gao, X. (2024). Deep cross-modal hashing with multi-task latent space learning. <i>Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence</i> , 136, 108944.	2024
15	Online hashing with partially known labels for cross-modal retrieval	Shu, Z., Li, L., & Yu, Z. (2024). Online hashing with partially known labels for cross-modal retrieval. <i>Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence</i> , 138, 109367.	2024
16	ResVG: Enhancing Relation and Semantic Understanding in Multiple Instances for Visual Grounding	Zheng, M., Zhang, J., Chen, Q., Peng, Y., & Liu, Y. (2024, October). ResVG: Enhancing Relation and Semantic Understanding in Multiple Instances for Visual Grounding. In <i>Proceedings of the 32nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia</i> (pp. 1187-1196).	2024

17	Deep Noisy Multi-label Learning for Robust Cross-Modal Retrieval	Pu, R., Peng, D., & Hua, F. (2024, October). Deep Noisy Multi-label Learning for Robust Cross-Modal Retrieval. In Chinese Conference on Pattern Recognition and Computer Vision (PRCV) (pp. 304-317). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.	2024
18	Enabling Secure Cross-Modal Search over Encrypted Data via Federated Learning	Wang, X., Li, J., Liu, Z., Tang, Q., & Wang, X. (2024). Enabling Secure Cross-Modal Search over Encrypted Data via Federated Learning. IEEE Internet of Things Journal.	2024
19	Deep supervised fused similarity hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Ng, W. W., Xu, Y., Tian, X., & Wang, H. (2024). Deep supervised fused similarity hashing for cross-modal retrieval. Multimedia Tools and Applications, 1-19.	2024
20	Grounding Language in Images and Videos	Sadhu, A. (2024). Grounding Language in Images and Videos (Doctoral dissertation, University of Southern California).	2024
21	Distribution Consistency Guided Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Sun, Y., Liu, K., Li, Y., Ren, Z., Dai, J., & Peng, D. (2024, October). Distribution Consistency Guided Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval. In Proceedings of the 32nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia (pp. 5623-5632).	2024
22	Dual semantic fusion hashing for multi-label cross-modal retrieval	Liu, K., Gong, Y., Cao, Y., Ren, Z., Peng, D., & Sun, Y. (2024, August). Dual semantic fusion hashing for multi-label cross-modal retrieval. In International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence Organization, IJCAI (pp. 4569-4577).	2024
23	Unsupervised Online Cross-modal Hashing With Multiple Association Exploitation	Kang, X., Liu, X., Zhang, X., Xue, W., Nie, X., Wang, S., & Yin, Y. (2024, July). Unsupervised Online Cross-modal Hashing With Multiple Association Exploitation. In 2024 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2024
24	Semantic Preservation and Hash Fusion Network for Unsupervised Cross-Modal Retrieval	Shu, X., & Li, M. (2024, August). Semantic Preservation and Hash Fusion Network for Unsupervised Cross-Modal Retrieval. In Asia-Pacific Web (APWeb) and Web-Age Information Management (WAIM) Joint International Conference on Web and Big Data (pp. 146-161). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.	2024
25	Segvg: Transferring object bounding box to segmentation for visual grounding	Kang, W., Liu, G., Shah, M., & Yan, Y. (2024, September). Segvg: Transferring object bounding box to segmentation for visual grounding. In European Conference on Computer Vision (pp. 57-75). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.	2024
26	Identifying Question Ambiguity in Visual Question Answering	Venkatesh, A. K. (2024). Identifying Question Ambiguity in Visual Question Answering (Master's thesis, University of Colorado at Boulder).	2024
27	From methods to datasets: A survey on Image-Caption Generators	Agarwal, L., & Verma, B. (2024). From methods to datasets: A survey on Image-Caption Generators. Multimedia Tools and Applications, 83(9), 28077-28123.	2024
28	Actress: Active retraining for semi-supervised visual grounding	Kang, W., Qu, M., Wei, Y., & Yan, Y. (2024). Actress: Active retraining for semi-supervised visual grounding. arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.03251.	2024

29	Language conditioned multi-scale visual attention networks for visual grounding	Yao, H., Wang, L., Cai, C., Wang, W., Zhang, Z., & Shang, X. (2024). Language conditioned multi-scale visual attention networks for visual grounding. <i>Image and Vision Computing</i> , 150, 105242.	2024
30	Graph convolutional multi-label hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Shen, X., Chen, Y., Liu, W., Zheng, Y., Sun, Q. S., & Pan, S. (2024). Graph convolutional multi-label hashing for cross-modal retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems</i> .	2024
31	Knowledge graph construction in hyperbolic space for automatic image annotation	Lotfi, F., Jamzad, M., Beigy, H., Farhood, H., Sheng, Q. Z., & Beheshti, A. (2024). Knowledge graph construction in hyperbolic space for automatic image annotation. <i>Image and Vision Computing</i> , 151, 105293.	2024
32	Visual Grounding with Multi-modal Conditional Adaptation	Yao, R., Xiong, S., Zhao, Y., & Rong, Y. (2024, October). Visual Grounding with Multi-modal Conditional Adaptation. In <i>Proceedings of the 32nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia</i> (pp. 3877-3886).	2024
33	一种基于对比学习大模型的视觉定位方法	陆庆阳, 袁广林, 朱虹, 秦晓燕, & 薛模根. (2024). 一种基于对比学习大模型的视觉定位方法. <i>电子学报</i> , 52(10), 3448-3458.	2024
34	Adaptive Kernel-Attention Framework for Multimodal Representation Learning	James, L., Monroe, Z., & Roy, J. (2024). Adaptive Kernel-Attention Framework for Multimodal Representation Learning.	2024
35	OneRef: Unified One-tower Expression Grounding and Segmentation with Mask Referring Modeling	Xiao, L., Yang, X., Peng, F., Wang, Y., & Xu, C. (2024). OneRef: Unified One-tower Expression Grounding and Segmentation with Mask Referring Modeling. <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.08021</i> .	2024
36	Robust Contrastive Cross-modal Hashing with Noisy Labels	Wang, L., Qin, Y., Sun, Y., Peng, D., Peng, X., & Hu, P. (2024, October). Robust Contrastive Cross-modal Hashing with Noisy Labels. In <i>Proceedings of the 32nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia</i> (pp. 5752-5760).	2024
37	Category correlations embedded semantic centers hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Fan, W., Yang, C., Luo, K., Zhang, M., & Li, H. (2024). Category correlations embedded semantic centers hashing for cross-modal retrieval. <i>Information Sciences</i> , 683, 121262.	2024
38	DCMFNet: Deep Cross-Modal Fusion Network for Different Modalities with Iterative Gated Fusion	Huang, Z., Xue, M., Liu, Y., Xu, K., Li, J., & Yu, C. (2024, June). DCMFNet: Deep Cross-Modal Fusion Network for Different Modalities with Iterative Gated Fusion. In <i>Proceedings of the 50th Graphics Interface Conference</i> (pp. 1-12).	2024
39	Network for Unsupervised Cross-Modal	Shu, X., & Li, M. (2024). Network for Unsupervised Cross-Modal. In <i>Web and Big Data: 8th International Joint Conference, APWeb-WAIM 2024, Jinhua, China, August 30-September 1, 2024, Proceedings, Part V</i> (Vol. 14965, p. 146). Springer Nature.	2024

40	CMIRNet: Cross-Modal Interactive Reasoning Network for Referring Image Segmentation	Xu, M., Xiao, T., Liu, Y., Tang, H., Hu, Y., & Nie, L. (2024). CMIRNet: Cross-Modal Interactive Reasoning Network for Referring Image Segmentation. <i>IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology</i> .	2024
41	Bridging Modalities: A Survey of Cross-Modal Image-Text Retrieval	Li, T., Kong, L., Yang, X., Wang, B., & Xu, J. (2024). Bridging Modalities: A Survey of Cross-Modal Image-Text Retrieval. <i>Chinese Journal of Information Fusion</i> , 1(1), 79-92.	2024
42	Improving visual grounding with multi-modal interaction and auto-regressive vertex generation	Qin, X., Li, F., He, C., Pei, R., & Zhang, X. (2024). Improving visual grounding with multi-modal interaction and auto-regressive vertex generation. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 598, 128227.	2024
43	基于迁移知识的跨模态双重哈希	钟建奇, 林秋斌, & 曹文明. (2024). 基于迁移知识的跨模态双重哈希. <i>电子学报</i> , 1-12.	2024
44	Towards Visual Grounding: A Survey	Xiao, L., Yang, X., Lan, X., Wang, Y., & Xu, C. (2024). Towards Visual Grounding: A Survey. <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.20206</i> .	2024
45	A comprehensive construction of deep neural network-based encoder-decoder framework for automatic image captioning systems	Rahman, M. M., Uzzaman, A., Sami, S. I., Khatun, F., & Bhuiyan, M. A. A. (2024). A comprehensive construction of deep neural network-based encoder-decoder framework for automatic image captioning systems. <i>IET Image Processing</i> , 18(14), 4778-4798.	2024
46	Contrastive Incomplete Cross-Modal Hashing	Luo, H., Zhang, Z., & Nie, L. (2024). Contrastive Incomplete Cross-Modal Hashing. <i>IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering</i> .	2024
47	Visual grounding with attention-driven constraint balancing	Kang, W., Zhou, L., Wu, J., Sun, C., & Yan, Y. (2024). Visual grounding with attention-driven constraint balancing. <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.03243</i> .	2024
48	Overview of Multimodal Machine Learning	Al-Zoghby, A., Al-Awadly, E., Ebada, A. I., & Awad, W. A. E. K. (2024). Overview of Multimodal Machine Learning. <i>ACM Transactions on Asian and Low-Resource Language Information Processing</i> .	2024
49	Deep semantics-preserving cross-modal hashing	Lai, Z., Fang, X., & Kong, H. (2024). Deep semantics-preserving cross-modal hashing. <i>Big Data Research</i> , 38, 100494.	2024
50	Towards unbiased visual language reasoning and consistent segmentation	Huang, J. (2023). Towards unbiased visual language reasoning and consistent segmentation.	2023
51	RetPur: Diffusion Purification Model for Defending Hash Retrieval Target Attacks	Liu, Y., Wu, X., Wu, J., Senhadji, L., & Shu, H. (2023). RetPur: Diffusion Purification Model for Defending Hash Retrieval Target Attacks.	2023
52	Unsupervised hashing retrieval via efficient correlation distillation	Xi, Z., Wang, X., & Cheng, P. (2023). Unsupervised hashing retrieval via efficient correlation distillation. <i>IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology</i> , 33(7), 3529-3541.	2023

53	基于文本引导对抗哈希的跨模态检索方法.	朱杰. (2022). 基于文本引导对抗哈希的跨模态检索方法. <i>Application Research of Computers/Jisuanji Yingyong Yanjiu</i> , 39(2).	2022
54	Multimodal Semi-supervised Learning for Sentiment Analysis of Image Macros	Phạm, T. H. T., & Ngô, T. A. (2022). Multimodal Semi-supervised Learning for Sentiment Analysis of Image Macros (Doctoral dissertation, FPTU HN).	2022
55	Developing a deep neural network-based encoder-decoder framework in automatic image captioning systems	Rahman, M. M., Uzzaman, A., Sami, S. I., & Khatun, F. (2022). Developing a deep neural network-based encoder-decoder framework in automatic image captioning systems.	2022
56	Information Fusion: Machine Learning Methods	Li, J., Zhang, B., & Zhang, D. (2022). <i>Information Fusion: Machine Learning Methods</i> . Springer Nature.	2022
57	Computational methods for integrating vision and language	Kanatani, K., & Sugaya, Y. (2022). <i>Computational methods for integrating vision and language</i> . Springer Nature.	2022
58	NEVIS'22: A Stream of 100 Tasks Sampled from 30 Years of Computer Vision Research	Bornschein, J., Galashov, A., Hemsley, R., Rannen-Triki, A., Chen, Y., Chaudhry, A., ... & Ranzato, M. A. (2022). NEVIS'22: A Stream of 100 Tasks Sampled from 30 Years of Computer Vision Research. <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2211.11747</i> .	2022
59	语言引导的多粒度特征融合目标分割方法	谭荃戈, 王蓉, & 吴澳. (2022). 语言引导的多粒度特征融合目标分割方法. <i>北京航空航天大学学报</i> , 50(2), 542-550.	2022
60	Language-guided target segmentation method based on multi-granularity feature fusion	TAN, Q., WANG, R., & WU, A. (2022). Language-guided target segmentation method based on multi-granularity feature fusion. <i>北京航空航天大学学报</i> , 50(2), 542-550.	2022
61	Visual grounding: building cross-modal visual-text alignment	Yang, Z. (2021). <i>Visual grounding: building cross-modal visual-text alignment</i> . University of Rochester.	2021
62	Descripción automática de imágenes	Pallarés Font de Mora, P. (2021). <i>Descripción automática de imágenes</i> .	2021
63	Quelques contributions à l'extraction, l'enrichissement des connaissances et à la prédiction de données spatio-temporelles massives	Mellouli-Nauwynck, N. (2021). <i>Quelques contributions à l'extraction, l'enrichissement des connaissances et à la prédiction de données spatio-temporelles massives</i> (Doctoral dissertation, Université Paris 8).	2021
64	基于对象特征的深度哈希跨模态检索.	朱杰, 白弘焜, 张仲羽, 谢博望, & 张俊三. (2021). 基于对象特征的深度哈希跨模态检索. <i>Journal of Frontiers of Computer Science & Technology</i> , 15(5).	2021
65	Improving one-stage visual grounding by recursive sub-query construction	Yang, Z., Chen, T., Wang, L., & Luo, J. (2020). Improving one-stage visual grounding by recursive sub-query construction. In <i>Computer Vision-ECCV 2020: 16th European Conference, Glasgow, UK, August 23-28, 2020, Proceedings, Part XIV 16</i> (pp. 387-404). Springer International Publishing.	2020
66	Content Based Image Retrieval by Deep Multi Modal Hashing for Sentinel Images	Bank, H. (2020). <i>Content Based Image Retrieval by Deep Multi Modal Hashing for Sentinel Images</i> .	2020

67	Language Controls More Than Top-Down Attention: Modulating Bottom-Up Visual Processing with Referring Expressions	Can, O. A., Kesen, I., & Yuret, D. (2020). Language Controls More Than Top-Down Attention: Modulating Bottom-Up Visual Processing with Referring Expressions.	2020
68	Learning and evaluation of topics via distributional semantics	Augustin, A. (2020). Learning and evaluation of topics via distributional semantics (Doctoral dissertation, University of Southampton).	2020
69	Deep learning and reinforcement learning methods for grounded goal-oriented dialogue	de Vries, H. (2020). Deep learning and reinforcement learning methods for grounded goal-oriented dialogue.	2020
70	从视觉到文本: 图像描述生成的研究进展综述	魏忠钰, 范智昊, 王瑞泽, 承怡菁, 赵王榕, & 黄萱菁. (2020). 从视觉到文本: 图像描述生成的研究进展综述. 中文信息学报, 34(7), 19-29.	2020
71	Quantitative Phase Retrieval with Digital In-line Holographic Microscopy	D'Angelo, J. M. (2020). Quantitative Phase Retrieval with Digital In-line Holographic Microscopy (Doctoral dissertation, Northern Arizona University).	2020
72	Image annotation method based on graph volume network	Zhu, Z., & Hangchi, Z. (2020, January). Image annotation method based on graph volume network. In 2020 International Conference on Intelligent Transportation, Big Data & Smart City (ICITBS) (pp. 885-888). IEEE.	2020
73	Efficient Privacy-Aware Imagery Data Analysis	Tian, Y. (2019). Efficient Privacy-Aware Imagery Data Analysis. Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University.	2019
74	Deep learning for image captioning: an encoder-decoder architecture with soft attention	Gómez Martínez, M. (2019). Deep learning for image captioning: an encoder-decoder architecture with soft attention.	2019
75	Visual Commonality and Specificity	Li, Y. (2019). Visual Commonality and Specificity. The Chinese University of Hong Kong (Hong Kong).	2019
76	Understanding the message of images	Weiland, L. (2018). Understanding the message of images.	2018
77	MAESTRO EN INGENIERÍA	RESENDIZ, J. D. H. (2018). MAESTRO EN INGENIERÍA (Doctoral dissertation, UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE VICTORIA).	2018
78	Dynamic Multimodal Object Segmentation based on natural language referring expressions and its applications	Margffoy Tuay, E. A. (2018). Dynamic Multimodal Object Segmentation based on natural language referring expressions and its applications.	2018
79	Locating people in video surveillance from semantic descriptions	Halstead, M. A. (2017). Locating people in video surveillance from semantic descriptions (Doctoral dissertation, Queensland University of Technology).	2017
80	LIP6@ CLEF2017: Multi-Modal Spatial Role Labeling using Word Embeddings.	Zablocki, E., Bordes, P., Soulier, L., Piwowarski, B., & Gallinari, P. (2017). LIP6@ CLEF2017: Multi-Modal Spatial Role Labeling using Word Embeddings. In CLEF (Working Notes).	2017
81	Bayesian aggregation of categorical distributions with applications in crowdsourcing	Augustin, A., Venanzi, M., Hare, J., Rogers, A., & Jennings, N. (2017, July). Bayesian aggregation of categorical distributions with applications in crowdsourcing. AAAI Press/International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence.	2017
82	Multimodal Learning for Vision and Language	Mao, J. (2017). Multimodal Learning for Vision and Language. University of California, Los Angeles.	2017

83	Understanding Spatial Semantics in Natural Language	Mazalov, A. (2016). Understanding Spatial Semantics in Natural Language.	2016
84	Computational methods for integrating vision and language	Barnard, K. (2016). Computational methods for integrating vision and language. Morgan & Claypool Publishers.	2016
85	Easy things first: Installments improve referring expression generation for objects in photographs	Zarrieß, S., & Schlangen, D. (2016, August). Easy things first: Installments improve referring expression generation for objects in photographs. In Proceedings of the 54th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers) (pp. 610-620).	2016
86	Towards Generating Colour Terms for Referents in Photographs: Prefer the Expected or the Unexpected?	Zarrieß, S., & Schlangen, D. (2016). Towards Generating Colour Terms for Referents in Photographs: Prefer the Expected or the Unexpected?. In Proceedings of the 9th International Natural Language Generation conference (pp. 246-255).	2016
87	Segmentation from natural language expressions	Hu, R., Rohrbach, M., & Darrell, T. (2016). Segmentation from natural language expressions. In Computer Vision-ECCV 2016: 14th European Conference, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, October 11-14, 2016, Proceedings, Part I 14 (pp. 108-124). Springer International Publishing.	2016
88	Grounding, Justification, Adaptation: Towards Machines That Mean What They Say	Schlangen, D. (2016). Grounding, Justification, Adaptation: Towards Machines That Mean What They Say. In Proceedings of the 20th Workshop on the Semantics and Pragmatics of Dialogue (JerSem).	2016
89	Describing Images using a Multilayer Framework based on Qualitative Spatial Models	Wang, T., & Shi, H. (2015). Describing Images using a Multilayer Framework based on Qualitative Spatial Models. Baltic International Yearbook of Cognition, Logic and Communication, 10(1), 10.	2015
90	Domain Transfer Learning for Object and Action Recognition	Zheng, J. (2015). Domain Transfer Learning for Object and Action Recognition (Doctoral dissertation, University of Maryland, College Park).	2015
91	基于标注词相关度的图像自动标注改善方法	徐功文, 廖明海, 郑森红, 赵洪鑫, 张志军, 赵倩, & 许春秀. (2015). 基于标注词相关度的图像自动标注改善方法. 计算机科学, 42(S1), 238-240.	2015
92	网络控制器 OpenDaylight 的研究与分析	许名广, 刘亚萍, & 邓文平. (2015). 网络控制器 OpenDaylight 的研究与分析. 计算机科学, (S1), 249-252.	2015
93	Optimierung von Algorithmen zur Videoanalyse: Ein Analyseframework für die Anforderungen lokaler Fernsehsender	Ritter, M. (2014). Optimierung von Algorithmen zur Videoanalyse: Ein Analyseframework für die Anforderungen lokaler Fernsehsender (Doctoral dissertation, Technische Universität Chemnitz).	2014
94	Optimierung von Algorithmen zur Videoanalyse für die Anforderungen lokaler Fernsehsender	Ritter, M. (2014). Optimierung von Algorithmen zur Videoanalyse für die Anforderungen lokaler Fernsehsender (Doctoral dissertation, Technische Universität Chemnitz).	2014
95	Multiple-instance active learning with online labeling	Salmani, K. (2013). Multiple-instance active learning with online labeling (Doctoral dissertation).	2013

96	Multi-Instance Active Learning with Online Labeling	Niasar, K. S. (2013). Multi-Instance Active Learning with Online Labeling (Doctoral dissertation, Texas Tech University).	2013
97	On the use of visual conceptual information for the indexing and retrieval of image regions	Jarrar, R. (2012). On the use of visual conceptual information for the indexing and retrieval of image regions (Doctoral dissertation, Monash University).	2012
98	Semantic image understanding: from pixel to word	Fu, H. (2012). Semantic image understanding: from pixel to word (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nottingham).	2012
99	Information Fusion	Li, S., Yang, B., & Hu, J. (2010). Information Fusion.	2010
100	Ontology-based image annotation	Yuee, L. (2010). Ontology-based image annotation (Doctoral dissertation, Queensland University of Technology).	2010
101	CKDH: CLIP-based Knowledge Distillation Hashing for Cross-modal Retrieval	Li, J., Wong, W. K., Jiang, L., Fang, X., Xie, S., & Xu, Y. (2024). CKDH: CLIP-based Knowledge Distillation Hashing for Cross-modal Retrieval. IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology.	2024
102	LGR-NET: Language Guided Reasoning Network for Referring Expression Comprehension	Lu, M., Li, R., Feng, F., Ma, Z., & Wang, X. (2024). LGR-NET: Language Guided Reasoning Network for Referring Expression Comprehension. IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology.	2024
103	Online Cross-modal Hashing With Dynamic Prototype	Kang, X., Liu, X., Xue, W., Nie, X., & Yin, Y. (2024). Online Cross-modal Hashing With Dynamic Prototype. ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications and Applications, 20(8), 1-18.	2024
104	Discrete online cross-modal hashing with consistency preservation	Kang, X., Liu, X., Xue, W., Zhang, X., Nie, X., & Yin, Y. (2024). Discrete online cross-modal hashing with consistency preservation. Pattern Recognition, 110688.	2024
105	Semi-paired Multi-modal Query Hashing Method	YU, J., MA, J., XIAN, Y., HOU, R., & SUN, W. (2024). Semi-paired Multi-modal Query Hashing Method. 电子与信息学报, 46(2), 481-491.	2024
106	Collaborative Position Reasoning Network for Referring Image Segmentation	Cao, J., Dai, B., Li, Y., Qin, X., & Wang, J. (2024). Collaborative Position Reasoning Network for Referring Image Segmentation. arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.11775.	2024
107	Hierarchical feature selection based on neighborhood interclass spacing from fine to coarse	Lin, Z., & Lin, Y. (2024). Hierarchical feature selection based on neighborhood interclass spacing from fine to coarse. Neurocomputing, 575, 127319.	2024
108	Efficient Discriminative Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Huang, J., Kang, P., Fang, X., Han, N., Xie, S., & Gao, H. (2024). Efficient Discriminative Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval. IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems.	2024
109	Deep Self-Supervised Hashing With Fine-Grained Similarity Mining for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Han, L., Wang, R., Chen, C., Zhang, H., Zhang, Y., & Zhang, W. (2024). Deep Self-Supervised Hashing With Fine-Grained Similarity Mining for Cross-Modal Retrieval. IEEE Access, 12, 31756-31770.	2024

110	Text-assisted attention-based cross-modal hashing	Yuan, X., Shan, S., Huo, Y., Jiang, J., & Wu, S. (2024). Text-assisted attention-based cross-modal hashing. <i>International Journal of Multimedia Information Retrieval</i> , 13(1), 3.	2024
111	Similarity Transitivity Broken-Aware Multi-Modal Hashing	Tu, R. C., Mao, X. L., Liu, J., Wei, W., & Huang, H. (2024). Similarity Transitivity Broken-Aware Multi-Modal Hashing. <i>IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering</i> .	2024
112	Key Points Centered Sparse Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Hu, Z., Cheung, Y. M., Li, M., Lan, W., & Zhang, D. (2024, April). Key Points Centered Sparse Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval. In <i>ICASSP 2024-2024 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)</i> (pp. 8431-8435). IEEE.	2024
113	Manufacturing domain instruction comprehension using synthetic data	Johari, K., Tong, C. T. Z., Bhardwaj, R., Subbaraju, V., Kim, J. J., & Tan, U. X. (2024). Manufacturing domain instruction comprehension using synthetic data. <i>The Visual Computer</i> , 1-15.	2024
114	Supervised Semantic-Embedded Hashing for Multimedia Retrieval	Chen, Y., Long, J., Guo, L., & Yang, Z. (2024). Supervised Semantic-Embedded Hashing for Multimedia Retrieval. <i>Knowledge-Based Systems</i> , 112023.	2024
115	BadCM: Invisible Backdoor Attack Against Cross-Modal Learning	Zhang, Z., Yuan, X., Zhu, L., Song, J., & Nie, L. (2024). BadCM: Invisible Backdoor Attack Against Cross-Modal Learning. <i>IEEE Transactions on Image Processing</i> .	2024
116	Robust Asymmetric Cross-Modal Hashing Retrieval With Dual Semantic Enhancement	Teng, S., Xu, T., Zheng, Z., Wu, N., Zhang, W., & Teng, L. (2024). Robust Asymmetric Cross-Modal Hashing Retrieval With Dual Semantic Enhancement. <i>IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems</i> .	2024
117	When Visual Grounding Meets Gigapixel-level Large-scale Scenes: Benchmark and Approach	Ma, T., Bai, B., Lin, H., Wang, H., Wang, Y., Luo, L., & Fang, L. (2024). When Visual Grounding Meets Gigapixel-level Large-scale Scenes: Benchmark and Approach. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition</i> (pp. 22119-22128).	2024
118	Robust online hashing with label semantic enhancement for cross-modal retrieval	Li, L., Shu, Z., Yu, Z., & Wu, X. J. (2024). Robust online hashing with label semantic enhancement for cross-modal retrieval. <i>Pattern Recognition</i> , 145, 109972.	2024
119	Cross-Modal Hashing Method with Properties of Hamming Space: A New Perspective	Hu, Z., Cheung, Y. M., Li, M., & Lan, W. (2024). Cross-Modal Hashing Method with Properties of Hamming Space: A New Perspective. <i>IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence</i> .	2024
120	HiVG: Hierarchical Multimodal Fine-grained Modulation for Visual Grounding	Xiao, L., Yang, X., Peng, F., Wang, Y., & Xu, C. (2024). HiVG: Hierarchical Multimodal Fine-grained Modulation for Visual Grounding. <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.13400</i> .	2024
121	MFVG: A Visual Grounding Network with Multi-scale Fusion	Chen, P., Qi, K., Tao, X., Xu, W., & Zhang, J. (2024, May). MFVG: A Visual Grounding Network with Multi-scale Fusion. In <i>Proceedings of the 2024 International Conference on Multimedia Retrieval</i> (pp. 713-721).	2024

122	Large-Scale Cross-Modal Hashing with Unified Learning and Multi-Object Regional Correlation Reasoning	Li, B., & Li, Z. (2024). Large-Scale Cross-Modal Hashing with Unified Learning and Multi-Object Regional Correlation Reasoning. <i>Neural Networks</i> , 171, 276-292.	2024
123	Towards language-guided visual recognition via dynamic convolutions	Luo, G., Zhou, Y., Sun, X., Wu, Y., Gao, Y., & Ji, R. (2024). Towards language-guided visual recognition via dynamic convolutions. <i>International Journal of Computer Vision</i> , 132(1), 1-19.	2024
124	A survey of efficient fine-tuning methods for Vision-Language Models—Prompt and Adapter	Xing, J., Liu, J., Wang, J., Sun, L., Chen, X., Gu, X., & Wang, Y. (2024). A survey of efficient fine-tuning methods for Vision-Language Models—Prompt and Adapter. <i>Computers & Graphics</i> .	2024
125	Asymmetric low-rank double-level cooperation for scalable discrete cross-modal hashing	Chen, R., Tan, J., Zhou, Y., Yang, Z., Nie, F., & Chen, T. (2024). Asymmetric low-rank double-level cooperation for scalable discrete cross-modal hashing. <i>Expert Systems with Applications</i> , 237, 121703.	2024
126	ScanFormer: Referring Expression Comprehension by Iteratively Scanning	Su, W., Miao, P., Dou, H., & Li, X. (2024). ScanFormer: Referring Expression Comprehension by Iteratively Scanning. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition</i> (pp. 13449-13458).	2024
127	Adaptive semi-paired query hashing for multi-modal retrieval	Yu, J., Huang, W., Li, Z., Li, K., Shu, Z., Wang, Q., & Jiao, J. (2023). Adaptive semi-paired query hashing for multi-modal retrieval. <i>Digital Signal Processing</i> , 143, 104226.	2023
128	CMMix: Cross-Modal Mix Augmentation Between Images and Texts for Visual Grounding	Hong, T., Wang, Y., Sun, X., Li, X., & Ma, J. (2023, November). CMMix: Cross-Modal Mix Augmentation Between Images and Texts for Visual Grounding. In <i>International Conference on Neural Information Processing</i> (pp. 471-482). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.	2023
129	Neural module networks: a review	Fashandi, H. (2023). Neural module networks: a review. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 126518.	2023
130	Confidence-aware Pseudo-label Learning for Weakly Supervised Visual Grounding	Liu, Y., Zhang, J., Chen, Q., & Peng, Y. (2023). Confidence-aware Pseudo-label Learning for Weakly Supervised Visual Grounding. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision</i> (pp. 2828-2838).	2023
131	Joint semantic preserving sparse hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Hu, Z., Cheung, Y. M., Li, M., Lan, W., Zhang, D., & Liu, Q. (2023). Joint semantic preserving sparse hashing for cross-modal retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology</i> .	2023
132	Polyformer: Referring image segmentation as sequential polygon generation	Liu, J., Ding, H., Cai, Z., Zhang, Y., Satzoda, R. K., Mahadevan, V., & Manmatha, R. (2023). Polyformer: Referring image segmentation as sequential polygon generation. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition</i> (pp. 18653-18663).	2023
133	Fuzzy rough sets-based incremental feature selection for hierarchical classification	Huang, W., She, Y., He, X., & Ding, W. (2023). Fuzzy rough sets-based incremental feature selection for hierarchical classification. <i>IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems</i> .	2023

134	Language adaptive weight generation for multi-task visual grounding	Su, W., Miao, P., Dou, H., Wang, G., Qiao, L., Li, Z., & Li, X. (2023). Language adaptive weight generation for multi-task visual grounding. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (pp. 10857-10866).	2023
135	Continuous cross-modal hashing	Zheng, H., Wang, J., Zhen, X., Song, J., Zheng, F., Lu, K., & Qi, G. J. (2023). Continuous cross-modal hashing. Pattern Recognition, 142, 109662.	2023
136	Data-aware proxy hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Tu, R. C., Mao, X. L., Ji, W., Wei, W., & Huang, H. (2023, July). Data-aware proxy hashing for cross-modal retrieval. In Proceedings of the 46th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval (pp. 686-696).	2023
137	MAFH: Multilabel aware framework for bit-scalable cross-modal hashing	Li, X., Yu, J., Lu, H., Jiang, S., Li, Z., & Yao, P. (2023). MAFH: Multilabel aware framework for bit-scalable cross-modal hashing. Knowledge-Based Systems, 279, 110922.	2023
138	Local-global coordination with transformers for referring image segmentation	Liu, F., Kong, Y., Zhang, L., Feng, G., & Yin, B. (2023). Local-global coordination with transformers for referring image segmentation. Neurocomputing, 522, 39-52.	2023
139	Cross-Modal Retrieval: A Systematic Review of Methods and Future Directions	Zhu, L., Wang, T., Li, F., Li, J., Zhang, Z., & Shen, H. T. (2023). Cross-Modal Retrieval: A Systematic Review of Methods and Future Directions. arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.14263.	2023
140	Graph Convolutional Network Semantic Enhancement Hashing for Self-supervised Cross-Modal Retrieval	Hu, J., Li, M., & Zhang, J. (2023, September). Graph Convolutional Network Semantic Enhancement Hashing for Self-supervised Cross-Modal Retrieval. In International Conference on Artificial Neural Networks (pp. 410-422). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.	2023
141	A Cross-Modal Hash Retrieval Method with Fused Triples	Li, W., Mei, H., Li, Y., Yu, J., Zhang, X., Xue, X., & Wang, J. (2023). A Cross-Modal Hash Retrieval Method with Fused Triples. Applied Sciences, 13(18), 10524.	2023
142	A triple fusion model for cross-modal deep hashing retrieval	Wang, H., Zhao, K., & Zhao, D. (2023). A triple fusion model for cross-modal deep hashing retrieval. Multimedia Systems, 29(1), 347-359.	2023
143	Language-Guided Diffusion Model for Visual Grounding	Chen, S., & Li, B. (2023). Language-Guided Diffusion Model for Visual Grounding. arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.09599.	2023
144	图像—文本多模态指代表达理解研究综述	王丽安, 缪佩翰, 苏伟, 李玺, 吉娜烨, & 姜燕冰. (2023). 图像—文本多模态指代表达理解研究综述. 中国图象图形学报, 28(5), 1308-1325.	2023
145	Referring expression comprehension using language adaptive inference	Su, W., Miao, P., Dou, H., Fu, Y., & Li, X. (2023, June). Referring expression comprehension using language adaptive inference. In Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (Vol. 37, No. 2, pp. 2357-2365).	2023

146	Two-Stage Asymmetric Similarity Preserving Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Huang, J., Kang, P., Han, N., Chen, Y., Fang, X., Gao, H., & Zhou, G. (2023). Two-Stage Asymmetric Similarity Preserving Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering</i> .	2023
147	Label-wise Deep Semantic-Alignment Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Li, L., & Sun, W. (2023, June). Label-wise Deep Semantic-Alignment Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval. In <i>Proceedings of the 2023 ACM International Conference on Multimedia Retrieval</i> (pp. 416-424).	2023
148	Improving visual grounding by encouraging consistent gradient-based explanations	Yang, Z., Kafle, K., Deroncourt, F., & Ordonez, V. (2023). Improving visual grounding by encouraging consistent gradient-based explanations. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition</i> (pp. 19165-19174).	2023
149	Asymmetric supervised fusion-oriented hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Yang, Z., Deng, X., Guo, L., & Long, J. (2023). Asymmetric supervised fusion-oriented hashing for cross-modal retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics</i> .	2023
150	Targeted adversarial attack against deep cross-modal hashing retrieval	Wang, T., Zhu, L., Zhang, Z., Zhang, H., & Han, J. (2023). Targeted adversarial attack against deep cross-modal hashing retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology</i> .	2023
151	LUNA: Language as Continuing Anchors for Referring Expression Comprehension	Liang, Y., Yang, Z., Tang, Y., Fan, J., Li, Z., Wang, J., ... & Huang, S. L. (2023, October). LUNA: Language as Continuing Anchors for Referring Expression Comprehension. In <i>Proceedings of the 31st ACM International Conference on Multimedia</i> (pp. 5174-5184).	2023
152	Multi-label hashing for dependency relations among multiple objectives	Peng, L., Qian, J., Xu, Z., Xin, Y., & Guo, L. (2023). Multi-label hashing for dependency relations among multiple objectives. <i>IEEE Transactions on Image Processing</i> , 32, 1759-1773.	2023
153	Contrastive grouping with transformer for referring image segmentation	Tang, J., Zheng, G., Shi, C., & Yang, S. (2023). Contrastive grouping with transformer for referring image segmentation. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition</i> (pp. 23570-23580).	2023
154	Cross-modal hashing with missing labels	Ni, H., Zhang, J., Kang, P., Fang, X., Sun, W., Xie, S., & Han, N. (2023). Cross-modal hashing with missing labels. <i>Neural Networks</i> , 165, 60-76.	2023
155	A fast weighted multi-view Bayesian learning scheme with deep learning for text-based image retrieval from unlabeled galleries	Oussama, A., Khaldi, B., & Kherfi, M. L. (2023). A fast weighted multi-view Bayesian learning scheme with deep learning for text-based image retrieval from unlabeled galleries. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 82(7), 10795-10812.	2023
156	An incremental approach to hierarchical feature selection by applying fuzzy rough set technique	She, Y., Wu, J., & He, X. (2023). An incremental approach to hierarchical feature selection by applying fuzzy rough set technique. <i>Artificial Intelligence Review</i> , 56(Suppl 2), 2571-2598.	2023

157	Vision-Aware Language Reasoning for Referring Image Segmentation	Xu, F., Luo, B., Zhang, C., Xu, L., Pu, M., & Li, B. (2023). Vision-Aware Language Reasoning for Referring Image Segmentation. <i>Neural Processing Letters</i> , 55(8), 11313-11331.	2023
158	Cross-modal attention guided visual reasoning for referring image segmentation	Zhang, W., Hu, M., Tan, Q., Zhou, Q., & Wang, R. (2023). Cross-modal attention guided visual reasoning for referring image segmentation. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 82(19), 28853-28872.	2023
159	Transformer-Based Discriminative and Strong Representation Deep Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Zhou, S., Han, Y., Chen, N., Huang, S., Igorevich, K. K., Luo, J., & Zhang, P. (2023). Transformer-Based Discriminative and Strong Representation Deep Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval. <i>IEEE Access</i> .	2023
160	Referring image segmentation using text supervision	Liu, F., Liu, Y., Kong, Y., Xu, K., Zhang, L., Yin, B., ... & Lau, R. (2023). Referring image segmentation using text supervision. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision</i> (pp. 22124-22134).	2023
161	Multiple Information Embedded Hashing for Large-Scale Cross-Modal Retrieval	Wang, Y., Zhan, Y. W., Chen, Z. D., Luo, X., & Xu, X. S. (2023). Multiple Information Embedded Hashing for Large-Scale Cross-Modal Retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology</i> .	2023
162	Nevis' 22: A Stream of 100 Tasks Sampled from 30 Years of Computer Vision Research	Bornschein, J., Galashov, A., Hemsley, R., Rannen-Triki, A., Chen, Y., Chaudhry, A., ... & Ranzato, M. A. (2023). Nevis' 22: A Stream of 100 Tasks Sampled from 30 Years of Computer Vision Research. <i>Journal of Machine Learning Research</i> , 24(308), 1-77.	2023
163	Unsupervised cross-modal hashing with modality-interaction	Tu, R. C., Jiang, J., Lin, Q., Cai, C., Tian, S., Wang, H., & Liu, W. (2023). Unsupervised cross-modal hashing with modality-interaction. <i>IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology</i> .	2023
164	Suspected Objects Matter: Rethinking Model's Prediction for One-stage Visual Grounding	Jiao, Y., Jie, Z., Chen, J., Ma, L., & Jiang, Y. G. (2023, October). Suspected Objects Matter: Rethinking Model's Prediction for One-stage Visual Grounding. In <i>Proceedings of the 31st ACM International Conference on Multimedia</i> (pp. 17-26).	2023
165	ONION: Online Semantic Autoencoder Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Zhang, D., Wu, X. J., & Chen, G. (2023). ONION: Online Semantic Autoencoder Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval. <i>ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology</i> , 14(2), 1-18.	2023
166	Label-consistent Kernel Transform Learning based Sparse Hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Maggu, J. (2023). Label-consistent Kernel Transform Learning based Sparse Hashing for cross-modal retrieval. Available at SSRN 4473322.	2023
167	Dual-graph hierarchical interaction network for referring image segmentation	Shi, Z., Wu, Q., Li, H., Meng, F., & Ngan, K. N. (2023). Dual-graph hierarchical interaction network for referring image segmentation. <i>Displays</i> , 80, 102575.	2023

168	Cross-modal transformer with language query for referring image segmentation	Zhang, W., Tan, Q., Li, P., Zhang, Q., & Wang, R. (2023). Cross-modal transformer with language query for referring image segmentation. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 536, 191-205.	2023
169	Self-paced Multi-grained Cross-modal Interaction Modeling for Referring Expression Comprehension	Miao, P., Su, W., Wang, G., Li, X., & Li, X. (2023). Self-paced Multi-grained Cross-modal Interaction Modeling for Referring Expression Comprehension. <i>IEEE Transactions on Image Processing</i> .	2023
170	Three-stage semisupervised cross-modal hashing with pairwise relations exploitation	Fan, W., Zhang, C., Li, H., Jia, X., & Wang, G. (2023). Three-stage semisupervised cross-modal hashing with pairwise relations exploitation. <i>IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems</i> .	2023
171	Non-Co-Occurrence Enhanced Multi-Label Cross-Modal Hashing Retrieval Based on Graph Convolutional Network	Li, M., Fan, J., & Lin, Z. (2023). Non-Co-Occurrence Enhanced Multi-Label Cross-Modal Hashing Retrieval Based on Graph Convolutional Network. <i>IEEE Access</i> , 11, 16310-16322.	2023
172	Adaptive marginalized semantic hashing for unpaired cross-modal retrieval	Luo, K., Zhang, C., Li, H., Jia, X., & Chen, C. (2023). Adaptive marginalized semantic hashing for unpaired cross-modal retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Multimedia</i> .	2023
173	Online Discriminative Cross-modal Hashing	Kang, X., Liu, X., Zhang, X., Nie, X., & Yin, Y. (2023). Online Discriminative Cross-modal Hashing. <i>IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology</i> .	2023
174	SemiMemes: A Semi-supervised Learning Approach for Multimodal Memes Analysis	Tung, P. T. H., Viet, N. T., Anh, N. T., & Hung, P. D. (2023, September). SemiMemes: A Semi-supervised Learning Approach for Multimodal Memes Analysis. In <i>International Conference on Computational Collective Intelligence</i> (pp. 565-577). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.	2023
175	Referring Image Segmentation With Fine-Grained Semantic Funneling Infusion	Yang, J., Zhang, L., & Lu, H. (2023). Referring Image Segmentation With Fine-Grained Semantic Funneling Infusion. <i>IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems</i> .	2023
176	Transvg++: End-to-end visual grounding with language conditioned vision transformer	Deng, J., Yang, Z., Liu, D., Chen, T., Zhou, W., Zhang, Y., ... & Ouyang, W. (2023). Transvg++: End-to-end visual grounding with language conditioned vision transformer. <i>IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence</i> .	2023
177	Deep Label Feature Fusion Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval	Ren, D., Xu, W., Wang, Z., & Sun, Q. (2022). Deep Label Feature Fusion Hashing for Cross-Modal Retrieval. <i>IEEE Access</i> , 10, 100276-100285.	2022
178	Modulating bottom-up and top-down visual processing via language-conditional filters	Kesen, I., Can, O. A., Erdem, E., Erdem, A., & Yüret, D. (2022). Modulating bottom-up and top-down visual processing via language-conditional filters. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition</i> (pp. 4610-4620).	2022
179	Discrete fusion adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Li, J., Yu, E., Ma, J., Chang, X., Zhang, H., & Sun, J. (2022). Discrete fusion adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval. <i>Knowledge-Based Systems</i> , 253, 109503.	2022

180	Unsupervised contrastive cross-modal hashing	Hu, P., Zhu, H., Lin, J., Peng, D., Zhao, Y. P., & Peng, X. (2022). Unsupervised contrastive cross-modal hashing. <i>IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence</i> , 45(3), 3877-3889.	2022
181	Deep cross-modal proxy hashing	Tu, R. C., Mao, X. L., Tu, R. X., Bian, B., Cai, C., Wang, H., ... & Huang, H. (2022). Deep cross-modal proxy hashing. <i>IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering</i> , 35(7), 6798-6810.	2022
182	Online robust specific and consistent hashing	Lin, H., Meng, M., & Wu, J. (2022, July). Online robust specific and consistent hashing. In <i>2022 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME)</i> (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2022
183	Multi-label modalit enhanced attention based self-super ised deep cross-modal hashing,.. doi: 10.1016/. knos s. 2021.107927 Version: Publisher's Version ...	Zou, X., Wu, S., Zhang, N., & Bakker, E. M. (2022). Multi-label modalit enhanced attention based self-super ised deep cross-modal hashing,.. doi: 10.1016/. knos s. 2021.107927 Version: Publisher's Version License: Licensed under rticle 25fa Cop right ct. Law (mendment Ta erne) Downloaded from: https://hdl.handle.net/1887/3483908 .	2022
184	A proposal-free one-stage framework for referring expression comprehension and generation via dense cross-attention	Sun, M., Suo, W., Wang, P., Zhang, Y., & Wu, Q. (2022). A proposal-free one-stage framework for referring expression comprehension and generation via dense cross-attention. <i>IEEE Transactions on Multimedia</i> .	2022
185	Deep discrete cross-modal hashing with multiple supervision	Yu, E., Ma, J., Sun, J., Chang, X., Zhang, H., & Hauptmann, A. G. (2022). Deep discrete cross-modal hashing with multiple supervision. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 486, 215-224.	2022
186	Referring Expression Comprehension	Wu, Q., Wang, P., Wang, X., He, X., & Zhu, W. (2022). Referring Expression Comprehension. In <i>Visual Question Answering: From Theory to Application</i> (pp. 219-230). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.	2022
187	Improving visual grounding with visual-linguistic verification and iterative reasoning	Yang, L., Xu, Y., Yuan, C., Liu, W., Li, B., & Hu, W. (2022). Improving visual grounding with visual-linguistic verification and iterative reasoning. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition</i> (pp. 9499-9508).	2022
188	An improved automatic image annotation approach using convolutional neural network-Slantlet transform	Adnan, M. M., Rahim, M. S. M., Khan, A. R., Saba, T., Fati, S. M., & Bahaj, S. A. (2022). An improved automatic image annotation approach using convolutional neural network-Slantlet transform. <i>IEEE Access</i> , 10, 7520-7532.	2022
189	MS2GAH: Multi-label semantic supervised graph attention hashing for robust cross-modal retrieval	Duan, Y., Chen, N., Zhang, P., Kumar, N., Chang, L., & Wen, W. (2022). MS2GAH: Multi-label semantic supervised graph attention hashing for robust cross-modal retrieval. <i>Pattern Recognition</i> , 128, 108676.	2022
190	Multi-view multi-label canonical correlation analysis for cross-modal matching and retrieval	Sanghavi, R., & Verma, Y. (2022). Multi-view multi-label canonical correlation analysis for cross-modal matching and retrieval. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition</i> (pp. 4701-4710).	2022

191	Learning from box annotations for referring image segmentation	Feng, G., Zhang, L., Hu, Z., & Lu, H. (2022). Learning from box annotations for referring image segmentation. <i>IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems</i> .	2022
192	Deconfounded visual grounding	Huang, J., Qin, Y., Qi, J., Sun, Q., & Zhang, H. (2022, June). Deconfounded visual grounding. In <i>Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence</i> (Vol. 36, No. 1, pp. 998-1006).	2022
193	A high-dimensional sparse hashing framework for cross-modal retrieval	Wang, Y., Chen, Z. D., Luo, X., & Xu, X. S. (2022). A high-dimensional sparse hashing framework for cross-modal retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology</i> , 32(12), 8822-8836.	2022
194	A model of semantic-based image retrieval using C-tree and neighbor graph	Nhi, N. T. U., & Le, T. M. (2022). A model of semantic-based image retrieval using C-tree and neighbor graph. <i>International Journal on Semantic Web and Information Systems (IJSWIS)</i> , 18(1), 1-23.	2022
195	Referring Segmentation via Encoder-Fused Cross-Modal Attention Network	Feng, G., Zhang, L., Sun, J., Hu, Z., & Lu, H. (2022). Referring Segmentation via Encoder-Fused Cross-Modal Attention Network. <i>IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence</i> .	2022
196	Multi-label enhancement based self-supervised deep cross-modal hashing	Zou, X., Wu, S., Bakker, E. M., & Wang, X. (2022). Multi-label enhancement based self-supervised deep cross-modal hashing. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 467, 138-162.	2022
197	Cross-modality synergy network for referring expression comprehension and segmentation	Li, Q., Zhang, Y., Sun, S., Wu, J., Zhao, X., & Tan, M. (2022). Cross-modality synergy network for referring expression comprehension and segmentation. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 467, 99-114.	2022
198	Information fusion based on deep learning	Li, J., Zhang, B., & Zhang, D. (2022). Information fusion based on deep learning. In <i>Information Fusion: Machine Learning Methods</i> (pp. 197-256). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.	2022
199	A novel deep translated attention hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Yu, H., Ma, R., Su, M., An, P., & Li, K. (2022). A novel deep translated attention hashing for cross-modal retrieval. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 81(18), 26443-26461.	2022
200	Two-stage Cross Modal Hashing Retrieval Based on Composite Quantization and Cauchy Distribution	Li, X., He, J., & Fan, B. (2022, May). Two-stage Cross Modal Hashing Retrieval Based on Composite Quantization and Cauchy Distribution. In <i>2022 4th International Conference on Communications, Information System and Computer Engineering (CISCE)</i> (pp. 51-56). IEEE.	2022
201	图像指代分割研究综述.	邱爽, 赵耀, & 韦世奎. (2022). 图像指代分割研究综述. <i>Journal of Signal Processing</i> , 38(6).	2022
202	Contrastive label correlation enhanced unified hashing encoder for cross-modal retrieval	Wu, H., Zhang, L., Chen, Q., Deng, Y., Siebert, J., Han, Y., ... & Cao, Z. (2022, October). Contrastive label correlation enhanced unified hashing encoder for cross-modal retrieval. In <i>Proceedings of the 31st ACM International Conference on Information & Knowledge Management</i> (pp. 2158-2168).	2022

203	A review of multi-modal learning from the text-guided visual processing viewpoint	Ullah, U., Lee, J. S., An, C. H., Lee, H., Park, S. Y., Baek, R. H., & Choi, H. C. (2022). A review of multi-modal learning from the text-guided visual processing viewpoint. <i>Sensors</i> , 22(18), 6816.	2022
204	Coupalalign: Coupling word-pixel with sentence-mask alignments for referring image segmentation	Zhang, Z., Zhu, Y., Liu, J., Liang, X., & Ke, W. (2022). Coupalalign: Coupling word-pixel with sentence-mask alignments for referring image segmentation. <i>Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems</i> , 35, 14729-14742.	2022
205	Progressive language-customized visual feature learning for one-stage visual grounding	Liao, Y., Zhang, A., Chen, Z., Hui, T., & Liu, S. (2022). Progressive language-customized visual feature learning for one-stage visual grounding. <i>IEEE Transactions on Image Processing</i> , 31, 4266-4277.	2022
206	Multi-label modality enhanced attention based self-supervised deep cross-modal hashing	Zou, X., Wu, S., Zhang, N., & Bakker, E. M. (2022). Multi-label modality enhanced attention based self-supervised deep cross-modal hashing. <i>Knowledge-Based Systems</i> , 239, 107927.	2022
207	Shifting more attention to visual backbone: Query-modulated refinement networks for end-to-end visual grounding	Ye, J., Tian, J., Yan, M., Yang, X., Wang, X., Zhang, J., ... & Lin, X. (2022). Shifting more attention to visual backbone: Query-modulated refinement networks for end-to-end visual grounding. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition</i> (pp. 15502-15512).	2022
208	Hierarchical GAN-Tree and Bi-Directional Capsules for multi-label image classification	Wang, B., Hu, X., Zhang, C., Li, P., & Philip, S. Y. (2022). Hierarchical GAN-Tree and Bi-Directional Capsules for multi-label image classification. <i>Knowledge-Based Systems</i> , 238, 107882.	2022
209	What kinds of errors do reference resolution models make and what can we learn from them?	Sánchez, J., Mazuecos, M., Maina, H., & Benotti, L. (2022, July). What kinds of errors do reference resolution models make and what can we learn from them?. In <i>Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: NAACL 2022</i> (pp. 1971-1986).	2022
210	Seqtr: A simple yet universal network for visual grounding	Zhu, C., Zhou, Y., Shen, Y., Luo, G., Pan, X., Lin, M., ... & Ji, R. (2022, October). Seqtr: A simple yet universal network for visual grounding. In <i>European Conference on Computer Vision</i> (pp. 598-615). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.	2022
211	Entity-enhanced adaptive reconstruction network for weakly supervised referring expression grounding	Liu, X., Li, L., Wang, S., Zha, Z. J., Li, Z., Tian, Q., & Huang, Q. (2022). Entity-enhanced adaptive reconstruction network for weakly supervised referring expression grounding. <i>IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence</i> , 45(3), 3003-3018.	2022
212	Yoro-lightweight end to end visual grounding	Ho, C. H., Appalaraju, S., Jasani, B., Manmatha, R., & Vasconcelos, N. (2022, October). Yoro-lightweight end to end visual grounding. In <i>European Conference on Computer Vision</i> (pp. 3-23). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.	2022

213	DAPCMH: Deep Adversarial Privacy-Preserving Cross-Modal Hashing	Zhu, L., Song, J., Yang, Z., Huang, W., Zhang, C., & Yu, W. (2022). DAP 2 CMH: Deep adversarial privacy-preserving cross-modal hashing. <i>Neural Processing Letters</i> , 54(4), 2549-2569.	2022
214	Restr: Convolution-free referring image segmentation using transformers	Kim, N., Kim, D., Lan, C., Zeng, W., & Kwak, S. (2022). Restr: Convolution-free referring image segmentation using transformers. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition</i> (pp. 18145-18154).	2022
215	Understanding synonymous referring expressions via contrastive features	Chen, Y. W., Tsai, Y. H., & Yang, M. H. (2022). Understanding synonymous referring expressions via contrastive features. <i>International Journal of Computer Vision</i> , 130(10), 2501-2516.	2022
216	Lpgn: Language-guided proposal generation network for referring expression comprehension	Wang, G., Yang, C., Feng, S., & Jiang, B. (2022, July). Lpgn: Language-guided proposal generation network for referring expression comprehension. In <i>2022 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME)</i> (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2022
217	Efficient modal-aware feature learning with application in multimodal hashing	Chu, H., Zeng, H., Lai, H., & Tang, Y. (2022). Efficient modal-aware feature learning with application in multimodal hashing. <i>Intelligent Data Analysis</i> , 26(2), 345-360.	2022
218	Weakly-supervised enhanced semantic-aware hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Zhang, C., Li, H., Gao, Y., & Chen, C. (2022). Weakly-supervised enhanced semantic-aware hashing for cross-modal retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering</i> , 35(6), 6475-6488.	2022
219	Rethinking and Improving Feature Pyramids for One-Stage Referring Expression Comprehension	Suo, W., Sun, M., Wang, P., Zhang, Y., & Wu, Q. (2022). Rethinking and Improving Feature Pyramids for One-Stage Referring Expression Comprehension. <i>IEEE Transactions on Image Processing</i> , 32, 854-864.	2022
220	Cross-modal recurrent semantic comprehension for referring image segmentation	Shang, C., Li, H., Qiu, H., Wu, Q., Meng, F., Zhao, T., & Ngan, K. N. (2022). Cross-modal recurrent semantic comprehension for referring image segmentation. <i>IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology</i> .	2022
221	Adaptive weight multi-channel center similar deep hashing	Liu, X., Cao, G., Lin, Q., & Cao, W. (2022). Adaptive weight multi-channel center similar deep hashing. <i>Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation</i> , 89, 103642.	2022
222	Structured attention network for referring image segmentation	Lin, L., Yan, P., Xu, X., Yang, S., Zeng, K., & Li, G. (2021). Structured attention network for referring image segmentation. <i>IEEE Transactions on Multimedia</i> , 24, 1922-1932.	2021
223	A semi-supervised learning approach based on adaptive weighted fusion for automatic image annotation	Li, Z., Lin, L., Zhang, C., Ma, H., Zhao, W., & Shi, Z. (2021). A semi-supervised learning approach based on adaptive weighted fusion for automatic image annotation. <i>ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications, and Applications (TOMM)</i> , 17(1), 1-23.	2021

224	Global and Local Feature Based Deep Cross-Modal Hashing	Yu, H., Ma, R., Su, M., An, P., & Li, K. (2021, December). Global and Local Feature Based Deep Cross-Modal Hashing. In International Forum on Digital TV and Wireless Multimedia Communications (pp. 253-265). Singapore: Springer Singapore.	2021
225	Few-shot visual grounding for natural human-robot interaction	Tziafas, G., & Kasaei, H. (2021, April). Few-shot visual grounding for natural human-robot interaction. In 2021 IEEE International Conference on Autonomous Robot Systems and Competitions (ICARSC) (pp. 50-55). IEEE.	2021
226	Multi-attention based semantic deep hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Zhu, L., Tian, G., Wang, B., Wang, W., Zhang, D., & Li, C. (2021). Multi-attention based semantic deep hashing for cross-modal retrieval. Applied Intelligence, 51, 5927-5939.	2021
227	Magnet: Multi-region attention-assisted grounding of natural language queries at phrase level	Shrestha, A., Pugdeethosapol, K., Fang, H., & Qiu, Q. (2021, January). Magnet: Multi-region attention-assisted grounding of natural language queries at phrase level. In 2020 25th International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR) (pp. 8275-8282). IEEE.	2021
228	Encoder fusion network with co-attention embedding for referring image segmentation	Feng, G., Hu, Z., Zhang, L., & Lu, H. (2021). Encoder fusion network with co-attention embedding for referring image segmentation. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (pp. 15506-15515).	2021
229	One-stage visual grounding via semantic-aware feature filter	Ye, J., Lin, X., He, L., Li, D., & Chen, Q. (2021, October). One-stage visual grounding via semantic-aware feature filter. In Proceedings of the 29th ACM International Conference on Multimedia (pp. 1702-1711).	2021
230	Know Yourself and Know Others: Efficient Common Representation Learning for Few-shot Cross-modal Retrieval	Wang, S., Lai, H., & Shi, Z. (2021, August). Know Yourself and Know Others: Efficient Common Representation Learning for Few-shot Cross-modal Retrieval. In Proceedings of the 2021 International Conference on Multimedia Retrieval (pp. 303-311).	2021
231	Two-stage visual cues enhancement network for referring image segmentation	Jiao, Y., Jie, Z., Luo, W., Chen, J., Jiang, Y. G., Wei, X., & Ma, L. (2021, October). Two-stage visual cues enhancement network for referring image segmentation. In Proceedings of the 29th ACM international conference on multimedia (pp. 1331-1340).	2021
232	Deep adversarial quantization network for cross-modal retrieval	Zhou, Y., Feng, Y., Zhou, M., Qiang, B., & Zhu, J. (2021, June). Deep adversarial quantization network for cross-modal retrieval. In ICASSP 2021-2021 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP) (pp. 4325-4329). IEEE.	2021
233	Transvg: End-to-end visual grounding with transformers	Deng, J., Yang, Z., Chen, T., Zhou, W., & Li, H. (2021). Transvg: End-to-end visual grounding with transformers. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (pp. 1769-1779).	2021

234	Deep Unified Cross-Modality Hashing by Pairwise Data Alignment.	Wang, Y., Xue, B., Cheng, Q., Chen, Y., & Zhang, L. (2021, August). Deep Unified Cross-Modality Hashing by Pairwise Data Alignment. In IJCAI (pp. 1129-1135).	2021
235	High-dimensional sparse cross-modal hashing with fine-grained similarity embedding	Wang, Y., Chen, Z. D., Luo, X., & Xu, X. S. (2021, April). High-dimensional sparse cross-modal hashing with fine-grained similarity embedding. In Proceedings of the Web Conference 2021 (pp. 2900-2909).	2021
236	Bidirectional relationship inferring network for referring image localization and segmentation	Feng, G., Hu, Z., Zhang, L., Sun, J., & Lu, H. (2021). Bidirectional relationship inferring network for referring image localization and segmentation. IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems, 34(5), 2246-2258.	2021
237	DAH: Discrete asymmetric hashing for efficient cross-media retrieval	Zhang, D., Wu, X. J., Xu, T., & Yin, H. F. (2021). DAH: Discrete asymmetric hashing for efficient cross-media retrieval. IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering, 35(2), 1365-1378.	2021
238	MOON: Multi-hash codes joint learning for cross-media retrieval	Zhang, D., Wu, X. J., Yin, H. F., & Kittler, J. (2021). MOON: Multi-hash codes joint learning for cross-media retrieval. Pattern recognition letters, 151, 19-25.	2021
239	Implementing Deep Neural Network Based Encoder-Decoder Framework for Image Captioning	Rahman, M. M., Uzzaman, A., & Sami, S. I. (2021, December). Implementing Deep Neural Network Based Encoder-Decoder Framework for Image Captioning. In 2021 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Information, Communication & Systems (SPICSCON) (pp. 26-31). IEEE.	2021
240	Cross-modal progressive comprehension for referring segmentation	Liu, S., Hui, T., Huang, S., Wei, Y., Li, B., & Li, G. (2021). Cross-modal progressive comprehension for referring segmentation. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 44(9), 4761-4775.	2021
241	Referring segmentation in images and videos with cross-modal self-attention network	Ye, L., Rochan, M., Liu, Z., Zhang, X., & Wang, Y. (2021). Referring segmentation in images and videos with cross-modal self-attention network. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 44(7), 3719-3732.	2021
242	Fast cross-modal hashing with global and local similarity embedding	Wang, Y., Chen, Z. D., Luo, X., Li, R., & Xu, X. S. (2021). Fast cross-modal hashing with global and local similarity embedding. IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics, 52(10), 10064-10077.	2021
243	Proposal-free one-stage referring expression via grid-word cross-attention	Suo, W., Sun, M., Wang, P., & Wu, Q. (2021). Proposal-free one-stage referring expression via grid-word cross-attention. arXiv preprint arXiv:2105.02061.	2021
244	Local graph convolutional networks for cross-modal hashing	Chen, Y., Wang, S., Lu, J., Chen, Z., Zhang, Z., & Huang, Z. (2021, October). Local graph convolutional networks for cross-modal hashing. In Proceedings of the 29th ACM international conference on multimedia (pp. 1921-1928).	2021
245	Unsupervised cross-modal similarity via latent structure discrete hashing factorization	Fang, Y., Li, B., Li, X., & Ren, Y. (2021). Unsupervised cross-modal similarity via latent structure discrete hashing factorization. Knowledge-Based Systems, 218, 106857.	2021

246	Survey on deep multi-modal data analytics: Collaboration, rivalry, and fusion	Wang, Y. (2021). Survey on deep multi-modal data analytics: Collaboration, rivalry, and fusion. <i>ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications, and Applications (TOMM)</i> , 17(1s), 1-25.	2021
247	Task-adaptive asymmetric deep cross-modal hashing	Li, F., Wang, T., Zhu, L., Zhang, Z., & Wang, X. (2021). Task-adaptive asymmetric deep cross-modal hashing. <i>Knowledge-Based Systems</i> , 219, 106851.	2021
248	Goal-driven text descriptions for images	Luo, R. (2021). Goal-driven text descriptions for images. <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.12575</i> .	2021
249	Multi-label semantics preserving based deep cross-modal hashing	Zou, X., Wang, X., Bakker, E. M., & Wu, S. (2021). Multi-label semantics preserving based deep cross-modal hashing. <i>Signal Processing: Image Communication</i> , 93, 116131.	2021
250	Mask cross-modal hashing networks	Lin, Q., Cao, W., He, Z., & He, Z. (2020). Mask cross-modal hashing networks. <i>IEEE Transactions on Multimedia</i> , 23, 550-558.	2020
251	Dual convolutional LSTM network for referring image segmentation	Ye, L., Liu, Z., & Wang, Y. (2020). Dual convolutional LSTM network for referring image segmentation. <i>IEEE Transactions on Multimedia</i> , 22(12), 3224-3235.	2020
252	Self-constraining and attention-based hashing network for bit-scalable cross-modal retrieval	Wang, X., Zou, X., Bakker, E. M., & Wu, S. (2020). Self-constraining and attention-based hashing network for bit-scalable cross-modal retrieval. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 400, 255-271.	2020
253	A SEMANTIC-BASED IMAGE RETRIEVAL SYSTEM USING A HYBRID METHOD K-MEANS AND K-NEAREST-NEIGHBOR	Nhi, N. T. U., Thi, N. T. U., & Han, P. T. A. (2020, July). A SEMANTIC-BASED IMAGE RETRIEVAL SYSTEM USING A HYBRID METHOD K-MEANS AND K-NEAREST-NEIGHBOR. In <i>Annales Universitatis Scientiarum Budapestinensis de Rolando Eotvos Nominatae. Sectio Computatorica (Vol. 51)</i> .	2020
254	Referring expression comprehension: A survey of methods and datasets	Qiao, Y., Deng, C., & Wu, Q. (2020). Referring expression comprehension: A survey of methods and datasets. <i>IEEE Transactions on Multimedia</i> , 23, 4426-4440.	2020
255	An innovative multi-label learning based algorithm for city data computing	Mei, M., Zhong, Y., He, F., & Xu, C. (2020). An innovative multi-label learning based algorithm for city data computing. <i>Geoinformatica</i> , 24, 221-245.	2020
256	Deep semantic similarity adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Qiang, H., Wan, Y., Xiang, L., & Meng, X. (2020). Deep semantic similarity adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 400, 24-33.	2020
257	VSE-fs: Fast Full-Sample Visual Semantic Embedding	Zhai, S., Guo, G., Yuan, F., Liu, Y., & Wang, X. (2020). VSE-fs: Fast Full-Sample Visual Semantic Embedding. <i>IEEE Intelligent Systems</i> , 36(4), 3-12.	2020
258	Semantic deep cross-modal hashing	Lin, Q., Cao, W., He, Z., & He, Z. (2020). Semantic deep cross-modal hashing. <i>Neurocomputing</i> , 396, 113-122.	2020

259	Referring image segmentation via cross-modal progressive comprehension	Huang, S., Hui, T., Liu, S., Li, G., Wei, Y., Han, J., ... & Li, B. (2020). Referring image segmentation via cross-modal progressive comprehension. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (pp. 10488-10497).	2020
260	Cross-modal omni interaction modeling for phrase grounding	Yu, T., Hui, T., Yu, Z., Liao, Y., Yu, S., Zhang, F., & Liu, S. (2020, October). Cross-modal omni interaction modeling for phrase grounding. In Proceedings of the 28th ACM international conference on multimedia (pp. 1725-1734).	2020
261	Ppgn: Phrase-guided proposal generation network for referring expression comprehension	Yang, C., Wang, G., Li, D., Shen, H., Feng, S., & Jiang, B. (2020). Ppgn: Phrase-guided proposal generation network for referring expression comprehension. arXiv preprint arXiv:2012.10890.	2020
262	Asymmetric supervised consistent and specific hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Meng, M., Wang, H., Yu, J., Chen, H., & Wu, J. (2020). Asymmetric supervised consistent and specific hashing for cross-modal retrieval. IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, 30, 986-1000.	2020
263	A self-balanced clustering tree for semantic-based image retrieval	Nhi, N. T. U. (2020). A self-balanced clustering tree for semantic-based image retrieval. Journal of Computer Science and Cybernetics, 36(1), 49-67.	2020
264	A review of hashing methods for multimodal retrieval	Cao, W., Feng, W., Lin, Q., Cao, G., & He, Z. (2020). A review of hashing methods for multimodal retrieval. IEEE Access, 8, 15377-15391.	2020
265	Harmonization shared autoencoder gaussian process latent variable model with relaxed hamming distance	Li, J., Zhang, B., Lu, G., Xu, Y., Wu, F., & Zhang, D. (2020). Harmonization shared autoencoder gaussian process latent variable model with relaxed hamming distance. IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems, 32(11), 5093-5107.	2020
266	Transferrable referring expression grounding with concept transfer and context inheritance	Liu, X., Li, L., Wang, S., Zha, Z. J., Meng, D., & Huang, Q. (2020, October). Transferrable referring expression grounding with concept transfer and context inheritance. In Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Multimedia (pp. 3938-3946).	2020
267	Label embedding online hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Wang, Y., Luo, X., & Xu, X. S. (2020, October). Label embedding online hashing for cross-modal retrieval. In Proceedings of the 28th ACM international conference on multimedia (pp. 871-879).	2020
268	Deep cross-modal hashing via margin-dynamic-softmax loss	Tu, R. C., Mao, X. L., Tu, R., Bian, B., Wei, W., & Huang, H. (2020). Deep cross-modal hashing via margin-dynamic-softmax loss. arXiv preprint arXiv:2011.03451.	2020
269	Multi-task consistency-preserving adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Xie, D., Deng, C., Li, C., Liu, X., & Tao, D. (2020). Multi-task consistency-preserving adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval. IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, 29, 3626-3637.	2020

270	Multi-level correlation adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Ma, X., Zhang, T., & Xu, C. (2020). Multi-level correlation adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Multimedia</i> , 22(12), 3101-3114.	2020
271	Enabling secure cross-modal retrieval over encrypted heterogeneous IoT databases with collective matrix factorization	Guo, C., Jia, J., Jie, Y., Liu, C. Z., & Choo, K. K. R. (2020). Enabling secure cross-modal retrieval over encrypted heterogeneous IoT databases with collective matrix factorization. <i>IEEE Internet of Things Journal</i> , 7(4), 3104-3113.	2020
272	Deep cross-modal hashing with hashing functions and unified hash codes jointly learning	Tu, R. C., Mao, X. L., Ma, B., Hu, Y., Yan, T., Wei, W., & Huang, H. (2020). Deep cross-modal hashing with hashing functions and unified hash codes jointly learning. <i>IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering</i> , 34(2), 560-572.	2020
273	Joint versus independent multiview hashing for cross-view retrieval	Hu, P., Peng, X., Zhu, H., Lin, J., Zhen, L., & Peng, D. (2020). Joint versus independent multiview hashing for cross-view retrieval. <i>IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics</i> , 51(10), 4982-4993.	2020
274	Bi-directional relationship inferring network for referring image segmentation	Hu, Z., Feng, G., Sun, J., Zhang, L., & Lu, H. (2020). Bi-directional relationship inferring network for referring image segmentation. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition</i> (pp. 4424-4433).	2020
275	Cross-modal self-attention network for referring image segmentation	Ye, L., Rochan, M., Liu, Z., & Wang, Y. (2019). Cross-modal self-attention network for referring image segmentation. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition</i> (pp. 10502-10511).	2019
276	Dual asymmetric deep hashing learning	Li, J., Zhang, B., Lu, G., & Zhang, D. (2019). Dual asymmetric deep hashing learning. <i>IEEE Access</i> , 7, 113372-113384.	2019
277	Growbit: Incremental hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Mandal, D., Annadani, Y., & Biswas, S. (2019). Growbit: Incremental hashing for cross-modal retrieval. In <i>Computer Vision-ACCV 2018: 14th Asian Conference on Computer Vision, Perth, Australia, December 2-6, 2018, Revised Selected Papers, Part IV 14</i> (pp. 305-321). Springer International Publishing.	2019
278	Comprehensive Semi-Supervised Multi-Modal Learning.	Yang, Y., Wang, K. T., Zhan, D. C., Xiong, H., & Jiang, Y. (2019, August). Comprehensive Semi-Supervised Multi-Modal Learning. In <i>IJCAI</i> (pp. 4092-4098).	2019
279	Hierarchical feature extraction based on discriminant analysis	Liu, X., & Zhao, H. (2019). Hierarchical feature extraction based on discriminant analysis. <i>Applied Intelligence</i> , 49, 2780-2792.	2019
280	Zero-shot grounding of objects from natural language queries	Sadhu, A., Chen, K., & Nevatia, R. (2019). Zero-shot grounding of objects from natural language queries. In <i>Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision</i> (pp. 4694-4703).	2019

281	A fast and accurate one-stage approach to visual grounding	Yang, Z., Gong, B., Wang, L., Huang, W., Yu, D., & Luo, J. (2019). A fast and accurate one-stage approach to visual grounding. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision (pp. 4683-4693).	2019
282	Diverse image annotation with missing labels	Verma, Y. (2019). Diverse image annotation with missing labels. Pattern Recognition, 93, 470-484.	2019
283	Adaptive hypergraph embedded semi-supervised multi-label image annotation	Tang, C., Liu, X., Wang, P., Zhang, C., Li, M., & Wang, L. (2019). Adaptive hypergraph embedded semi-supervised multi-label image annotation. IEEE Transactions on Multimedia, 21(11), 2837-2849.	2019
284	Relaxed asymmetric deep hashing learning: Point-to-angle matching	Li, J., Zhang, B., Lu, G., You, J., Xu, Y., Wu, F., & Zhang, D. (2019). Relaxed asymmetric deep hashing learning: Point-to-angle matching. IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems, 31(11), 4791-4805.	2019
285	Fuzzy rough set based feature selection for large-scale hierarchical classification	Zhao, H., Wang, P., Hu, Q., & Zhu, P. (2019). Fuzzy rough set based feature selection for large-scale hierarchical classification. IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems, 27(10), 1891-1903.	2019
286	Semi-supervised multi-modal multi-instance multi-label deep network with optimal transport	Yang, Y., Fu, Z. Y., Zhan, D. C., Liu, Z. B., & Jiang, Y. (2019). Semi-supervised multi-modal multi-instance multi-label deep network with optimal transport. IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering, 33(2), 696-709.	2019
287	Chained ensemble classifier for image annotation	Marin-Castro, H. M., Hernandez-Resendiz, J. D., Escalante-Balderas, H. J., Pellegrin, L., & Tello-Leal, E. (2019). Chained ensemble classifier for image annotation. Multimedia Tools and Applications, 78, 26263-26285.	2019
288	Improved deep hashing with soft pairwise similarity for multi-label image retrieval	Zhang, Z., Zou, Q., Lin, Y., Chen, L., & Wang, S. (2019). Improved deep hashing with soft pairwise similarity for multi-label image retrieval. IEEE Transactions on Multimedia, 22(2), 540-553.	2019
289	Тимофеева АЕ	Кудін, О. В., Кривохата, А. Г., & Ліснюк, А. О. (2019). Тимофеева АЕ. ВЧЕНІ ЗАПИСКИ, 22019214.	2019
290	Adaptive reconstruction network for weakly supervised referring expression grounding	Liu, X., Li, L., Wang, S., Zha, Z. J., Meng, D., & Huang, Q. (2019). Adaptive reconstruction network for weakly supervised referring expression grounding. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (pp. 2611-2620).	2019
291	Hierarchical feature selection with subtree based graph regularization	Tuo, Q., Zhao, H., & Hu, Q. (2019). Hierarchical feature selection with subtree based graph regularization. Knowledge-Based Systems, 163, 996-1008.	2019
292	Discrete latent factor model for cross-modal hashing	Jiang, Q. Y., & Li, W. J. (2019). Discrete latent factor model for cross-modal hashing. IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, 28(7), 3490-3501.	2019

293	Generating easy-to-understand referring expressions for target identifications	Tanaka, M., Itamochi, T., Narioka, K., Sato, I., Ushiku, Y., & Harada, T. (2019). Generating easy-to-understand referring expressions for target identifications. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (pp. 5794-5803).	2019
294	R2 Índices de validación de clustering para la sintonización de técnicas de segmentación automática utilizando imágenes de escenas naturales	Reséndiz, J. D. H., Marin, H. M., & Tello, E. (2019). R2 Índices de validación de clustering para la sintonización de técnicas de segmentación automática utilizando imágenes de escenas naturales. IEEE Latin America Transactions, 17(8), 1229-1236.	2019
295	Knowledge-guided pairwise reconstruction network for weakly supervised referring expression grounding	Liu, X., Li, L., Wang, S., Zha, Z. J., Su, L., & Huang, Q. (2019, October). Knowledge-guided pairwise reconstruction network for weakly supervised referring expression grounding. In Proceedings of the 27th ACM International Conference on Multimedia (pp. 539-547).	2019
296	Modal-aware Features for Multimodal Hashing	Zeng, H., Lai, H., Chu, H., Tang, Y., & Yin, J. (2019). Modal-aware Features for Multimodal Hashing. arXiv preprint arXiv:1911.08479.	2019
297	Large scale datasets for image and video captioning in italian	Antonio, S., Croce, D., & Basili, R. (2019). Large scale datasets for image and video captioning in italian. IJCoL. Italian Journal of Computational Linguistics, 5(5-2), 49-60.	2019
298	A comparative study of clustering validation indices and maximum entropy for sintonization of automatic segmentation techniques	RESÉNDIZ, J. D. H., CASTRO, H. M. M., & LEAL, E. T. (2019). A comparative study of clustering validation indices and maximum entropy for sintonization of automatic segmentation techniques. IEEE Latin America Transactions, 17(08), 1229-1236.	2019
299	Deep robust unsupervised multi-modal network	Yang, Y., Wu, Y. F., Zhan, D. C., Liu, Z. B., & Jiang, Y. (2019, July). Deep robust unsupervised multi-modal network. In Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (Vol. 33, No. 01, pp. 5652-5659).	2019
300	Cross-modal hashing with semantic deep embedding	Yan, C., Bai, X., Wang, S., Zhou, J., & Hancock, E. R. (2019). Cross-modal hashing with semantic deep embedding. Neurocomputing, 337, 58-66.	2019
301	Independent feature and label components for multi-label classification	Zhong, Y., Xu, C., Du, B., & Zhang, L. (2018, November). Independent feature and label components for multi-label classification. In 2018 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM) (pp. 827-836). IEEE.	2018
302	Supervised deep hashing for hierarchical labeled data	Wang, D., Huang, H., Lu, C., Feng, B. S., Wen, G., Nie, L., & Mao, X. L. (2018, April). Supervised deep hashing for hierarchical labeled data. In Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (Vol. 32, No. 1).	2018
303	Dmtmv: a unified learning framework for deep multi-task multi-view learning	Wu, Y. F., Zhan, D. C., & Jiang, Y. (2018, November). Dmtmv: a unified learning framework for deep multi-task multi-view learning. In 2018 IEEE international conference on big knowledge (ICBK) (pp. 49-56). IEEE.	2018

304	Attention-aware deep adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Zhang, X., Lai, H., & Feng, J. (2018). Attention-aware deep adversarial hashing for cross-modal retrieval. In Proceedings of the European conference on computer vision (ECCV) (pp. 591-606).	2018
305	Real-time referring expression comprehension by single-stage grounding network	Chen, X., Ma, L., Chen, J., Jie, Z., Liu, W., & Luo, J. (2018). Real-time referring expression comprehension by single-stage grounding network. arXiv preprint arXiv:1812.03426.	2018
306	Weakly supervised phrase localization with multi-scale anchored transformer network	Zhao, F., Li, J., Zhao, J., & Feng, J. (2018). Weakly supervised phrase localization with multi-scale anchored transformer network. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (pp. 5696-5705).	2018
307	CPAR: Cloud-Assisted Privacy-preserving Image Annotation with Randomized KD-Forest	Tian, Y., Hou, Y., & Yuan, J. (2018). CPAR: Cloud-Assisted Privacy-preserving Image Annotation with Randomized KD-Forest. arXiv preprint arXiv:1811.04195.	2018
308	Referring image segmentation via recurrent refinement networks	Li, R., Li, K., Kuo, Y. C., Shu, M., Qi, X., Shen, X., & Jia, J. (2018). Referring image segmentation via recurrent refinement networks. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (pp. 5745-5753).	2018
309	Complex object classification: A multi-modal multi-instance multi-label deep network with optimal transport	Yang, Y., Wu, Y. F., Zhan, D. C., Liu, Z. B., & Jiang, Y. (2018, July). Complex object classification: A multi-modal multi-instance multi-label deep network with optimal transport. In Proceedings of the 24th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining (pp. 2594-2603).	2018
310	Global and local semantics-preserving based deep hashing for cross-modal retrieval	Ma, L., Li, H., Meng, F., Wu, Q., & Ngan, K. N. (2018). Global and local semantics-preserving based deep hashing for cross-modal retrieval. Neurocomputing, 312, 49-62.	2018
311	Region-based image retrieval using relevance feature weights	Bchir, O., Ismail, M. M. B., & Aljam, H. (2018). Region-based image retrieval using relevance feature weights. International journal of fuzzy logic and intelligent systems, 18(1), 65-77.	2018
312	Image annotation: Then and now	Bhagat, P. K., & Choudhary, P. (2018). Image annotation: Then and now. Image and Vision Computing, 80, 1-23.	2018
313	Guesswhat?! visual object discovery through multi-modal dialogue	De Vries, H., Strub, F., Chandar, S., Pietquin, O., Larochelle, H., & Courville, A. (2017). Guesswhat?! visual object discovery through multi-modal dialogue. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (pp. 5503-5512).	2017
314	Pattern graph-based image retrieval system combining semantic and visual features	Allani, O., Zghal, H. B., Mellouli, N., & Akdag, H. (2017). Pattern graph-based image retrieval system combining semantic and visual features. Multimedia Tools and Applications, 76, 20287-20316.	2017
315	Robust web image annotation via exploring multi-facet and structural knowledge	Hu, M., Yang, Y., Shen, F., Zhang, L., Shen, H. T., & Li, X. (2017). Robust web image annotation via exploring multi-facet and structural knowledge. IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, 26(10), 4871-4884.	2017

316	Learning to disambiguate by asking discriminative questions	Li, Y., Huang, C., Tang, X., & Change Loy, C. (2017). Learning to disambiguate by asking discriminative questions. In Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (pp. 3419-3428).	2017
317	Deep cross-modal hashing	Jiang, Q. Y., & Li, W. J. (2017). Deep cross-modal hashing. In Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (pp. 3232-3240).	2017
318	Automatic Visual Theme Discovery from Joint Image and Text Corpora	Sun, K., Hou, X., Zhang, Q., & Qiu, G. (2017, March). Automatic Visual Theme Discovery from Joint Image and Text Corpora. In 2017 2nd International Conference on Multimedia and Image Processing (ICMIP) (pp. 220-224). IEEE.	2017
319	Comprehension-guided referring expressions	Luo, R., & Shakhnarovich, G. (2017). Comprehension-guided referring expressions. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (pp. 7102-7111).	2017
320	Hashgan: Attention-aware deep adversarial hashing for cross modal retrieval	Zhang, X., Zhou, S., Feng, J., Lai, H., Li, B., Pan, Y., ... & Yan, S. (2017). Hashgan: Attention-aware deep adversarial hashing for cross modal retrieval. arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.09347.	2017
321	CAPIA: Cloud assisted privacy-preserving image annotation	Tian, Y., Hou, Y., & Yuan, J. (2017, October). CAPIA: Cloud assisted privacy-preserving image annotation. In 2017 IEEE Conference on Communications and Network Security (CNS) (pp. 1-9). IEEE.	2017
322	Lip6@ clef2017: Multi-modal spatial role labeling using word embeddings working notes	Zablocki, É., Bordes, P., Soulier, L., Piwowarski, B., & Gallinari, P. (2017). Lip6@ clef2017: Multi-modal spatial role labeling using word embeddings working notes. In CLEF 2017.	2017
323	Multi label learning and multi feature extraction for automatic image annotation	Renuse, S., & Bogiri, N. (2017, August). Multi label learning and multi feature extraction for automatic image annotation. In 2017 International Conference on Computing, Communication, Control and Automation (ICCUBEA) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2017
324	Visual and semantic context modeling for scene-centric image annotation	Zand, M., Doraisamy, S., Abdul Halin, A., & Mustafa, M. R. (2017). Visual and semantic context modeling for scene-centric image annotation. Multimedia Tools and Applications, 76, 8547-8571.	2017
325	Hierarchical multi-label classification using fully associative ensemble learning	Zhang, L., Shah, S. K., & Kakadiaris, I. A. (2017). Hierarchical multi-label classification using fully associative ensemble learning. Pattern Recognition, 70, 89-103.	2017
326	Spatial language understanding with multimodal graphs using declarative learning based programming	Kordjamshidi, P., Rahgooy, T., & Manzoor, U. (2017, September). Spatial language understanding with multimodal graphs using declarative learning based programming. In Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Structured Prediction for Natural Language Processing (pp. 33-43).	2017
327	An Attention-based Regression Model for Grounding Textual Phrases in Images.	Endo, K., Aono, M., Nichols, E., & Funakoshi, K. (2017, August). An Attention-based Regression Model for Grounding Textual Phrases in Images. In IJCAI (pp. 3995-4001).	2017

328	The Semantics of Images and Associated Text	Barnard, K. (2016). The Semantics of Images and Associated Text. In Computational Methods for Integrating Vision and Language (pp. 27-33). Cham: Springer International Publishing.	2016
329	Multi-label dictionary learning for image annotation	Jing, X. Y., Wu, F., Li, Z., Hu, R., & Zhang, D. (2016). Multi-label dictionary learning for image annotation. IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, 25(6), 2712-2725.	2016
330	Natural language object retrieval	Hu, R., Xu, H., Rohrbach, M., Feng, J., Saenko, K., & Darrell, T. (2016). Natural language object retrieval. In Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (pp. 4555-4564).	2016
331	Integrating global and local visual features with semantic hierarchies for two-level image annotation	Qian, Z., Zhong, P., & Chen, J. (2016). Integrating global and local visual features with semantic hierarchies for two-level image annotation. Neurocomputing, 171, 1167-1174.	2016
332	Facial expression recognition based-on saliency guided support vector machine	Dou, Y., Zhou, M., Wang, J., & Qiang, J. (2016, December). Facial expression recognition based-on saliency guided support vector machine. In 2016 9th International Symposium on Computational Intelligence and Design (ISCID) (Vol. 2, pp. 389-393). IEEE.	2016
333	Multimodal compact bilinear pooling for visual question answering and visual grounding	Fukui, A., Park, D. H., Yang, D., Rohrbach, A., Darrell, T., & Rohrbach, M. (2016). Multimodal compact bilinear pooling for visual question answering and visual grounding. arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.01847.	2016
334	On the coupled use of signal and semantic concepts to bridge the semantic and user intention gaps for visual content retrieval	Jarrar, R., & Belkhatir, M. (2016). On the coupled use of signal and semantic concepts to bridge the semantic and user intention gaps for visual content retrieval. International journal of multimedia information retrieval, 5, 165-172.	2016
335	A generic framework for ontology-based information retrieval and image retrieval in web data	Vijayarajan, V., Dinakaran, M., Tejaswin, P., & Lohani, M. (2016). A generic framework for ontology-based information retrieval and image retrieval in web data. Human-centric Computing and Information Sciences, 6, 1-30.	2016
336	Generation and comprehension of unambiguous object descriptions	Mao, J., Huang, J., Toshev, A., Camburu, O., Yuille, A. L., & Murphy, K. (2016). Generation and comprehension of unambiguous object descriptions. In Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (pp. 11-20).	2016
337	A benchmark data set to evaluate the illumination robustness of image processing algorithms for object segmentation and classification	Khan, A. U. M., Mikut, R., & Reischl, M. (2015). A benchmark data set to evaluate the illumination robustness of image processing algorithms for object segmentation and classification. Plos one, 10(7), e0131098.	2015
338	Learning descriptive visual representation for image classification and annotation	Lu, Z., & Wang, L. (2015). Learning descriptive visual representation for image classification and annotation. Pattern Recognition, 48(2), 498-508.	2015

339	An exploratory study to identify relevant cues for the deletion of faces for multimedia retrieval	Ritter, M., & Bahr, G. S. (2015, June). An exploratory study to identify relevant cues for the deletion of faces for multimedia retrieval. In 2015 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia & Expo Workshops (ICMEW) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2015
340	Decision making for content management systems: Criteria identification and categorisation	Angelopoulos, S., & Kitsios, F. (2015, January). Decision making for content management systems: Criteria identification and categorisation. In 2015 48th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (pp. 1233-1239). IEEE.	2015
341	Automatic image annotation for description of urban and outdoor scenes	Cruz-Perez, C., Starostenko, O., Alarcon-Aquino, V., & Rodriguez-Asomoza, J. (2015). Automatic image annotation for description of urban and outdoor scenes. In Innovations and advances in computing, informatics, systems sciences, networking and engineering (pp. 139-147). Springer International Publishing.	2015
342	Understanding the time characteristic of user behavior on online forums	Chen, G., Wang, N., Zhang, F., & Jiang, H. (2015, October). Understanding the time characteristic of user behavior on online forums. In 2015 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data) (pp. 2300-2306). IEEE.	2015
343	Automatic image annotation using semi-supervised generative modeling	Amiri, S. H., & Jamzad, M. (2015). Automatic image annotation using semi-supervised generative modeling. Pattern Recognition, 48(1), 174-188.	2015
344	Image with a message: Towards detecting non-literal image usages by visual linking	Weiland, L., Dietz, L., & Ponzetto, S. P. (2015, September). Image with a message: Towards detecting non-literal image usages by visual linking. In Proceedings of the Fourth Workshop on Vision and Language (pp. 40-47).	2015
345	A New Framework to Bridge Semantic Gap for Semantics Based Image Retrieval	Rizvi, E. S. S. H. (2014). A New Framework to Bridge Semantic Gap for Semantics Based Image Retrieval. Iqra University Islamabad Campus.	2014
346	Probabilistic component identification	Sajani, H. S., & Lopes, C. V. (2014, February). Probabilistic component identification. In Proceedings of the 7th India Software Engineering Conference (pp. 1-10).	2014
347	Semantic sparse recoding of visual content for image applications	Lu, Z., Han, P., Wang, L., & Wen, J. R. (2014). Semantic sparse recoding of visual content for image applications. IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, 24(1), 176-188.	2014
348	Architecture-parametric timing analysis	Reineke, J., & Doerfert, J. (2014, April). Architecture-parametric timing analysis. In 2014 IEEE 19th Real-Time and Embedded Technology and Applications Symposium (RTAS) (pp. 189-200). IEEE.	2014
349	Automatic image annotation using an evolutionary algorithm (IAGA)	Bahrami, S., & Abadeh, M. S. (2014, September). Automatic image annotation using an evolutionary algorithm (IAGA). In 7th International Symposium on Telecommunications (IST'2014) (pp. 320-325). IEEE.	2014

350	A Novel Topology in Modular ANN Approach for Multi-Modal Concept Identification and Image Retrieval	Hussain, S. S., Hashmani, M., Moinuddin, M., & Raza, K. (2014). A Novel Topology in Modular ANN Approach for Multi-Modal Concept Identification and Image Retrieval. <i>Intelligent Automation & Soft Computing</i> , 20(1), 131-141.	2014
351	PIR: a domain specific language for multimedia information retrieval	Huang, X., Zhao, T., & Cao, Y. (2014). PIR: a domain specific language for multimedia information retrieval. <i>International Journal of Multimedia Data Engineering and Management (IJMDEM)</i> , 5(3), 1-27.	2014
352	Labeling complicated objects: Multi-view multi-instance multi-label learning	Nguyen, C. T., Wang, X., Liu, J., & Zhou, Z. H. (2014, June). Labeling complicated objects: Multi-view multi-instance multi-label learning. In <i>Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (Vol. 28, No. 1)</i> .	2014
353	Fully Associative Ensemble Learning for Hierarchical Multi-Label Classification.	Zhang, L., Shah, S. K., & Kakadiaris, I. A. (2014, September). Fully Associative Ensemble Learning for Hierarchical Multi-Label Classification. In <i>BMVC</i> .	2014
354	Locating people in video from semantic descriptions: A new database and approach	Halstead, M., Denman, S., Sridharan, S., & Fookes, C. (2014, August). Locating people in video from semantic descriptions: A new database and approach. In <i>2014 22nd International Conference on Pattern Recognition (pp. 4501-4506)</i> . IEEE.	2014
355	Text-aided object segmentation and classification in images	Tegen, A. (2014). Text-aided object segmentation and classification in images. <i>Master's Theses in Mathematical Sciences</i> .	2014
356	Image segmentation and labeling using free-form semantic annotation	Tegen, A., Weegar, R., Hammarlund, L., Oskarsson, M., Jjang, F., Medved, D., ... & Åström, K. (2014, August). Image segmentation and labeling using free-form semantic annotation. In <i>2014 22nd International Conference on Pattern Recognition (pp. 2281-2286)</i> . IEEE.	2014
357	On Forensics Investigation Models	Dieko, E., Alese Boniface, K., Thompson Aderonke, F., & Otasowie, I. (2014). On Forensics Investigation Models. In <i>Proceedings of the World Congress on Engineering and Computer Science (Vol. 1)</i> .	2014
358	Reconsidering mutual information based feature selection: A statistical significance view	Vinh, N., Chan, J., & Bailey, J. (2014, June). Reconsidering mutual information based feature selection: A statistical significance view. In <i>Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (Vol. 28, No. 1)</i> .	2014
359	Referitgame: Referring to objects in photographs of natural scenes	Kazemzadeh, S., Ordonez, V., Matten, M., & Berg, T. (2014, October). Referitgame: Referring to objects in photographs of natural scenes. In <i>Proceedings of the 2014 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing (EMNLP) (pp. 787-798)</i> .	2014
360	Assessing the relationships among tag syntax, semantics, and perceived usefulness	Jørgensen, C., Stvilia, B., & Wu, S. (2014). Assessing the relationships among tag syntax, semantics, and perceived usefulness. <i>Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology</i> , 65(4), 836-849.	2014

361	Visual entity linking: A preliminary study	Weegar, R., Hammarlund, L., Tegen, A., Oskarsson, M., Åström, K., & Nugues, P. (2014, June). Visual entity linking: A preliminary study. In Workshops at the Twenty-Eighth AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence.	2014
362	Multi-instance active learning with online labeling for object recognition	Salmani, K., & Sridharan, M. (2014, May). Multi-instance active learning with online labeling for object recognition. In The Twenty-Seventh International Flairs Conference.	2014
363	Towards modelling visual ambiguity for visual object detection	Chatzilari, E., Nikolopoulos, S., Kompatsiaris, Y., & Kittler, J. (2014, September). Towards modelling visual ambiguity for visual object detection. In Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Knowledge Technologies and Data-driven Business (pp. 1-7).	2014
364	Using tagged images of low visual ambiguity to boost the learning efficiency of object detectors	Chatzilari, E. (2013, October). Using tagged images of low visual ambiguity to boost the learning efficiency of object detectors. In Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Multimedia (pp. 1027-1030).	2013
365	Label localization by appearance guided graph inferring	Yu, L., Liu, J., & Xu, C. (2013, September). Label localization by appearance guided graph inferring. In 2013 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (pp. 3456-3460). IEEE.	2013
366	Local image tagging via graph regularized joint group sparsity	Yang, Y., Huang, Z., Yang, Y., Liu, J., Shen, H. T., & Luo, J. (2013). Local image tagging via graph regularized joint group sparsity. Pattern Recognition, 46(5), 1358-1368.	2013
367	Feature Reduction and Selection for Automatic Image Annotation	Chen, G. B., & Chien, B. C. (2013). Feature Reduction and Selection for Automatic Image Annotation. In Advances in Intelligent Systems and Applications-Volume 1: Proceedings of the International Computer Symposium ICS 2012 Held at Hualien, Taiwan, December 12-14, 2012 (pp. 317-326). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2013
368	Lyric-based automatic music image generator for music browser using scene knowledge	Kasai, H. (2013). Lyric-based automatic music image generator for music browser using scene knowledge. IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics, 59(3), 578-586.	2013
369	Label localization with weakly spatial constrained graph propagation	Yu, L., Liu, J., Xu, C., & Zhou, X. (2013, July). Label localization with weakly spatial constrained graph propagation. In 2013 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2013
370	Unified dictionary learning and region tagging with hierarchical sparse representation	Cao, X., Wei, X., Han, Y., Yang, Y., Sebe, N., & Hauptmann, A. (2013). Unified dictionary learning and region tagging with hierarchical sparse representation. Computer Vision and Image Understanding, 117(8), 934-946.	2013
371	Combination of classification and regression in decision tree for multi-labeling image annotation and retrieval	Fakhari, A., & Moghadam, A. M. E. (2013). Combination of classification and regression in decision tree for multi-labeling image annotation and retrieval. Applied Soft Computing, 13(2), 1292-1302.	2013

372	Tag taxonomy aware dictionary learning for region tagging	Zheng, J., & Jiang, Z. (2013). Tag taxonomy aware dictionary learning for region tagging. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (pp. 369-376).	2013
373	Image annotation by semantic sparse recoding of visual content	Lu, Z., & Peng, Y. (2012, October). Image annotation by semantic sparse recoding of visual content. In Proceedings of the 20th ACM international conference on Multimedia (pp. 499-508).	2012
374	Uso combinado de tecnologías semánticas y análisis visual para la anotación automática de imágenes y su recuperación	Rodríguez-Vaamonde, S., Ruiz-Ibáñez, P., & González-Rodríguez, M. (2012). Uso combinado de tecnologías semánticas y análisis visual para la anotación automática de imágenes y su recuperación. Profesional de la información/Information Professional, 21(1), 27-33.	2012
375	Automated annotation of natural images using an extended annotation model	Mihai, G. A. B. R. I. E. L., & Stanescu, L. I. A. N. A. (2012). Automated annotation of natural images using an extended annotation model. International Journal of Computer Science and Applications.	2012
376	Random forest for image annotation	Fu, H., Zhang, Q., & Qiu, G. (2012). Random forest for image annotation. In Computer Vision-ECCV 2012: 12th European Conference on Computer Vision, Florence, Italy, October 7-13, 2012, Proceedings, Part VI 12 (pp. 86-99). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2012
377	Understanding and predicting importance in images	Berg, A. C., Berg, T. L., Daume, H., Dodge, J., Goyal, A., Han, X., ... & Yamaguchi, K. (2012, June). Understanding and predicting importance in images. In 2012 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (pp. 3562-3569). IEEE.	2012
378	Graph-guided sparse reconstruction for region tagging	Han, Y., Wu, F., Shao, J., Tian, Q., & Zhuang, Y. (2012, June). Graph-guided sparse reconstruction for region tagging. In 2012 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (pp. 2981-2988). IEEE.	2012
379	Noisy tag alignment with image regions	Liu, Y., Liu, J., Li, Z., & Lu, H. (2012, July). Noisy tag alignment with image regions. In 2012 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (pp. 266-271). IEEE.	2012
380	Multi-modal region selection approach for training object detectors	Chatzilari, E., Nikolopoulos, S., Kompatsiaris, Y., & Kittler, J. (2012, June). Multi-modal region selection approach for training object detectors. In Proceedings of the 2nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia Retrieval (pp. 1-8).	2012
381	On the use of conceptual information in a concept-based image indexing and retrieval framework	Jarrar, R., Belkhatir, M., & Messom, C. H. (2011, September). On the use of conceptual information in a concept-based image indexing and retrieval framework. In 2011 18th IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (pp. 2441-2444). IEEE.	2011

382	Fusing object detection and region appearance for image-text alignment	Del Pero, L., Lee, P., Magahern, J., Hartley, E., Barnard, K., Wang, P., ... & Haering, N. (2011, November). Fusing object detection and region appearance for image-text alignment. In Proceedings of the 19th ACM international conference on Multimedia (pp. 1113-1116).	2011
383	Automated annotation system for natural images	Mihai, G., & Stanescu, L. (2011, September). Automated annotation system for natural images. In 2011 Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems (FedCSIS) (pp. 755-762). IEEE.	2011
384	Semi-supervised object recognition using flickr images	Chatzilari, E., Nikolopoulos, S., Papadopoulos, S., Zigkolis, C., & Kompatsiaris, Y. (2011, June). Semi-supervised object recognition using flickr images. In 2011 9th International Workshop on Content-Based Multimedia Indexing (CBMI) (pp. 229-234). IEEE.	2011
385	Automated system for annotating and retrieving images	Mihai, G., Stanescu, L., Burdescu, D. D., & Spahiu, C. S. (2011, November). Automated system for annotating and retrieving images. In 2011 IEEE International Conference on Signal and Image Processing Applications (ICSIPA) (pp. 490-494). IEEE.	2011
386	Tag localization with spatial correlations and joint group sparsity	Yang, Y., Yang, Y., Huang, Z., Shen, H. T., & Nie, F. (2011, June). Tag localization with spatial correlations and joint group sparsity. In CVPR 2011 (pp. 881-888). IEEE.	2011
387	Hierarchical Decision Tree (HDT) Approach for Image Annotation	Fakhari, A., & Eftekhari-Moghaddam, A. M. (2011, November). Hierarchical Decision Tree (HDT) Approach for Image Annotation. In 2011 7th Iranian Conference on Machine Vision and Image Processing (pp. 1-5). IEEE.	2011
388	Multi-Instance Multi-Label Learning for Image Classification with Large Vocabularies.	Yakhnenko, O., & Honavar, V. G. (2011, September). Multi-Instance Multi-Label Learning for Image Classification with Large Vocabularies. In BMVC (pp. 1-12).	2011
389	Custom ontologies for an automated image annotation system	Mihai, G., Stanescu, L., Burdescu, D. D., & Brezovan, M. (2011). Custom ontologies for an automated image annotation system. In Knowledge-Based and Intelligent Information and Engineering Systems: 15th International Conference, KES 2011, Kaiserslautern, Germany, September 12-14, 2011, Proceedings, Part I 15 (pp. 505-515). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2011
390	Large-Scale Text to Image Retrieval Using a Bayesian K-Neighborhood Model	Paredes, R. (2010, August). Large-scale text to image retrieval using a Bayesian K-neighborhood model. In Joint IAPR International Workshops on Statistical Techniques in Pattern Recognition (SPR) and Structural and Syntactic Pattern Recognition (SSPR) (pp. 483-492). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2010
391	Swedish road weather visualization	Lundblad, P., Thoursie, J., & Jern, M. (2010, July). Swedish road weather visualization. In 2010 14th International Conference Information Visualisation (pp. 313-321). IEEE.	2010

392	Seven years of image retrieval evaluation	Clough, P., Müller, H., & Sanderson, M. (2010). Seven years of image retrieval evaluation. In ImageCLEF: Experimental Evaluation in Visual Information Retrieval (pp. 3-18). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2010
393	Multiscale segmentation based on mode-shift clustering	Tarnawski, W., Miroslaw, L., Pawlikowski, R., & Ociepa, K. (2010, October). Multiscale segmentation based on mode-shift clustering. In Proceedings of the International Multiconference on Computer Science and Information Technology (pp. 129-133). IEEE.	2010
394	Special issue on image and video retrieval evaluation	Hanbury, A., Müller, H., & Clough, P. (2010). Special issue on image and video retrieval evaluation. Computer Vision and Image Understanding, 114(4), 409-410.	2010
395	Contextual kernel and spectral methods for learning the semantics of images	Lu, Z., Ip, H. H., & Peng, Y. (2010). Contextual kernel and spectral methods for learning the semantics of images. IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, 20(6), 1739-1750.	2010

16.- Modeling spatial relations for image retrieval by conceptual graphs

Carlos Hernández-Gracidás, L Enrique Sucar, Manuel Montes-y Gómez
2026, First Chilean Workshop on Pattern Recognition

Citas: 5

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Check for Graph-Based Image Retrieval: State of the Art Imane Belahyane (), Mouad Mammass (), Hasna Abioui (), and Ali Idarrou (四) ID 9	Belahyane, I. (2020, July). Check for Graph-Based Image Retrieval: State of the Art Imane Belahyane (), Mouad Mammass (), Hasna Abioui (), and Ali Idarrou (四) ID 9. In Image and Signal Processing: 9th International Conference, ICISP 2020, Marrakesh, Morocco, June 4–6, 2020, Proceedings (Vol. 12119, p. 299). Springer Nature.	2020
2	基于概念图的关联规则知识表示	郭晓波, 赵书良, 刘军丹, 赵娇娇, & 王长宾. (2013). 基于概念图的关联规则知识表示. 计算机科学, 40(8), 261-265.	2013
3	Information Retrieval in XML Document: State of the Art	Belahyane, I., Mammass, M., Abioui, H., & Idarrou, A. (2023, October). Information Retrieval in XML Document: State of the Art. In International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Systems for Sustainable Development (pp. 322-331). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.	2023
4	Graph-Based Image Retrieval: State of the Art	Belahyane, I., Mammass, M., Abioui, H., & Idarrou, A. (2020). Graph-Based Image Retrieval: State of the Art. In Image and Signal Processing: 9th International Conference, ICISP 2020, Marrakesh, Morocco, June 4–6, 2020, Proceedings 9 (pp. 299-307). Springer International Publishing.	2020
5	A knowledge-based image retrieval system integrating semantic and visual features	Allani, O., Zghal, H. B., Mellouli, N., & Akdag, H. (2016). A knowledge-based image retrieval system integrating semantic and visual features. Procedia Computer Science, 96, 1428-1436.	2016

17.- Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval

Hugo Jair Escalante, Jesús A Gonzalez, Carlos A Hernández, Aurelio López, Manuel Montes, Eduardo Morales, Luis E Sucar, Luis Villaseñor-Pineda 2008,

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	RISE: Relevant Image Search Engine	Segarra Querol, F. M. (2011). RISE: Relevant Image Search Engine.	2011
2	A New Framework to Bridge Semantic Gap for Semantics Based Image Retrieval	Rizvi, E. S. S. H. (2014). A New Framework to Bridge Semantic Gap for Semantics Based Image Retrieval. Iqra University Islamabad Campus.	2014

18.- Towards annotation-based query and document expansion for image retrieval

Hugo Jair Escalante, Carlos Hernández, Aurelio López, Heidy Marín, Manuel Montes, Eduardo Morales, Enrique Sucar, Luis Villaseñor 2008,

Citas: 5

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Investigating Methods Of Annotating Lifelogs For Use In Search	Scells, H. (2016). Investigating Methods Of Annotating Lifelogs For Use In Search (Doctoral dissertation, Queensland University of Technology).	2016
2	Identifying important features for graph retrieval	Li, Z., Carberry, S., Fang, H., & McCoy, K. F. (2014, August). Identifying important features for graph retrieval. In Proceedings of COLING 2014, the 25th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: Technical Papers (pp. 600-609).	2014
3	Infographics retrieval: A new methodology	Li, Z., Carberry, S., Fang, H., McCoy, K. F., & Peterson, K. (2014). Infographics retrieval: A new methodology. In Natural Language Processing and Information Systems: 19th International Conference on Applications of Natural Language to Information Systems, NLDB 2014, Montpellier, France, June 18-20, 2014. Proceedings 19 (pp. 101-113). Springer International Publishing.	2014
4	An analysis of photo editors' query formulations for image retrieval	Hung, T. Y. (2012). An analysis of photo editors' query formulations for image retrieval. Journal of Librarianship and Information Studies, 4(1), 13-16.	2012
5	Magma—efficient method for image annotation in low dimensional feature space based on multivariate Gaussian models	Broda, B., Kwasnicka, H., Paradowski, M., & Stanek, M. (2009, October). Magma—efficient method for image annotation in low dimensional feature space based on multivariate Gaussian models. In 2009 International Multiconference on Computer Science and Information Technology (pp. 131-138). IEEE.	2009

19.- TIA-INAOE's Participation at ImageCLEF 2007.

Hugo Jair Escalante, Jesús A González, Carlos A Hernández, Aurelio López-López, Manuel Montes-y-Gómez, Eduardo F Morales, Elias Ruiz, Luis Enrique Sucar, Luis Villaseñor Pineda
2008,

Citas: 8

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Ordenamiento de imagenes recuperadas utilizando un enfoque de fusion de informacion multimodal	GARCIA, R. C. (2010). Ordenamiento de imagenes recuperadas utilizando un enfoque de fusion de informacion multimodal.	2010
2	Framework for Integration of Medical Image and Text-Based Report Retrieval to Support Radiological Diagnosis	Kulkarni, S., Savyanavar, A., Kulkarni, P., Stranieri, A., & Ghorpade, V. (2018). Framework for Integration of Medical Image and Text-Based Report Retrieval to Support Radiological Diagnosis. In Biomedical Signal and Image Processing in Patient Care (pp. 86-122). IGI Global.	2018
3	Object and concept recognition for image retrieval	Nowak, S., Hanbury, A., & Deselaers, T. (2010). Object and concept recognition for image retrieval. In ImageCLEF: Experimental Evaluation in Visual Information Retrieval (pp. 199-219). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2010
4	Performance measures for multilabel evaluation: a case study in the area of image classification	Nowak, S., Lukashevich, H., Dunker, P., & Rüger, S. (2010, March). Performance measures for multilabel evaluation: a case study in the area of image classification. In Proceedings of the international conference on Multimedia information retrieval (pp. 35-44).	2010
5	Overview of the CLEF 2009 large-scale visual concept detection and annotation task	Nowak, S., & Dunker, P. (2009, September). Overview of the CLEF 2009 large-scale visual concept detection and annotation task. In Workshop of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum for European Languages (pp. 94-109). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2009
6	Overview of the ImageCLEFphoto 2007 photographic retrieval task	Grubinger, M., Clough, P., Hanbury, A., & Müller, H. (2008). Overview of the ImageCLEFphoto 2007 photographic retrieval task. In Advances in Multilingual and Multimodal Information Retrieval: 8th Workshop of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum, CLEF 2007, Budapest, Hungary, September 19-21, 2007, Revised Selected Papers 8 (pp. 433-444). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2008
7	A Multimodal Approach to the Medical Retrieval Task using IR-n.	Navarro, S., Munoz, R., & Llopis, F. (2008, September). A Multimodal Approach to the Medical Retrieval Task using IR-n. In CLEF (Working Notes).	2008
8	A Textual Approach Based on Passages Using IR-n in WikipediaMM Task 2008.	Navarro, S., Munoz, R., & Llopis, F. (2008). A Textual Approach Based on Passages Using IR-n in WikipediaMM Task 2008. In CLEF (Working Notes).	2008

20.- Late fusion of heterogeneous methods for multimedia image retrieval

Hugo Jair Escalante, Carlos A Hérnandez, Luis Enrique Sucar, Manuel Montes

2008,

Citas: 88

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	A deep learning approach for image and text classification using neutrosophy	Wajid, M. A., Zafar, A., & Wajid, M. S. (2024). A deep learning approach for image and text classification using neutrosophy. <i>International Journal of Information Technology</i> , 16(2), 853-859.	2024
2	Convolutional neural networks for relevance feedback in content based image retrieval	Lorenzo, P., Luca, P., & Giorgio, G. (2020). Convolutional neural networks for relevance feedback in content based image retrieval. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 79(37-38), 26995-27021.	2020
3	Combinação seletiva não supervisionada de listas ranqueadas aplicada à busca de imagens pelo conteúdo	Valem, L. P. (2019). Combinação seletiva não supervisionada de listas ranqueadas aplicada à busca de imagens pelo conteúdo.	2019
4	Blending the Past and Present of Automatic Image Annotation	Dutta, A. (2019). Blending the Past and Present of Automatic Image Annotation (Doctoral dissertation, International Institute of Information Technology, Hyderabad).	2019
5	Maximizing Insight from Modern Economic Analysis	Antenucci, D. (2018). Maximizing Insight from Modern Economic Analysis (Doctoral dissertation).	2018
6	Пребарување на медицински документи со мултимодални податоци	Китановски, И. (2017). Пребарување на медицински документи со мултимодални податоци (Doctoral dissertation, ФИНКИ, УКИМ, Скопје).	2017
7	Very Fast Image Retrieval	da Silva Romoao, D. A. (2016). Very Fast Image Retrieval.	2016
8	Dissertation/Thesis Approval Form	Aryafar, K. (2015). Dissertation/Thesis Approval Form.	2015
9	Visual Search for Musical Performances and Endoscopic Videos	Carlos, J. R. (2015). Visual Search for Musical Performances and Endoscopic Videos (Doctoral dissertation, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya. Escola Tècnica Superior d'Enginyeria de Telecomunicació de Barcelona. Departament de Teoria del Senyal i Comunicacions, 2015 (Enginyeria de Telecomunicació)).	2015
10	Adaptation of Visual Models with Cross-modal Regularization	Costa Pereira, J. M. C. (2015). Adaptation of Visual Models with Cross-modal Regularization (Doctoral dissertation, UC San Diego).	2015
11	Multimodal Information Retrieval and Classification	Aryafar, K. (2015). Multimodal Information Retrieval and Classification. Drexel University.	2015
12	Visual search for musical performances and endoscopic videos	Roldán Carlos, J. (2015). Visual search for musical performances and endoscopic videos.	2015
13	Adaptation of Visual Models with Cross-modal Regularization	Pereira, J. C. (2015). Adaptation of Visual Models with Cross-modal Regularization. University of California, San Diego.	2015

14	Majority voting re-ranking algorithm for content based-image retrieval	Mosbah, M., & Boucheham, B. (2015). Majority voting re-ranking algorithm for content based-image retrieval. In Metadata and Semantics Research: 9th Research Conference, MTSR 2015, Manchester, UK, September 9-11, 2015, Proceedings 9 (pp. 121-131). Springer International Publishing.	2015
15	annotation automatique d'images	OUIAOURA, M. (2014). annotation automatique d'images.	2014
16	Handling imperfections for multimodal image annotation	Znaidia, A. (2014). Handling imperfections for multimodal image annotation (Doctoral dissertation, Ecole Centrale Paris).	2014
17	Building and Using Knowledge Models for Semantic Image Annotation	Bannour, H. (2013). Building and Using Knowledge Models for Semantic Image Annotation (Doctoral dissertation, Ecole Centrale Paris).	2013
18	Towards Large-Scale Multi-Modal Image Search	Budiková, P. (2013). Towards Large-Scale Multi-Modal Image Search.	2013
19	Effective heterogeneous similarity measure with nearest neighbors for cross-media retrieval	Zhai, X., Peng, Y., & Xiao, J. (2012). Effective heterogeneous similarity measure with nearest neighbors for cross-media retrieval. In Advances in Multimedia Modeling: 18th International Conference, MMM 2012, Klagenfurt, Austria, January 4-6, 2012. Proceedings 18 (pp. 312-322). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2012
20	Multimodal Fusion for Combining Textual and Visual Information in a Semantic Model	Tran, N. K. (2012). Multimodal Fusion for Combining Textual and Visual Information in a Semantic Model.	2012
21	Semantic image representation for visual recognition	Rasiwasia, N. (2011). Semantic image representation for visual recognition. University of California, San Diego.	2011
22	RISE: Relevant Image Search Engine	Segarra Querol, F. M. (2011). RISE: Relevant Image Search Engine.	2011
23	Représentations visuelles de concepts textuels pour la recherche et l'annotation interactives d'images	Van Nguyen, N. (2011). Représentations visuelles de concepts textuels pour la recherche et l'annotation interactives d'images (Doctoral dissertation, Université de La Rochelle).	2011
24	Ordenamiento de imagenes recuperadas utilizando un enfoque de fusion de informacion multimodal	GARCIA, R. C. (2010). Ordenamiento de imagenes recuperadas utilizando un enfoque de fusion de informacion multimodal.	2010
25	Neutrosophic-CNN-based image and text fusion for multimodal classification	Wajid, M. A., Zafar, A., Terashima-Marín, H., & Wajid, M. S. (2023). Neutrosophic-CNN-based image and text fusion for multimodal classification. Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems, 45(1), 1039-1055.	2023
26	Influence of Late Fusion of High-Level Features on User Relevance Feedback for Videos	Khan, O. S., Zahálka, J., & Jónsson, B. P. (2022, October). Influence of Late Fusion of High-Level Features on User Relevance Feedback for Videos. In Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Interactive Multimedia Retrieval (pp. 17-24).	2022
27	Multimodal fusion: a review, taxonomy, open challenges, research roadmap and future directions	Wajid, M. A., & Zafar, A. (2021). Multimodal fusion: a review, taxonomy, open challenges, research roadmap and future directions. Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 45(1), 8.	2021

28	Efficient and effective multi-modal queries through heterogeneous network embedding	Duong, C. T., Nguyen, T. T., Yin, H., Weidlich, M., Mai, T. S., Aberer, K., & Nguyen, Q. V. H. (2021). Efficient and effective multi-modal queries through heterogeneous network embedding. <i>IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering</i> , 34(11), 5307-5320.	2021
29	A multi-stream recurrent neural network for social role detection in multiparty interactions	Zhang, L., & Radke, R. J. (2020). A multi-stream recurrent neural network for social role detection in multiparty interactions. <i>IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing</i> , 14(3), 554-567.	2020
30	Convolutional neural networks for relevance feedback in content based image retrieval: A Content based image retrieval system that exploits convolutional neural ...	Putzu, L., Piras, L., & Giacinto, G. (2020). Convolutional neural networks for relevance feedback in content based image retrieval: A Content based image retrieval system that exploits convolutional neural networks both for feature extraction and for relevance feedback. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 79(37), 26995-27021.	2020
31	Recurrent image annotation with explicit inter-label dependencies	Dutta, A., Verma, Y., & Jawahar, C. V. (2020, August). Recurrent image annotation with explicit inter-label dependencies. In <i>European Conference on Computer Vision</i> (pp. 191-207). Cham: Springer International Publishing.	2020
32	Modality-Dependent Cross-Modal Retrieval Based on Graph Regularization	Wang, G., Ji, H., Kong, D., & Zhang, N. (2020). Modality-Dependent Cross-Modal Retrieval Based on Graph Regularization. <i>Mobile Information Systems</i> , 2020(1), 4164692.	2020
33	Generation of Visual Patterns from BoVW for Image Retrieval using modified Similarity Score Fusion.	Arulmozhi, P., & Abirami, M. (2020). Generation of Visual Patterns from BoVW for Image Retrieval using modified Similarity Score Fusion. <i>Advances in Electrical & Computer Engineering</i> , 20(2).	2020
34	Graph embeddings for one-pass processing of heterogeneous queries	Duong, C. T., Yin, H., Hoang, D., Nguyen, M. H., Weidlich, M., Nguyen, Q. V. H., & Aberer, K. (2020, April). Graph embeddings for one-pass processing of heterogeneous queries. In <i>2020 IEEE 36th International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE)</i> (pp. 1994-1997). IEEE.	2020
35	Multimodal information access and retrieval notable work and milestones	Wajid, M. A., & Zafar, A. (2019, July). Multimodal information access and retrieval notable work and milestones. In <i>2019 10th International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)</i> (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2019
36	Multi-modal multi-layered topic classification model for social event analysis	Chen, Y. H., Yin, C. Y., Lin, Y. J., & Zuo, W. L. (2018). Multi-modal multi-layered topic classification model for social event analysis. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 77, 23291-23315.	2018

37	Ten years of relevance score for content based image retrieval	Putzu, L., Piras, L., & Giacinto, G. (2018). Ten years of relevance score for content based image retrieval. In Machine Learning and Data Mining in Pattern Recognition: 14th International Conference, MLDM 2018, New York, NY, USA, July 15-19, 2018, Proceedings, Part II 14 (pp. 117-131). Springer International Publishing.	2018
38	Cross-media correlation analysis with semi-supervised graph regularization	Zhang, H., & Qi, T. (2018). Cross-media correlation analysis with semi-supervised graph regularization. In Intelligent Computing Theories and Application: 14th International Conference, ICIC 2018, Wuhan, China, August 15-18, 2018, Proceedings, Part I 14 (pp. 254-265). Springer International Publishing.	2018
39	Biomedical compound figure detection using deep learning and fusion techniques	Lee, S. L., & Zare, M. R. (2018). Biomedical compound figure detection using deep learning and fusion techniques. IET Image Processing, 12(6), 1031-1037.	2018
40	Cross-Media Feature Learning Framework with Semi-supervised Graph Regularization	Qi, T., Zhang, H., & Dai, G. (2018). Cross-Media Feature Learning Framework with Semi-supervised Graph Regularization. In Advances in Multimedia Information Processing-PCM 2018: 19th Pacific-Rim Conference on Multimedia, Hefei, China, September 21-22, 2018, Proceedings, Part I 19 (pp. 667-677). Springer International Publishing.	2018
41	Joint graph regularization based modality-dependent cross-media retrieval	Yan, J., Zhang, H., Sun, J., Wang, Q., Guo, P., Meng, L., ... & Dong, X. (2018). Joint graph regularization based modality-dependent cross-media retrieval. Multimedia Tools and Applications, 77, 3009-3027.	2018
42	Cross-media retrieval based on semi-supervised regularization and correlation learning	Zhang, H., Dai, G., Tang, D., & Xu, X. (2018). Cross-media retrieval based on semi-supervised regularization and correlation learning. Multimedia Tools and Applications, 77, 22455-22473.	2018
43	Cross-Media Retrieval via Deep Semantic Canonical Correlation Analysis and Logistic Regression	Zhang, H., & Xia, L. (2018). Cross-Media Retrieval via Deep Semantic Canonical Correlation Analysis and Logistic Regression. In Advances in Multimedia Information Processing-PCM 2018: 19th Pacific-Rim Conference on Multimedia, Hefei, China, September 21-22, 2018, Proceedings, Part III 19 (pp. 123-133). Springer International Publishing.	2018
44	Deep learning—A new era in bridging the semantic gap	Markowska-Kaczmar, U., & Kwaśnicka, H. (2018). Deep learning—A new era in bridging the semantic gap. Bridging the Semantic Gap in Image and Video Analysis, 123-159.	2018
45	Opensea: open search based classification tool	Pogorelov, K., Albisser, Z., Ostroukhova, O., Lux, M., Johansen, D., Halvorsen, P., & Riegler, M. (2018, June). Opensea: open search based classification tool. In Proceedings of the 9th ACM Multimedia Systems Conference (pp. 363-368).	2018

46	Information fusion in content based image retrieval: A comprehensive overview	Piras, L., & Giacinto, G. (2017). Information fusion in content based image retrieval: A comprehensive overview. <i>Information Fusion</i> , 37, 50-60.	2017
47	Multimodal medical image retrieval system	Kitanovski, I., Strezoski, G., Dimitrovski, I., Madjarov, G., & Loskovska, S. (2017). Multimodal medical image retrieval system. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 76, 2955-2978.	2017
48	Deep learning for action and gesture recognition in image sequences: A survey	Asadi-Aghbolaghi, M., Clapés, A., Bellantonio, M., Escalante, H. J., Ponce-López, V., Baró, X., ... & Escalera, S. (2017). Deep learning for action and gesture recognition in image sequences: A survey. <i>Gesture Recognition</i> , 539-578.	2017
49	A support vector approach for cross-modal search of images and texts	Verma, Y., & Jawahar, C. V. (2017). A support vector approach for cross-modal search of images and texts. <i>Computer Vision and Image Understanding</i> , 154, 48-63.	2017
50	Pseudo relevance feedback based on majority voting mechanism	Mosbah, M., & Boucheham, B. (2017). Pseudo relevance feedback based on majority voting mechanism. <i>International Journal of Web Science</i> , 3(1), 58-81.	2017
51	From annotation to computer-aided diagnosis: Detailed evaluation of a medical multimedia system	Riegler, M., Pogorelov, K., Eskeland, S. L., Schmidt, P. T., Albisser, Z., Johansen, D., ... & Lange, T. D. (2017). From annotation to computer-aided diagnosis: Detailed evaluation of a medical multimedia system. <i>ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications, and Applications (TOMM)</i> , 13(3), 1-26.	2017
52	Selection and combination of unsupervised learning methods for image retrieval	Valem, L. P., & Pedronette, D. C. G. (2017, June). Selection and combination of unsupervised learning methods for image retrieval. In <i>Proceedings of the 15th International Workshop on Content-Based Multimedia Indexing</i> (pp. 1-6).	2017
53	Semi-supervised distance consistent cross-modal retrieval	Dong, X., Yu, E., Gao, M., Zhu, L., Sun, J., & Zhang, H. (2017, October). Semi-supervised distance consistent cross-modal retrieval. In <i>Proceedings of the Workshop on Visual Analysis in Smart and Connected Communities</i> (pp. 25-31).	2017
54	Crossmodal network-based distributional semantic models	Iosif, E., & Potamianos, A. (2016, May). Crossmodal network-based distributional semantic models. In <i>Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'16)</i> (pp. 3973-3979).	2016
55	Learning robust uniform features for cross-media social data by using cross autoencoders	Guo, Q., Jia, J., Shen, G., Zhang, L., Cai, L., & Yi, Z. (2016). Learning robust uniform features for cross-media social data by using cross autoencoders. <i>Knowledge-Based Systems</i> , 102, 64-75.	2016
56	Sense adaptive multimodal information fusion: A proposed model	Bokhari, M. U., & Hasan, F. (2016, March). Sense adaptive multimodal information fusion: A proposed model. In <i>2016 3rd International Conference on Computing for Sustainable Global Development (INDIACom)</i> (pp. 3976-3979). IEEE.	2016
57	A deep semantic framework for multimodal representation learning	Wang, C., Yang, H., & Meinel, C. (2016). A deep semantic framework for multimodal representation learning. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 75, 9255-9276.	2016

58	Computer aided disease detection system for gastrointestinal examinations	Riegler, M., Pogorelov, K., Markussen, J., Lux, M., Stensland, H. K., de Lange, T., ... & Eskeland, S. L. (2016, May). Computer aided disease detection system for gastrointestinal examinations. In Proceedings of the 7th international conference on Multimedia Systems (pp. 1-4).	2016
59	Multiple object detection for smart TV shopping video using point to point feature based SURF method	Chhabra, D., & Verma, A. (2016, August). Multiple object detection for smart TV shopping video using point to point feature based SURF method. In 2016 International Conference on Inventive Computation Technologies (ICICT) (Vol. 2, pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2016
60	Event video retrieval using global and local descriptors in visual domain	Carlos, J. R., Lux, M., Giro-i-Nieto, X., Munoz, P., & Anagnostopoulos, N. (2015, June). Event video retrieval using global and local descriptors in visual domain. In 2015 13th International Workshop on Content-Based Multimedia Indexing (CBMI) (pp. 1-4). IEEE.	2015
61	Unsupervised visual and textual information fusion in cbmir using graph-based methods	Ah-Pine, J., Csurka, G., & Clinchant, S. (2015). Unsupervised visual and textual information fusion in cbmir using graph-based methods. ACM Transactions on Information Systems (TOIS), 33(2), 1-31.	2015
62	Semi-supervised cross-media feature learning with unified patch graph regularization	Peng, Y., Zhai, X., Zhao, Y., & Huang, X. (2015). Semi-supervised cross-media feature learning with unified patch graph regularization. IEEE transactions on circuits and systems for video technology, 26(3), 583-596.	2015
63	Cross-modal retrieval: A pairwise classification approach	Menon, A. K., Surian, D., & Chawla, S. (2015, June). Cross-modal retrieval: A pairwise classification approach. In Proceedings of the 2015 SIAM International Conference on Data Mining (pp. 199-207). Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics.	2015
64	Visual information retrieval in endoscopic video archives	Carlos, J. R., Lux, M., Giro-i-Nieto, X., Munoz, P., & Anagnostopoulos, N. (2015, June). Visual information retrieval in endoscopic video archives. In 2015 13th International Workshop on Content-Based Multimedia Indexing (CBMI) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2015
65	Spectral multimodal hashing and its application to multimedia retrieval	Zhen, Y., Gao, Y., Yeung, D. Y., Zha, H., & Li, X. (2015). Spectral multimodal hashing and its application to multimedia retrieval. IEEE Transactions on cybernetics, 46(1), 27-38.	2015
66	Topic Correlations for Cross-Modal Multimedia Information Retrieval.	Yu, J., & Qin, Z. (2015). Topic Correlations for Cross-Modal Multimedia Information Retrieval. Gate to Computer Science & Research, 4.	2015
67	Multimodal distributional semantics	Bruni, E., Tran, N. K., & Baroni, M. (2014). Multimodal distributional semantics. Journal of artificial intelligence research, 49, 1-47.	2014

68	A Review Paper on Multimedia Information Retrieval based on Late Semantic Fusion Approaches	Kolhe, H. J., & Manekar, A. (2014). A Review Paper on Multimedia Information Retrieval based on Late Semantic Fusion Approaches. <i>International Journal of Computer Applications</i> , 975, 8887.	2014
69	A new multimodal fusion method based on association rules mining for image retrieval	Alghamdi, R. A., Taileb, M., & Ameen, M. (2014, April). A new multimodal fusion method based on association rules mining for image retrieval. In <i>MELECON 2014-2014 17th IEEE Mediterranean Electrotechnical Conference</i> (pp. 493-499). IEEE.	2014
70	Unsupervised visual and textual information fusion in multimedia retrieval-a graph-based point of view	Csurka, G., Ah-Pine, J., & Clinchant, S. (2014). Unsupervised visual and textual information fusion in multimedia retrieval-a graph-based point of view. <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:1401.6891</i> .	2014
71	Towards semantic image retrieval using multimodal fusion with association rules mining	Alghamdi, R. A., & Taileb, M. (2014). Towards semantic image retrieval using multimodal fusion with association rules mining. In <i>Human Interface and the Management of Information. Information and Knowledge Design and Evaluation: 16th International Conference, HCI International 2014, Heraklion, Crete, Greece, June 22-27, 2014. Proceedings, Part I 16</i> (pp. 407-418). Springer International Publishing.	2014
72	On the role of correlation and abstraction in cross-modal multimedia retrieval	Pereira, J. C., Coviello, E., Doyle, G., Rasiwasia, N., Lanckriet, G. R., Levy, R., & Vasconcelos, N. (2013). On the role of correlation and abstraction in cross-modal multimedia retrieval. <i>IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence</i> , 36(3), 521-535.	2013
73	Cross-media retrieval by intra-media and inter-media correlation mining	Zhai, X., Peng, Y., & Xiao, J. (2013). Cross-media retrieval by intra-media and inter-media correlation mining. <i>Multimedia systems</i> , 19, 395-406.	2013
74	Codage des modèles de tags.	Znaidia, A., Shabou, A., Le Borgne, H., & Hudelot, C. (2013). Codage des modèles de tags. <i>Rev. d'Intelligence Artif.</i> , 27(1), 39-63.	2013
75	Multimedia information retrieval based on late semantic fusion approaches: Experiments on a wikipedia image collection	Benavent, X., Garcia-Serrano, A., Granados, R., Benavent, J., & de Ves, E. (2013). Multimedia information retrieval based on late semantic fusion approaches: Experiments on a wikipedia image collection. <i>IEEE Transactions on Multimedia</i> , 15(8), 2009-2021.	2013
76	Learning cross-media joint representation with sparse and semisupervised regularization	Zhai, X., Peng, Y., & Xiao, J. (2013). Learning cross-media joint representation with sparse and semisupervised regularization. <i>IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology</i> , 24(6), 965-978.	2013
77	Cross-media retrieval by cluster-based correlation analysis	Ma, D., Zhai, X., & Peng, Y. (2013, September). Cross-media retrieval by cluster-based correlation analysis. In <i>2013 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing</i> (pp. 3986-3990). IEEE.	2013

78	Parallel field alignment for cross media retrieval	Mao, X., Lin, B., Cai, D., He, X., & Pei, J. (2013, October). Parallel field alignment for cross media retrieval. In Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on multimedia (pp. 897-906).	2013
79	Heterogeneous metric learning with joint graph regularization for cross-media retrieval	Zhai, X., Peng, Y., & Xiao, J. (2013, June). Heterogeneous metric learning with joint graph regularization for cross-media retrieval. In Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 1198-1204).	2013
80	Multimodal Queries to Access Multimedia Information Sources: First Steps	Martínez, Á., Lana Serrano, S., Martínez-Fernández, J. L., & Martínez, P. (2012). Multimodal Queries to Access Multimedia Information Sources: First Steps. In User Centric Media: Second International ICST Conference, UCMedia 2010, Palma de Mallorca, Spain, September 1-3, 2010. Revised Selected Papers 2 (pp. 35-40). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2012
81	Leveraging high-level and low-level features for multimedia event detection	Jiang, L., Hauptmann, A. G., & Xiang, G. (2012, October). Leveraging high-level and low-level features for multimedia event detection. In Proceedings of the 20th ACM international conference on Multimedia (pp. 449-458).	2012
82	Distributional semantics with eyes: Using image analysis to improve computational representations of word meaning	Bruni, E., Uijlings, J., Baroni, M., & Sebe, N. (2012, October). Distributional semantics with eyes: Using image analysis to improve computational representations of word meaning. In Proceedings of the 20th ACM international conference on Multimedia (pp. 1219-1228).	2012
83	Prise en compte de l'imperfection des tags pour la classification sémantique d'images	Znaidia, A., Le Borgne, H., Hudelot, C., & Popescu, A. (2012, January). Prise en compte de l'imperfection des tags pour la classification sémantique d'images. In RFA 2012 (Reconnaissance des Formes et Intelligence Artificielle) (pp. 978-2).	2012
84	Interactive Image Retrieval	Toselli, A. H., Vidal, E., Casacuberta, F., Toselli, A. H., Vidal, E., & Casacuberta, F. (2011). Interactive Image Retrieval. Multimodal Interactive Pattern Recognition and Applications, 209-226.	2011
85	Semantic combination of textual and visual information in multimedia retrieval	Clinchant, S., Ah-Pine, J., & Csurka, G. (2011, April). Semantic combination of textual and visual information in multimedia retrieval. In Proceedings of the 1st ACM international conference on multimedia retrieval (pp. 1-8).	2011
86	A relevant image search engine with late fusion: mixing the roles of textual and visual descriptors	Segarra, F. M., Leiva, L. A., & Paredes, R. (2011, February). A relevant image search engine with late fusion: mixing the roles of textual and visual descriptors. In Proceedings of the 16th international conference on Intelligent user interfaces (pp. 455-456).	2011
87	Sndocrank: a social network-based video search ranking framework	Gou, L., Chen, H. H., Kim, J. H., Zhang, X., & Giles, C. L. (2010, March). Sndocrank: a social network-based video search ranking framework. In Proceedings of the international conference on multimedia information retrieval (pp. 367-376).	2010

88	A new approach to cross-modal multimedia retrieval	Rasiwasia, N., Costa Pereira, J., Coviello, E., Doyle, G., Lanckriet, G. R., Levy, R., & Vasconcelos, N. (2010, October). A new approach to cross-modal multimedia retrieval. In Proceedings of the 18th ACM international conference on Multimedia (pp. 251-260).	2010
----	--	--	------

21.- Overview of the ImageCLEF 2007 object retrieval task

Thomas Deselaers, Allan Hanbury, Ville Viitaniemi, András Benczúr, Mátyás Brendel, Bálint Daróczy, Hugo Jair Escalante Balderas, Theo Gevers, Carlos Arturo Hernández Gracidas, Steven CH Hoi, Jorma Laaksonen, Mingjing Li, Heidy Marisol Marin Castro, Hermann Ney, Xiaoguang Rui, Nicu Sebe, Julian Stöttinger, Lei Wu
2007,

Citas: 9

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	What Happened in CLEF For Another While?	Ferro, N. (2024, September). What Happened in CLEF... For Another While?. In International Conference of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum for European Languages (pp. 3-57). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.	2024
2	Pressure as a non-dominant hand input modality for bimanual interaction techniques on touchscreen tablets	McLachlan, R. D. (2015). Pressure as a non-dominant hand input modality for bimanual interaction techniques on touchscreen tablets (Doctoral dissertation, University of Glasgow).	2015
3	Ambiguous Proximity Distribution	Wang, Q., & Li, Y. (2014). Ambiguous Proximity Distribution. In Intelligent Computing Methodologies: 10th International Conference, ICIC 2014, Taiyuan, China, August 3-6, 2014. Proceedings 10 (pp. 409-421). Springer International Publishing.	2014
4	What Happened in CLEF For a While?	Ferro, N. (2019, August). What Happened in CLEF For a While?. In International Conference of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum for European Languages (pp. 3-45). Cham: Springer International Publishing.	2019
5	Image retrieval evaluation in specific domains	Piras, L., Caputo, B., Dang-Nguyen, D. T., Riegler, M., & Halvorsen, P. (2019). Image retrieval evaluation in specific domains. Information Retrieval Evaluation in a Changing World: Lessons Learned from 20 Years of CLEF, 275-305.	2019
6	CLEF 15th birthday: Past, present, and future	Ferro, N. (2014, December). CLEF 15th birthday: Past, present, and future. In ACM SIGIR Forum (Vol. 48, No. 2, pp. 31-55). New York, NY, USA: ACM.	2014
7	Revisiting the feature and Content gap for landmark-Based and Image-to-Image Retrieval in Medical CBIR	Greenspan, H. (2009). Revisiting the feature and Content gap for landmark-Based and Image-to-Image Retrieval in Medical CBIR. International Journal of Healthcare Information Systems and Informatics (IJHISI), 4(1), 68-87.	2009

8	X-ray image categorization and retrieval using patch-based visualwords representation	Avni, U., Greenspan, H., Sharon, M., Konen, E., & Goldberger, J. (2009, June). X-ray image categorization and retrieval using patch-based visualwords representation. In 2009 IEEE International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging: From Nano to Macro (pp. 350-353). IEEE.	2009
9	University and hospitals of geneva participating at imageclef 2007	Zhou, X., Gobeill, J., Ruch, P., & Müller, H. (2008). University and hospitals of geneva participating at imageclef 2007. In Advances in Multilingual and Multimodal Information Retrieval: 8th Workshop of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum, CLEF 2007, Budapest, Hungary, September 19-21, 2007, Revised Selected Papers 8 (pp. 649-656). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2008

22.- Markov random fields and spatial information to improve automatic image annotation

Carlos Hernández-Gracidas, L Enrique Sucar
2007,

Citas: 19

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Contributions to collaborative clustering and its potential applications on very high resolution satellite images	Sublime, J. (2016). Contributions to collaborative clustering and its potential applications on very high resolution satellite images (Doctoral dissertation, Université Paris Saclay (COMUE)).	2016
2	These de doctorat de l'Université Paris-Saclay préparéea AgroParisTech	Sublime, M. J. (2016). These de doctorat de l'Université Paris-Saclay préparéea AgroParisTech (Doctoral dissertation, Université Paris 13).	2016
3	Towards better privacy preservation by detecting personal events in photos shared within online social networks	Raad, E. (2015). Towards better privacy preservation by detecting personal events in photos shared within online social networks (Doctoral dissertation, Laboratoire Electronique, Informatique et Image (LE2i)(Dijon, Côte d'Or; Auxerre, Yonne; Chalon-sur-Saône, Saône-et-Loire; Le Creusot, Saône-et-Loire)).	2015
4	A new energy model for the hidden markov random fields	Sublime, J., Cornuéjols, A., & Bennani, Y. (2014). A new energy model for the hidden markov random fields. In Neural Information Processing: 21st International Conference, ICONIP 2014, Kuching, Malaysia, November 3-6, 2014. Proceedings, Part II 21 (pp. 60-67). Springer International Publishing.	2014
5	Semantic Multimodelling Search & Retrieval	Aslam, N. (2011). Semantic Multimodelling Search & Retrieval.	2011
6	基于关键词的图像标注综述	郭乔进, 丁轶, & 李宁. (2011). 基于关键词的图像标注综述. 计算机工程与应用, 47(30), 155-158.	2011
7	Semantic multimedia modelling & interpretation for search & retrieval	Aslam, N. (2011). Semantic multimedia modelling & interpretation for search & retrieval (Doctoral dissertation, Middlesex University).	2011

8	Ontology-based image annotation	Yuee, L. (2010). Ontology-based image annotation (Doctoral dissertation, Queensland University of Technology).	2010
9	Assessing the role of spatial relations for the object recognition task	Morales-González, A., & García-Reyes, E. (2010). Assessing the role of spatial relations for the object recognition task. In Progress in Pattern Recognition, Image Analysis, Computer Vision, and Applications: 15th Iberoamerican Congress on Pattern Recognition, CIARP 2010, Sao Paulo, Brazil, November 8-11, 2010. Proceedings 15 (pp. 549-556). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2010
10	Semantics and statistics for automated image annotation	Coto, A. L. (2010). Semantics and statistics for automated image annotation. Open University (United Kingdom).	2010
11	Intra and inter spatial color descriptor for content based image retrieval	Rejeb, I. B., Ouni, S., & Zagrouba, E. (2019, November). Intra and inter spatial color descriptor for content based image retrieval. In 2019 IEEE/ACS 16th International Conference on Computer Systems and Applications (AICCSA) (pp. 1-8). IEEE.	2019
12	The spatial relation features for describing objects relationships within image	Saad, M. N., Muda, Z., Ashaari, N. S., & Hamid, H. A. (2015, August). The spatial relation features for describing objects relationships within image. In 2015 International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Informatics (ICEEI) (pp. 126-131). IEEE.	2015
13	A survey of refining image annotation techniques	ping Tian, D. (2014). A survey of refining image annotation techniques. International Journal of Multimedia and Ubiquitous Engineering, 9(3), 117-128.	2014
14	Fusing PLSA model and Markov random fields for automatic image annotation	田东平. (2014). Fusing PLSA model and Markov random fields for automatic image annotation. High Technology Letters, 20(4), 409-414.	2014
15	Un nouveau modèle d'énergie pour les champs aléatoires de Markov cachés	Sublime, J., Bennani, Y., & Cornuéjols, A. (2014). Un nouveau modèle d'énergie pour les champs aléatoires de Markov cachés. In 21. Rencontres de la Société Francophone de Classification SFC'14 (p. np).	2014
16	Simple object recognition based on spatial relations and visual features represented using irregular pyramids	Morales-González, A., & García-Reyes, E. B. (2013). Simple object recognition based on spatial relations and visual features represented using irregular pyramids. Multimedia tools and applications, 63(3), 875-897.	2013
17	Document ranking refinement using a Markov random field model	Villatoro, E., Juárez, A., Montes, M., Villasenor, L., & Sucar, L. E. (2012). Document ranking refinement using a Markov random field model. Natural Language Engineering, 18(2), 155-185.	2012

18	Hierarchical markov random fields with irregular pyramids for improving image annotation	Morales-González, A., García-Reyes, E., & Sucar, L. E. (2012). Hierarchical markov random fields with irregular pyramids for improving image annotation. In Advances in Artificial Intelligence-IBERAMIA 2012: 13th Ibero-American Conference on AI, Cartagena de Indias, Colombia, November 13-16, 2012. Proceedings 13 (pp. 521-530). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2012
19	Image retrieval using markov random fields and global image features	Llorente, A., Manmatha, R., & Rüger, S. (2010, July). Image retrieval using markov random fields and global image features. In Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Image and Video Retrieval (pp. 243-250).	2010

DOCUMENTOS CON CO - CITAS GOOGLE SCHOLAR

1.- Stable Numerical Identification of Sources in Non-Homogeneous Media

José Julio Conde Mones, Carlos Arturo Hernández Gracidas, María Monserrat Morín Castillo, José Jacobo Oliveros Oliveros, Lorenzo Héctor Juárez Valencia
2022, Mathematics

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Título: IDENTIFICACIÓN DE PARÁMETROS DEL MODELO SIR	Oliveros, J. J. O. (2024). Título: IDENTIFICACIÓN DE PARÁMETROS DEL MODELO SIR (Doctoral dissertation, BENEMÉRITA UNIVERSIDAD AUTÓNOMA DE PUEBLA).	2024
2	Stable identification of sources located on the cerebral cortex from EEG over the scalp	Cruz, J. Á. A., Castillo, M. M. M., Oliveros, J. J. O., & Arias, J. E. M. G. (2023). Stable identification of sources located on the cerebral cortex from EEG over the scalp. Revista Mexicana de Física, 69(5 Sep-Oct), 050702-1.	2023

2.- Stable Identification of Sources Located on Interface of Nonhomogeneous Media

José Julio Conde Mones, Emmanuel Roberto Estrada Aguayo, José Jacobo Oliveros Oliveros, Carlos Arturo Hernández Gracidas, María Monserrat Morín Castillo
2021, Mathematics

Citas: 6

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Título: IDENTIFICACIÓN DE PARÁMETROS DEL MODELO SIR	Oliveros, J. J. O. (2024). Título: IDENTIFICACIÓN DE PARÁMETROS DEL MODELO SIR (Doctoral dissertation, BENEMÉRITA UNIVERSIDAD AUTÓNOMA DE PUEBLA).	2024
2	FPGA-Based Hardware Implementation of a Stable Inverse Source Problem Algorithm in a Non-homogeneous Circular Region	Oliveros, J. J. O., Sánchez, J. R. C., Gracidas, C. A. H., Castillo, M. M. M., & Mones, J. J. C. (2023). FPGA-Based Hardware Implementation of a Stable Inverse Source Problem Algorithm in a Non-homogeneous Circular Region.	2023
3	FPGA-Based Hardware Implementation of a Stable Inverse Source Problem Algorithm in a Non-Homogeneous Circular Region	Oliveros-Oliveros, J. J., Conde-Sánchez, J. R., Hernández-Gracidas, C. A., Morín-Castillo, M. M., & Conde-Mones, J. J. (2024). FPGA-Based Hardware Implementation of a Stable Inverse Source Problem Algorithm in a Non-Homogeneous Circular Region. Applied Sciences, 14(4), 1388.	2024
4	Stable identification of sources located on the cerebral cortex from EEG over the scalp	Cruz, J. Á. A., Castillo, M. M. M., Oliveros, J. J. O., & Arias, J. E. M. G. (2023). Stable identification of sources located on the cerebral cortex from EEG over the scalp. Revista Mexicana de Física, 69(5 Sep-Oct), 050702-1.	2023

5	Analysis of dipolar sources in the solution of the Electroencephalographic Inverse Problem	Morín-Castillo, M. M., Arriaga-Hernández, J., Cuevas-Otahola, B., & Oliveros-Oliveros, J. J. (2022). Analysis of dipolar sources in the solution of the Electroencephalographic Inverse Problem. <i>Mathematics</i> , 10(11), 1926.	2022
6	Stable Numerical Identification of Sources in Non-Homogeneous Media	Conde Mones, J. J., Hernández Gracidas, C. A., Morín Castillo, M. M., Oliveros Oliveros, J. J., & Juárez Valencia, L. H. (2022). Stable Numerical Identification of Sources in Non-Homogeneous Media. <i>Mathematics</i> , 10(15), 2726.	2022

3.- An FPGA-based analysis of trade-offs in the presence of ill-conditioning and different precision levels in computations

Ignacio Algreto-Badillo, José Julio Conde-Mones, Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, María Monserrat Morín-Castillo, José Jacobo Oliveros-Oliveros, Claudia Feregrino-Urbe
2020, PloS one

Citas: 3

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Título: IDENTIFICACIÓN DE PARÁMETROS DEL MODELO SIR	Oliveros, J. J. O. (2024). Título: IDENTIFICACIÓN DE PARÁMETROS DEL MODELO SIR (Doctoral dissertation, BENEMÉRITA UNIVERSIDAD AUTÓNOMA DE PUEBLA).	2024
2	FPGA-Based Hardware Implementation of a Stable Inverse Source Problem Algorithm in a Non-homogeneous Circular Region	Oliveros, J. J. O., Sánchez, J. R. C., Gracidas, C. A. H., Castillo, M. M. M., & Mones, J. J. C. (2023). FPGA-Based Hardware Implementation of a Stable Inverse Source Problem Algorithm in a Non-homogeneous Circular Region.	2023
3	FPGA-Based Hardware Implementation of a Stable Inverse Source Problem Algorithm in a Non-Homogeneous Circular Region	Oliveros-Oliveros, J. J., Conde-Sánchez, J. R., Hernández-Gracidas, C. A., Morín-Castillo, M. M., & Conde-Mones, J. J. (2024). FPGA-Based Hardware Implementation of a Stable Inverse Source Problem Algorithm in a Non-Homogeneous Circular Region. <i>Applied Sciences</i> , 14(4), 1388.	2024

4.- On-road obstacle detection video system for traffic accident prevention

Luis Alberto Morales-Rosas, Ignacio Algreto-Badillo, Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, Héctor Rodríguez-Rangel, Mariana Lobato-Baez
2026, Recent Advances in Machine Learning and Soft Computing, of Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Real time FPGA-ANN architecture for outdoor obstacle detection focused in road safety	Algreto-Badillo, I., Morales-Rosales, L. A., Hernandez-Gracidas, C. A., Cruz-Victoria, J. C., Pacheco-Bautista, D., & Morales-Sandoval, M. (2019). Real time FPGA-ANN architecture for outdoor obstacle detection focused in road safety. <i>Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems</i> , 36(5), 4425-4436.	2019

5.- Self-navigating Robot based on Fuzzy Rules Designed for Autonomous Wheelchair Mobility

Ignacio Algreto-Badillo, Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, Luis Alberto Morales-Rosales, Ernesto Cortés-Pérez, J Jesús Arellano Pimentel
2016, International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security

Citas: 1

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Reactive Obstacle-Avoidance Systems for Wheeled Mobile Robots Based on Artificial Intelligence	Medina-Santiago, A., Morales-Rosales, L. A., Hernández-Gracidas, C. A., Algreto-Badillo, I., Pano-Azucena, A. D., & Orozco Torres, J. A. (2021). Reactive Obstacle-Avoidance Systems for Wheeled Mobile Robots Based on Artificial Intelligence. Applied Sciences, 11(14), 6468.	2021

6.- The Windows-Users and-Intruder simulations Logs dataset (WUIL): An experimental framework for masquerade detection mechanisms

J Benito Camiña, Carlos Hernández-Gracidas, Raúl Monroy, Luis Trejo
2014, Expert Systems with Applications

Citas: 8

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Towards a masquerade detection system based on user's tasks	Camina, J. B., Rodríguez, J., & Monroy, R. (2014). Towards a masquerade detection system based on user's tasks. In Research in Attacks, Intrusions and Defenses: 17th International Symposium, RAID 2014, Gothenburg, Sweden, September 17-19, 2014. Proceedings 17 (pp. 447-465). Springer International Publishing.	2014
2	Cluster validation in clustering-based one-class classification	Rodríguez-Ruiz, J., Monroy, R., Medina-Pérez, M. A., Loyola-González, O., & Cervantes, B. (2019). Cluster validation in clustering-based one-class classification. Expert Systems, 36(6), e12475.	2019
3	Classification based on multivariate contrast patterns	Cañete-Sifuentes, L., Monroy, R., Medina-Pérez, M. A., Loyola-González, O., & Voronisky, F. V. (2019). Classification based on multivariate contrast patterns. IEEE Access, 7, 55744-55762.	2019
4	Bagging-RandomMiner: A one-class classifier for file access-based masquerade detection	Camiña, J. B., Medina-Pérez, M. A., Monroy, R., Loyola-González, O., Villanueva, L. A. P., & Gurrola, L. C. G. (2019). Bagging-RandomMiner: A one-class classifier for file access-based masquerade detection. Machine vision and applications, 30, 959-974.	2019
5	Experimenting with masquerade detection via user task usage	Rodríguez, J., Cañete, L., Monroy, R., & Medina-Pérez, M. A. (2017). Experimenting with masquerade detection via user task usage. International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM), 11, 771-784.	2017
6	Bagging-TPMiner: a classifier ensemble for masquerader detection based on typical objects	Medina-Pérez, M. A., Monroy, R., Camiña, J. B., & García-Borroto, M. (2017). Bagging-TPMiner: a classifier ensemble for masquerader detection based on typical objects. Soft Computing, 21, 557-569.	2017

7	Temporal and spatial locality: an abstraction for masquerade detection	Camiña, J. B., Monroy, R., Trejo, L. A., & Medina-Pérez, M. A. (2016). Temporal and spatial locality: an abstraction for masquerade detection. <i>IEEE transactions on information Forensics and Security</i> , 11(9), 2036-2051.	2016
8	Ensemble of one-class classifiers for personal risk detection based on wearable sensor data	Rodríguez, J., Barrera-Animas, A. Y., Trejo, L. A., Medina-Pérez, M. A., & Monroy, R. (2016). Ensemble of one-class classifiers for personal risk detection based on wearable sensor data. <i>Sensors</i> , 16(10), 1619.	2016

7.- Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations

Carlos Arturo Hernández-Gracidas, Luis Enrique Sucar, Manuel Montes-y-Gómez
2013, Multimedia tools and applications

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Exploiting label semantic relatedness for unsupervised image annotation with large free vocabularies	Pellegrin, L., Escalante, H. J., Montes-y-Gómez, M., & González, F. A. (2019). Exploiting label semantic relatedness for unsupervised image annotation with large free vocabularies. <i>Multimedia Tools and Applications</i> , 78, 19641-19662.	2019
2	Markov random fields	Sucar, L. E., & Sucar, L. E. (2015). Markov random fields. <i>Probabilistic Graphical Models: Principles and Applications</i> , 83-99.	2015

8.- Data fusion and label weighting for image retrieval based on spatio-conceptual information

Carlos Hernández-Gracidas, Antonio Juárez, L Enrique Sucar, Manuel Montes-y-Gómez, Luis Villaseñor
2010,

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations	GRACIDAS, C. A. H., Succar, L. E. S., & Montes, M. (2013). Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations.	2013
2	Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations	Hernández-Gracidas, C. A., Sucar, L. E., & Montes-y-Gómez, M. (2013). Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations. <i>Multimedia tools and applications</i> , 62, 479-505.	2013

9.- The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark

Hugo Jair Escalante, Carlos A Hernández, Jesus A Gonzalez, Aurelio López-López, Manuel Montes, Eduardo F Morales, L Enrique Sucar, Luis Villaseñor, Michael Grubinger
2010, Computer Vision and Image Understanding

Citas: 21

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Visión de Alto Nivel	Sucar, L. E. (2018). Visión de Alto Nivel.	2018
2	Automated detection of hummingbirds in images: a deep learning approach	Serrano, S. A., Benítez-Jimenez, R., Nunez-Rosas, L., del Coro Arizmendi, M., Greeney, H., Reyes-Meza, V., ... & Escalante, H. J. (2018). Automated detection of hummingbirds in images: a deep learning approach. In Pattern Recognition: 10th Mexican Conference, MCP R 2018, Puebla, Mexico, June 27-30, 2018, Proceedings 10 (pp. 155-166). Springer International Publishing.	2018
3	Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations	GRACIDAS, C. A. H., Succar, L. E. S., & Montes, M. (2013). Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations.	2013
4	On the SAIAPR TC-12 benchmark	Escalante, H. J., Montes, M., & Sucar, E. On the SAIAPR TC-12 benchmark. In Proceedings of the 2009 Theseus/ImageCLEF Workshop (pp. 44-51).	2009
5	Academic competitions	Escalante, H. J., & Kruchinina, A. (2023). Academic competitions. arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.00268.	2023
6	Image annotation as Text-Image matching: Challenge design and results	Pellegrin, L., Loyola-González, O., Ortiz-Bejar, J., Medina-Pérez, M. A., Gutiérrez-Rodríguez, A. E., Tellez, E. S., ... & Escalante, H. J. (2019). Image annotation as Text-Image matching: Challenge design and results. Computación y Sistemas, 23(4), 1305-1321.	2019
7	Exploiting label semantic relatedness for unsupervised image annotation with large free vocabularies	Pellegrin, L., Escalante, H. J., Montes-y-Gómez, M., & González, F. A. (2019). Exploiting label semantic relatedness for unsupervised image annotation with large free vocabularies. Multimedia Tools and Applications, 78, 19641-19662.	2019
8	Overview of the 2017 redica text-image matching (ricatim) challenge	Pellegrin, L., Escalante, H. J., Morales, A., Morales, E. F., & Reyes-García, C. A. (2017, November). Overview of the 2017 redica text-image matching (ricatim) challenge. In 2017 IEEE International Autumn Meeting on Power, Electronics and Computing (ROPEC) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	2017
9	Multidimensional hierarchical classification	Hernández, J., Sucar, L. E., & Morales, E. F. (2014). Multidimensional hierarchical classification. Expert systems with applications, 41(17), 7671-7677.	2014
10	Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations	Hernández-Gracidas, C. A., Sucar, L. E., & Montes-y-Gómez, M. (2013). Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations. Multimedia tools and applications, 62, 479-505.	2013

11	A hybrid global-local approach for hierarchical classification	Hernandez, J. N., Sucar, L. E., & Morales, E. F. (2013, May). A hybrid global-local approach for hierarchical classification. In The Twenty-Sixth International FLAIRS Conference.	2013
12	Multimodal markov random field for image reranking based on relevance feedback	Chávez, R. O., Escalante, H. J., Montes-y-Gómez, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2013). Multimodal markov random field for image reranking based on relevance feedback. <i>International Scholarly Research Notices</i> , 2013(1), 428746.	2013
13	Semantic cohesion for image annotation and retrieval	Escalante, H. J., Sucar, L. E., & Montes-y-Gómez, M. (2012). Semantic cohesion for image annotation and retrieval. <i>Computación y Sistemas</i> , 16(1), 121-125.	2012
14	Multimodal indexing based on semantic cohesion for image retrieval	Escalante, H. J., Montes, M., & Sucar, E. (2012). Multimodal indexing based on semantic cohesion for image retrieval. <i>Information retrieval</i> , 15, 1-32.	2012
15	Cohesión semántica para la anotación y recuperación de imágenes	Escalante, H. J., Sucar, L. E., & Montes-y-Gómez, M. (2012). Cohesión semántica para la anotación y recuperación de imágenes. <i>Computación y Sistemas</i> , 16(1), 121-125.	2012
16	An energy-based model for region-labeling	Escalante, H. J., Montes-y-Gómez, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2011). An energy-based model for region-labeling. <i>Computer vision and image understanding</i> , 115(6), 787-803.	2011
17	Simplified quadtree image segmentation for image annotation	Marquez, G. R. C., Escalante, H. J., & Sucar, L. E. (2010). Simplified quadtree image segmentation for image annotation. <i>Proceedings of the 1st Automatic Image Annotation and Retrieval Workshop</i> , 2011, 24-34.	2010
18	Data fusion and label weighting for image retrieval based on spatio-conceptual information	Hernández-Gracidas, C., Juárez, A., Sucar, L. E., Montes-y-Gómez, M., & Villaseñor, L. (2010). Data fusion and label weighting for image retrieval based on spatio-conceptual information. In <i>Adaptivity, Personalization and Fusion of Heterogeneous Information</i> (pp. 76-79).	2010
19	Modeling spatial relations for image retrieval by conceptual graphs	Hernández-Gracidas, C., Sucar, L. E., & Montes-y Gómez, M. (2009). Modeling spatial relations for image retrieval by conceptual graphs. In <i>Proceedings of the first Chilean workshop on pattern recognition</i> .	2009
20	On multimedia image retrieval baselines	Escalante, H. J., Montes, M., & Sucar, E. (2009). On multimedia image retrieval baselines. In <i>Proceedings of the CIMAT-PI'09 workshop</i> , Guanajuato, Mexico.	2009
21	Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante, H. J., Gonzalez, J. A., Hernández, C. A., López, A., Montes, M., Morales, E., ... & Villaseñor-Pineda, L. (2009). Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval. In <i>Evaluating Systems for Multilingual and Multimodal Information Access: 9th Workshop of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum, CLEF 2008</i> , Aarhus, Denmark, September 17-19, 2008, Revised Selected Papers 9 (pp. 669-676). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2009

10.- Modeling spatial relations for image retrieval by conceptual graphs

Carlos Hernández-Gracidas, L Enrique Sucar, Manuel Montes-y Gómez
2026, First Chilean Workshop on Pattern Recognition

Citas: 3

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations	GRACIDAS, C. A. H., Succar, L. E. S., & Montes, M. (2013). Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations.	2013
2	Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations	Hernández-Gracidas, C. A., Sucar, L. E., & Montes-y-Gómez, M. (2013). Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations. Multimedia tools and applications, 62, 479-505.	2013
3	Data fusion and label weighting for image retrieval based on spatio-conceptual information	Hernández-Gracidas, C., Juárez, A., Sucar, L. E., Montes-y-Gómez, M., & Villaseñor, L. (2010). Data fusion and label weighting for image retrieval based on spatio-conceptual information. In Adaptivity, Personalization and Fusion of Heterogeneous Information (pp. 76-79).	2010

11.- Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval

Hugo Jair Escalante, Jesús A Gonzalez, Carlos A Hernández, Aurelio López, Manuel Montes, Eduardo Morales, Luis E Sucar, Luis Villaseñor-Pineda
2008,

Citas: 2

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Multimodal markov random field for image reranking based on relevance feedback	Chávez, R. O., Escalante, H. J., Montes-y-Gómez, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2013). Multimodal markov random field for image reranking based on relevance feedback. International Scholarly Research Notices, 2013(1), 428746.	2013
2	Multimodal indexing based on semantic cohesion for image retrieval	Escalante, H. J., Montes, M., & Sucar, E. (2012). Multimodal indexing based on semantic cohesion for image retrieval. Information retrieval, 15, 1-32.	2012

12.- Towards annotation-based query and document expansion for image retrieval

Hugo Jair Escalante, Carlos Hernández, Aurelio López, Heidy Marín, Manuel Montes, Eduardo Morales, Enrique Sucar, Luis Villaseñor
2008,

Citas: 4

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Multimodal indexing based on semantic cohesion for image retrieval	Escalante, H. J., Montes, M., & Sucar, E. (2012). Multimodal indexing based on semantic cohesion for image retrieval. Information retrieval, 15, 1-32.	2012

2	Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante, H. J., Gonzalez, J. A., Hernández, C. A., López, A., Montes, M., Morales, E., ... & Villaseñor-Pineda, L. (2009). Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval. In Evaluating Systems for Multilingual and Multimodal Information Access: 9th Workshop of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum, CLEF 2008, Aarhus, Denmark, September 17-19, 2008, Revised Selected Papers 9 (pp. 669-676). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2009
3	TIA-INAOE's Participation at ImageCLEF 2007.	Escalante, H. J., González, J. A., Hernández, C. A., López-López, A., Montes-y-Gómez, M., Morales, E. F., ... & Pineda, L. V. (2008, September). TIA-INAOE's Participation at ImageCLEF 2007. In CLEF (Working Notes).	2008
4	Late fusion of heterogeneous methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante, H. J., Hernández, C. A., Sucar, L. E., & Montes, M. (2008, October). Late fusion of heterogeneous methods for multimedia image retrieval. In Proceedings of the 1st ACM international conference on Multimedia information retrieval (pp. 172-179).	2008

13.- TIA-INAOE's Participation at ImageCLEF 2007.

Hugo Jair Escalante, Jesús A González, Carlos A Hernández, Aurelio López-López, Manuel Montes-y-Gómez, Eduardo F Morales, Elias Ruiz, Luis Enrique Sucar, Luis Villaseñor Pineda
2008,

Citas: 5

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Using a markov random field for image re-ranking based on visual and textual features	Chávez, R. O., Montes, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2011). Using a markov random field for image re-ranking based on visual and textual features. <i>Computación y Sistemas</i> , 14(4), 393-404.	2011
2	Utilizando un campo aleatorio de Markov para el reordenamiento de imágenes basado en atributos visuales y textuales	Chávez, R. O., Montes, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2011). Utilizando un campo aleatorio de Markov para el reordenamiento de imágenes basado en atributos visuales y textuales. <i>Computación y Sistemas</i> , 14(4), 393-404.	2011
3	Image Re-Ranking Based on Relevance Feedback Combining Internal and External Similarities	García, R. O. C., Montes, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2010, May). Image Re-Ranking Based on Relevance Feedback Combining Internal and External Similarities. In Twenty-Third International FLAIRS Conference.	2010
4	Selecting the n-top retrieval result lists for an effective data fusion	Juárez-González, A., Montes-y-Gómez, M., Villaseñor-Pineda, L., Pinto-Avendaño, D., & Pérez-Coutiño, M. (2010). Selecting the n-top retrieval result lists for an effective data fusion. In Computational Linguistics and Intelligent Text Processing: 11th International Conference, CICLing 2010, Iași, Romania, March 21-27, 2010. Proceedings 11 (pp. 580-589). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2010

5	On the Selection of the Best Retrieval Result Per Query-An Alternative Approach to Data Fusion-	Juárez-González, A., Montes-y-Gómez, M., Villaseñor-Pineda, L., & Ortíz-Arroyo, D. (2009). On the Selection of the Best Retrieval Result Per Query-An Alternative Approach to Data Fusion-. In Flexible Query Answering Systems: 8th International Conference, FQAS 2009, Roskilde, Denmark, October 26-28, 2009. Proceedings 8 (pp. 111-121). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2009
---	---	--	------

14.- Late fusion of heterogeneous methods for multimedia image retrieval

Hugo Jair Escalante, Carlos A Hernández, Luis Enrique Sucar, Manuel Montes
2008,

Citas: 6

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Learning to assemble classifiers via genetic programming	Acosta-Mendoza, N., Morales-Reyes, A., Escalante, H. J., & Gago-Alonso, A. (2014). Learning to assemble classifiers via genetic programming. International Journal of Pattern Recognition and Artificial Intelligence, 28(07), 1460005.	2014
2	Multimodal markov random field for image reranking based on relevance feedback	Chávez, R. O., Escalante, H. J., Montes-y-Gómez, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2013). Multimodal markov random field for image reranking based on relevance feedback. International Scholarly Research Notices, 2013(1), 428746.	2013
3	Using a markov random field for image re-ranking based on visual and textual features	Chávez, R. O., Montes, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2011). Using a markov random field for image re-ranking based on visual and textual features. Computación y Sistemas, 14(4), 393-404.	2011
4	Utilizando un campo aleatorio de Markov para el reordenamiento de imágenes basado en atributos visuales y textuales	Chávez, R. O., Montes, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2011). Utilizando un campo aleatorio de Markov para el reordenamiento de imágenes basado en atributos visuales y textuales. Computación y Sistemas, 14(4), 393-404.	2011
5	Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante, H. J., Gonzalez, J. A., Hernández, C. A., López, A., Montes, M., Morales, E., ... & Villaseñor-Pineda, L. (2009). Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval. In Evaluating Systems for Multilingual and Multimodal Information Access: 9th Workshop of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum, CLEF 2008, Aarhus, Denmark, September 17-19, 2008, Revised Selected Papers 9 (pp. 669-676). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2009
6	TIA-INAOE's Participation at ImageCLEF 2007.	Escalante, H. J., González, J. A., Hernández, C. A., López-López, A., Montes-y-Gómez, M., Morales, E. F., ... & Pineda, L. V. (2008, September). TIA-INAOE's Participation at ImageCLEF 2007. In CLEF (Working Notes).	2008

15.- Overview of the ImageCLEF 2007 object retrieval task

Thomas Deselaers, Allan Hanbury, Ville Viitaniemi, András Benczúr, Mátyás Brendel, Bálint Daróczy, Hugo Jair Escalante Balderas, Theo Gevers, Carlos Arturo Hernández Gracidas, Steven CH Hoi, Jorma Laaksonen, Mingjing Li, Heidy Marisol Marin Castro, Hermann Ney, Xiaoguang Rui, Nicu Sebe, Julian Stöttinger, Lei Wu
2007,

Citas: 10

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	SZTAKI@ ImageCLEF 2008 Visual Concept Detection	Brendel, B. D. Z. F. M. SZTAKI@ ImageCLEF 2008 Visual Concept Detection.	2008
2	Etiquetado automático de imágenes digitales mediante un algoritmo de ensamble semi-supervisado	Castro, H. M. M. (2008). Etiquetado automático de imágenes digitales mediante un algoritmo de ensamble semi-supervisado.	2008
3	Overview of the ImageCLEFmed 2007 Medical Retrieval and Medical Annotation Tasks	Müllerab, H., Deselaersc, T., Desernod, T. M., Kalpathy-Cramere, J., Kime, E., & Hershe, W. Overview of the ImageCLEFmed 2007 Medical Retrieval and Medical Annotation Tasks.	2007
4	Object and concept recognition for image retrieval	Nowak, S., Hanbury, A., & Deselaers, T. (2010). Object and concept recognition for image retrieval. In ImageCLEF: Experimental Evaluation in Visual Information Retrieval (pp. 199-219). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2010
5	The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark	Escalante, H. J., Hernández, C. A., Gonzalez, J. A., López-López, A., Montes, M., Morales, E. F., ... & Grubinger, M. (2010). The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark. Computer vision and image understanding, 114(4), 419-428.	2010
6	Automatic medical image annotation in ImageCLEF 2007: Overview, results, and discussion	Deselaers, T., Deserno, T. M., & Müller, H. (2008). Automatic medical image annotation in ImageCLEF 2007: Overview, results, and discussion. Pattern Recognition Letters, 29(15), 1988-1995.	2008
7	The visual concept detection task in ImageCLEF 2008	Deselaers, T., & Hanbury, A. (2008, September). The visual concept detection task in ImageCLEF 2008. In Workshop of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum for European Languages (pp. 531-538). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2008
8	Overview of the ImageCLEFmed 2007 medical retrieval and medical annotation tasks	Müller, H., Deselaers, T., Deserno, T. M., Kalpathy-Cramer, J., Kim, E., & Hersh, W. (2008). Overview of the ImageCLEFmed 2007 medical retrieval and medical annotation tasks. In Advances in Multilingual and Multimodal Information Retrieval: 8th Workshop of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum, CLEF 2007, Budapest, Hungary, September 19-21, 2007, Revised Selected Papers 8 (pp. 472-491). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2008

9	Overview of the ImageCLEF 2007 Medical Retrieval and Annotation Tasks.	Müller, H., Deselaers, T., Kim, E., Kalpathy-Cramer, J., Deserno, T. M., & Hersh, W. R. (2007, January). Overview of the ImageCLEF 2007 Medical Retrieval and Annotation Tasks. In CLEF (Working Notes).	2007
10	Thoughts on evaluation of image retrieval inspired by ImageCLEF 2007 object retrieval task	Viitaniemi, V., & Laaksonen, J. (2007, September). Thoughts on evaluation of image retrieval inspired by ImageCLEF 2007 object retrieval task. In Workshop on Image and Video Retrieval Evaluation (p. 20).	2007

16.- Markov random fields and spatial information to improve automatic image annotation

Carlos Hernández-Gracidas, L Enrique Sucar
2007,

Citas: 13

	Document Title	Cite	Year
1	Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations	GRACIDAS, C. A. H., Succar, L. E. S., & Montes, M. (2013). Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations.	2013
2	Image annotation by a hierarchical and iterative combination of recognition and segmentation	Morales-González, A., García-Reyes, E., & Sucar, L. E. (2018). Image annotation by a hierarchical and iterative combination of recognition and segmentation. <i>International Journal of Pattern Recognition and Artificial Intelligence</i> , 32(01), 1860014.	2018
3	Markov random fields	Sucar, L. E., & Sucar, L. E. (2015). Markov random fields. <i>Probabilistic Graphical Models: Principles and Applications</i> , 83-99.	2015
4	Improving image segmentation for boosting image annotation with irregular pyramids	Morales-González, A., García-Reyes, E., & Sucar, L. E. (2013). Improving image segmentation for boosting image annotation with irregular pyramids. In <i>Progress in Pattern Recognition, Image Analysis, Computer Vision, and Applications: 18th Iberoamerican Congress, CIARP 2013, Havana, Cuba, November 20-23, 2013, Proceedings, Part I 18</i> (pp. 399-406). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2013
5	Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations	Hernández-Gracidas, C. A., Sucar, L. E., & Montes-y-Gómez, M. (2013). Improving image retrieval by using spatial relations. <i>Multimedia tools and applications</i> , 62, 479-505.	2013
6	Multimodal markov random field for image reranking based on relevance feedback	Chávez, R. O., Escalante, H. J., Montes-y-Gómez, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2013). Multimodal markov random field for image reranking based on relevance feedback. <i>International Scholarly Research Notices</i> , 2013(1), 428746.	2013
7	Multi-class particle swarm model selection for automatic image annotation	Escalante, H. J., Montes, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2012). Multi-class particle swarm model selection for automatic image annotation. <i>Expert Systems with Applications</i> , 39(12), 11011-11021.	2012
8	An energy-based model for region-labeling	Escalante, H. J., Montes-y-Gómez, M., & Sucar, L. E. (2011). An energy-based model for region-labeling. <i>Computer vision and image understanding</i> , 115(6), 787-803.	2011

9	The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark	Escalante, H. J., Hernández, C. A., Gonzalez, J. A., López-López, A., Montes, M., Morales, E. F., ... & Grubinger, M. (2010). The segmented and annotated IAPR TC-12 benchmark. <i>Computer vision and image understanding</i> , 114(4), 419-428.	2010
10	Modeling spatial relations for image retrieval by conceptual graphs	Hernández-Gracidas, C., Sucar, L. E., & Montes-y Gómez, M. (2009). Modeling spatial relations for image retrieval by conceptual graphs. In <i>Proceedings of the first Chilean workshop on pattern recognition</i> .	2009
11	Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante, H. J., Gonzalez, J. A., Hernández, C. A., López, A., Montes, M., Morales, E., ... & Villaseñor-Pineda, L. (2009). Annotation-based expansion and late fusion of mixed methods for multimedia image retrieval. In <i>Evaluating Systems for Multilingual and Multimodal Information Access: 9th Workshop of the Cross-Language Evaluation Forum, CLEF 2008, Aarhus, Denmark, September 17-19, 2008, Revised Selected Papers 9</i> (pp. 669-676). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	2009
12	TIA-INAOE's Participation at ImageCLEF 2007.	Escalante, H. J., González, J. A., Hernández, C. A., López-López, A., Montes-y-Gómez, M., Morales, E. F., ... & Pineda, L. V. (2008, September). TIA-INAOE's Participation at ImageCLEF 2007. In <i>CLEF (Working Notes)</i> .	2008
13	Late fusion of heterogeneous methods for multimedia image retrieval	Escalante, H. J., Hernández, C. A., Sucar, L. E., & Montes, M. (2008, October). Late fusion of heterogeneous methods for multimedia image retrieval. In <i>Proceedings of the 1st ACM international conference on Multimedia information retrieval</i> (pp. 172-179).	2008